
**A FRAMEWORK TO OVERCOME INTERNATIONALISATION BARRIERS
ENCOUNTERED BY SMALL, AND MEDIUM SIZED ENTERPRISES: INSIGHTS
FROM CAMEROON'S MANUFACTURING INDUSTRY.**

A Thesis
Presented to School of
Business Enterprise

BY

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**Thesis submitted to the University of the West of Scotland in Partial Fulfilment of the
Requirements for Degree of Doctorate in Business Administration (DBA)**

JUNE 15, 2020

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Dedication

To God Almighty, who through all bounds of leaps and faith guided me in tough times, I overcame with the strength God provided for me to keep walking during this difficult project until the finish line despite the distraction's life offered. Also in memory of my Mother Ajap Vivian Forbin, my Grandmother Elizabeth Ajoche Forbin and Grandfather Dr.Nkengbeng Forbin, though not here today but your memory lives and the process you brought me to where I am today I am indeed grateful.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

There are many people that helped me through the process, and I would like to give gratitude and acknowledge to them.

Firstly, I would like to express my gratitude to my Director of Studies, Dr Daba Chowdhury. He took upon his shoulders the responsibility to guide me in every step of the DBA journey. There are times when I felt like giving up, but my DOS was unwavering. He encouraged me to keep on working hard and stay focused.

I am immensely thankful to my Assessor, Dr Eleri Jones, and my Supervisor Dr David Chitakunye. Their astute comments on my research thesis, helped to enhance the quality of the study. To Dr. David Chitakunye, thank you once again for taking time to read through my thesis. Your SPSS workshops opened my eyes to the realities of quantitative data analysis.

I would also like to thank my cohorts, and the entire staff at the business school at University of the West of Scotland that made it possible for wonderful and positive working atmosphere. To the lecturers at the taught process of the course, Professor Paul, Dr Lawrence, Dr Kumar, and the entire student administrative team, thank you for your support and advice. To the participating firms, this study would not have been completed without your voluntary engagement, and willingness to share valuable insights

I would like to say a big thank you to my family, most especially my parents (Mr and Mrs Biami), aunties, and uncles, cousins; especially Ajua Columbus Formin for the financial and moral support. If there are two people that have faith in my ability and always continues to encourage me to write are my very good friends Ayuk Tarhbey and Ingrid Tiege I would like to thank my other friends and buddies that constantly invited me out for fun and through friendly chats encouraged me not to give up. In memory also to my grandfather, my grandmother, and my mother, though you could not be here to see me achieve this, I want to acknowledge you and I say thank you.

ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to determine the challenges of the internationalization process of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) within the context of Cameroon and develop some guidelines that can help SMEs to internationalise their products and services. The intention was to provide insight insights about the internationalisation process of SMEs from Cameroon. The contextual literature reveals that Cameroon's export performance is very low. Within this, there is silence of the role played by SMEs within the export performance. Further, export activities of SMEs are relegated to a category of secondary theoretical interest. The focus of SME manufacturing has been on the domestic market, rather than the international market. Yet, the same SMEs have potential to manufacture products that can meet international standards. Therefore, there is a greater to understand and the internationalization process of manufacturing SMEs in Cameroon.

The study used convenience, and purposive sampling techniques to help arrive at those respondents of interest more effectively and efficiently. Survey data was collected from 112 firms, whilst qualitative data was collected from 16 firms. The estimated Cronbach's alpha statistic for the 44-item inventory items for the survey instrument was .889, indicating that 88.9% of the variability in the composite score of the 44 Likert scaled items would be considered as true score variance or internally consistent reliable variance.

The survey results revealed that the reason for SMEs to remain operating in the domestic market experience gained over time, low financial involvement, and competitive advantage. It also emerged that internationalisation barriers are concentrated around knowledge, human resources, product quality, and bureaucracy, among others. It was also found that firms enter the international market using unconventional means, such as the networks of friends and family. Others enter international markets without any documented strategies.

Respondents made some suggestions that helped to inform managerial recommendations and guidelines. An integrated theoretical framework was developed, and this could help managers enhance their chances of success when they engage with the internationalisation process.

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CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.0 Introduction

This chapter introduces the thesis, outlines the research problem; presents the research aim, research questions, and objectives. Further, the chapters provide a justification of the study, defines key terms, and provides a methodological summary. It also provides an overview of the thesis and concludes by providing a summary of the thesis.

1.1 Background to the research

Given the forces of globalisation, expanding a business across national borders is often a relevant opportunity for small enterprises to achieve new goals by increasing their customer's base, and entering new markets (Zahra, 2006; Anderson, 2009). The decision to go into a foreign market can be complex and is not prone to a one size fits all technique. Enterprises irrespective of their sizes, tend to identify their own styles and pattern to suit their expansion strategy beyond national borders (Leonidou, et al., 2007; Hutchinson, et al., 2005; Weiland, 2015)

Extant studies suggest that there are different reasons why a business will make the international investment decision (Hall & Cook, 2009; Hashai, N, 2009) The motives for internationalisation are linked to one or three of these economic factors, that is, the business scale, scope, and location (Chetty & Agndal, 2007; Chetty & Campbell-Hunt, 2003; Sousa & Coelho, 2008) Essentially due to the experiential development effects of cross-border activities, and the established capacity of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) to influence economic growth from national, regional till global heights (European, 2008), enterprises are now more encouraged to access the global markets. This is illustrated in figure 1.1.

Figure 1. 1: Internationalisation motives

Source: adapted from (Anderson & Gatignon, 1989)

The global market for FDI has encouraged SMEs to take their activities to international markets. However, these SMEs often face challenges that affect their profits, and take high risks (Sutton, 2014). Previous studies suggest specific methods that these firms must follow, no matter if they adopted the best plans (Chetty & Agndal, 2007). Others suggest that expertise is built through a gradual process with the intention of managing risks within the short-term and long-term (Coviello & Munro, 1997). In fact, SMEs have been previously classified as passive business operations than active players in the international milieu (Cardoza & Fornes, 2009). However, more recent studies suggest that this understanding is changing (Gao, 2004).

There is an increased growth share of FDI across many countries. In Cameroon, this has gone to considerable level with a record of over 35% (UNCTAD, 2015). In 2004. The level of growth was 10%. In fact, only nine out of twenty of the foreign investors were from small emerging economies (UNCTAD, 2015). It is worth noting that the increase in FDI was partially a result of SMEs engaging in foreign operations, through greenfield investments, mergers, and acquisitions.

Among the emerging economies, Asia has been a significant example of growth and international investment, while the Caribbean, Latin America and Africa have very little investment in international markets. Countries, with rapid international emerging growth of foreign direct investment outflows include China, Russian Federation, Republic of Korea, Singapore, Kuwait, Chile, and Taiwan province of China (UNCTAD, 2014). Figure 1.2 depicts the world's largest investment group, indicating a third of the total overall investment of internationalization by SMEs from Asia increased by 29% to \$432billion in 2014. The widespread growth included all major Asian economies and their sub-regions. There was an increase in China's growth to become the largest foreign investor after United States (UNCTAD, 2014)

Figure 1. 2: OFDI flows by economies and regional group

Source: (UNCTAD, 2015)

1.1.1 Standard of Comparison of Sub-Saharan (SSA) internationalization

Current growth in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) has been slow. More recently, big African economies including, South Africa, Nigeria, Ghana, and Cameroon, experienced a recession (IMF, 2016b), and this impacted on both FDI inflows and outflows. The global pandemic has even made conditions worse for these economies (IMF, 2016b).

The situation of SSA show a progressive variation of growth advancement. Studies from 2016 projected the challenging macroeconomic conditions, and this has forced countries to adapt to low income revenues. The biggest economy in SSA, Nigeria, decreased by 1.7% in 2016. This was caused by a disruption of oil production, devaluation of foreign currency, and low investment. South Africa, which is the third largest, experienced uncertainties. This made it difficult to achieve growth. Consequently, their GDP reduced to 1.2% in 2016 (IMF, 2016b). On the other hand, Cameroon is the largest economy in central Africa (CEMAC).

Rapid increase of internationalization continues among African countries. However, this is affected by socio-economic barriers, high foreign integration, invisible trade barriers, as well as a lack of internationalisation strategy on the part of SMEs. It is also worth noting that in Cameroon, the GDP has declined since 2016. This has been caused by increased instability, political barriers. This has affected the internationalisation of SME activities. And yet, there is a dearth of studies that focus on the barriers facing small and medium enterprises within Cameroon to internationalise their activities (IMF, 2014a). On the contrary, there is an increasing number of international enterprises, whether large or small, encroaching on the Cameroonian market, forcing many small enterprises in Cameroon to be less competitive. There is a need for SMEs in Cameroon to be outward oriented, and explore opportunities of entering foreign markets, and thus competing in the global marketplace. This area still needs more focused attention.

The literature suggests that globalisation provides important changes in contemporary times with significant increase in the emerging economies (Fayolle & Liñán, 2014). Studies have focused more on enterprises from established/developed economies, and how they mitigate challenges and competition in foreign markets (Fayolle & Liñán, 2014). Apparently, the landscape for competition in the foreign or external markets was carried out by most big firms in the past (McDougall & Oviatt, 2005).

Notwithstanding, there is an increase of global participation of African business within international markets. In fact, African SMEs do not only limit their internationalization within the African continent but have expanded to other continents. Studies shows that in 2012 a significant investment was seen in other parts of the world. For example, a cumulative figure of \$14.2billion in China, and over 43% increase of \$9.9billion of investment in Asia (Peng, et al., 2008; Philips, et al., 2009). China's top investors from Africa include South Africa, Nigeria, Mauritius Seychelles (Ramamurti, 2008). Notably, Cameroonian SMEs are missing within these statistics.

This veracity is even grimmer for Cameroon, which is the largest economy in CEMAC zone, due to an ongoing civil war. In fact, conflicts, destruction, starvation, political unrest, and instability, continues to affect infrastructure, and international trade (Ramamurti, 2004). Communication systems have been affected, and sectors such as the oil, textile, and metal industries have seen a downfall of its manufacturing capacity. This affects growth, development, as well as FDI outflows and inflows (Porter, 1980; Jolly, et al., 1992; OECD, 2018; Ayittey & Goerge, 1992; WorldBank, 2014)

1.1.2 Cameroon's Trends and Challenges

Historically, Cameroon was jointly administered as a French and British colony and gained its independence on 1 January 1960. Cameroon had a population of around 20 million in 2011, with 57 % of the population living in urban areas (Aaby & Slater, 1989). As in many Sub-Saharan African countries, Cameroon's population is becoming very young with 41 % of the population aged below 14 years (Bigsten & Söderbom, 2006).

The World Bank data reveal that the GDP per capita of Cameroon in 1960 was higher than that of Thailand (Aaby & Slater, 1989). However, as of 2017, the GDP per capita was than that of Thailand by 22%. This is cause for concern and indicates that there must be a turnaround strategy somewhere within the Cameroon economy. This concern is reinforced by the fact that

foreign direct investment (FDI) reached its highest of \$740 million in 2009, and by 2016 it had fallen by 47.7% to \$501 million, putting Cameroon behind its neighbours and peers Chad, Gabon, and DR Congo (WorldBank, 2013).

One of the major challenges of internationalisation for Africa's SMEs is the low GDP per capita. For instance, Africa's GDP per capita in 2013 was \$3,221, as compared to \$29,570 for Europe, \$31,533 for Oceania, \$27,249 for Americas, and \$8,622 for Asia (World Bank, 2013). And yet, the general trend of international operations of SMEs spurred from the boom of globalization. In fact, globalisation has largely affected SMEs as opposed to the larger firms. Of interest is that SMEs have the highest share in the international market (WEF, 2016; WorldBank, 2013; Gao, 2004)

Figure 1. 3: Cameroon's economic growth (GDP) per capita

Source: World Economic Forum (WEF, 2016)

Cameroon began to actively seek FDI's in the 20th century and increased this process at the turn of the 21st Century, as illustrated in figure 1.3. This framework is focused on large scale capital projects. The economy was largely reliant on export of few agricultural products. The tiny industrial sector, dominated by French capital, was mainly involved in the transformation of agricultural produce for export (IMF, 2014a)

Over two decades after its independence, Cameroon was one of the most affluent African nations. However, a decline in the prices of agricultural produce in the 1980's negatively affected Cameroon's export-driven economy. This was worsened by poor monetary policies. It is at this juncture that Cameroon turned to the economic prescriptions proposed by the World Bank, and the IMF (WEF, 2018; Amal & Filho, 2010). However, these economic prescriptions brought more harm than good to the Cameroonian economy (WorldBank, 2014), as illustrated in table 1.1.

Table 1. 1: Cameroon's economic indicators under SAP

Redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original table can be found at Worldbank.org.

Source: World Bank (World integrated trade solution)

Cameroon is the 8 largest exporters of oil on the African continent, with much large market size compared to its sub-Saharan counterparts. The microeconomic environment, when compared to other countries in Africa has shown good performance., Nonetheless, Cameroon faced challenging economic situations resulting in the devaluation of its currency in 2016. This also affected Cameroon's global competitiveness, reduced to a ranking of 138th position from 119th in 2016 (WEF, 2016).

The global competitiveness index includes indicators such as infrastructure, institution, educational growth, financial growth, technological growth, labour market, efficiency, innovation, goods and supply, health, and microeconomic environment. This is illustrated in figure 1.4. These indicators are deduced into sub-indexes of basic requirements, efficiency enhancers, innovation, and sophistication factors (WEF, 2016).

Figure 1. 4: WEF index Framework of Global competitiveness

Source: *World economic Forum* (WEF, 2016)

As illustrated figure 1.5, from the WEF’s analysis of the country’s specifics on CGI, Cameroon’s sub scores are higher than the expected SSA average score. It has a good score on 1-7 best, with GCI of 3.7 and ranked 116 in the market. The sub index shows the institutional pillar to be at 3.5, whilst infrastructure is very poor with a score of 2. 5. The microeconomic environment is 4.4, health and primary education stands at 4.7. The higher education score is 3.2, whilst the labour market score is 4.1. Finally, the financial market development stands at 3.5. These indicators illustrate the inherent problems within the Cameroonian economy. Of concern is that these problems affect SMEs’ engagement in internationalisation activities.

Figure 1. 5: Cameroon's competitive index, 2014 - 2015

Source: World Economic Forum (WEF, 2016)

Given the global competitive stands, the strengths of Cameroon’s microeconomic environment and the size of the market, there is need for development and growth across the 12 pillar sectors. There is a need for policy makers to take strategic measures that will enhance Cameroon’s competitiveness. The poor performance in the governance board illustrates the challenges in internationalization of SMEs (Welch & Welch, 2009). Figure 1.6 illustrates the challenging factors faced by CEO’s and entrepreneurs in doing business in Cameroon. Access to finance, and poor infrastructures are amongst the key areas of concern. Similarly, the level of education of the work force in Cameroon is poor, and this is of concern. Further, poor governance and corruption are other significant factors that impact on the competitiveness of business in Cameroon (WEF, 2016). It is within the realm of these problematic factors that SMEs must engage in the internationalisation process and compete effectively.

Figure 1. 6: Most problematic factors of doing business in Cameroon

Redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in the Africa Competitiveness Report, 2015.

Sources: Adopted from the Africa Competitiveness Report, (2015)

1.2 Research Problem Statement

The internationalisation of SMEs has gained attention across many countries. The globalisation drive has brought about increased activities of SMEs across national borders. However, international activities of SMEs are more common amongst SMEs in developed nations than those in emerging economies (Harvie, et al., 2013). Previous studies have focused more on the internationalization of MNEs (multi-national enterprises) from advanced economies. The literature reveals that previous studies in this area have been informed by different theories, such as Uppsala theory, OLI paradigm, stage theory amongst others. Whilst studies have also focused attention on the internationalization and market entry mode (Ramamurti, 2008; Peng, et al., 2008; Sterne, et al., 2016), there has been less attention on the entry mode strategies adopted by SMEs (Cardoza & Fornes, 2009). For instance, (Dunning, 1980) OLI investment growth strategy illustrates foreign investment by countries which are classified developed or advanced economies, and lower stage for less developed economies (Buckley, 1989).

There has been a shift in the pattern by SMEs in the emerging economy (Dunning,2000). For example, in the 1990's, most investors such as the Chinese, sought for natural resources in

Africa, which was their motivation for foreign investment (Axelsson & Easton, 1992). However, in the 2000s, the Chinese gained access to cheap labour market with low production costs in Africa (Aldrich, et al., 2006). Another issue that is essential is resource seeking, it is an important driver that make SMEs to embark of foreign activities.

Hence, there is a need to comprehend the internationalisation of SMEs in Cameroon. The literature suggests that an important aspect for SMEs internationalisation is to eradicate the “small market” effect syndrome and increase the capital income of the domestic market from the revenue gain in the international market (Acedo & Jones, 2007). However, only few SMEs in Cameroon have managed to internationalise their businesses. Some have also tried to internationalise and failed. Failure by the SMEs in Cameroon to extend their business across borders has created a myriad of problems in the domestic market. These problems have culminated in low income growth, incapacity to support downstream industries, high joblessness, and unforeseen difficulties (UNCTAD, 2015).

1.3 Purpose of the Study

Despite increased activities across borders by SMEs, very little focus is placed on SMEs in developing economies. Further, theories of internationalisation have continued to focus on the context of SMEs in developed economies, thereby ignoring the contextual issues of those SMEs in developing countries such as Cameroon. The failure of previous studies to capture the contextual understandings of internationalisation of SMEs in developing economies has proven to be a theoretical weakness in the field.

The contextual literature reveals that Cameroon’s international performance is very low. Within the contextual literature, there is silence on the role played by SMEs in foreign investment. Further, foreign activities of SMEs are relegated to a category of secondary theoretical interest. The focus of SME manufacturing has been on the domestic market, rather

than the international market. Yet, the same SMEs have potential to manufacture products that can meet international standards. Therefore, there is great degree of facet on the internationalization growth process of Manufacturing SMEs in Cameroon

The purpose of the study is to determine the process of internationalization and the challenges faced by small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) within the context of Cameroon. THE study attempts to answer the overreaching questions if Cameroon manufacturing SMEs adopt similar internationalization path as other emerging economy using specific variables and framework significant to the Cameroon market? Uppsala model amongst others is essential in market entry strategy. Ultimately, the study intends to draw from the findings, and then develop some guidelines that can help SMEs to internationalise their products.

1.3.1 Research Objectives

The research objectives are:

- 1) To critically review the literature on the internationalisation process of SMEs and identify gaps in knowledge.
- 2) To establish the perceptions and impact of managers on Market entry mode.
- 3) To determine the internal and external factors that affect the internationalisation of SMEs.
- 4) To develop guidelines and recommendation of internationalization for future research, policy makers and managers.

1.3.2 Research Questions

The research questions are:

1. What does the literature say about the internationalisation process of SMEs, and what are the gaps in knowledge?
2. What are manager's perceptions on market entry mode?
3. What are the internal and external factors that affect the internationalisation of SMEs?
4. What guidelines can be developed to help SMEs in Cameroon to overcome international Barriers?

1.4 Significance of the study

The literature suggests that a firms' internationalisation is essential for a country's economic growth (Hausmann, et al., 2007). Consistent with this, the growth in the economies of most industrialised nations over the past three decades is a result of their abilities to attain sustainable manufactured output and internationalisation (Fisher, et al., 2007). The idea of producing and distributing products and services globally has also helped to improve living standards in some countries.

This has also helped firms to produce products and services that meet internationally recognised quality standards. The ability to meet these international quality standards has often been used as a source of competitive advantage by large multinational firms. Within this, the literature finds that the sub-Saharan African (SSA) economic trade standard is highly dependent on international activities (export and import) of unprocessed raw materials that slow the nations' economic growth (Babatunde, 2002). Hence there are missed manufacturing opportunities. Further studies suggest that the average international SMEs are more productive than their counterparts that are domestically oriented (Teece, 2006; Johanson & Vahlne, 2011; Kiss, et al., 2012)

The study focuses on to the internationalisation of SMEs in Cameroon because there is a dearth of studies in this area. Thus, insights from this study could help SMEs to obtain information that can help them to make decisions within the competitive business environment. Further, insights from the study will be a vital resource for policy makers and managerial practices within SMEs. Given that the internationalisation of SMEs within t emerging markets is largely unexplored, the study provides an opportunity to provide contextualised understandings of the role of SMEs within the global business environment. Whilst SMEs face many challenges, there is increasing need to amplify their problems within the international context and

encourage them to be more outward looking and benefit from opportunities that are availed by the globalised business environment.

Given that Cameroon's business ranking has reduced by 10%, from number 148 to 158, it is imperative that business strategies are developed to improve Cameroon's business rankings. Within this context, the activities of SMEs within the international markets must be given due attention. Whilst there are many studies on the internationalisation of large firms to emerging markets, there is a silence on the internationalisation of SMEs from an emerging to a global economy (INS, 2011).

1.5 Scope of the Study

The study focuses on a specific region in Cameroon, and SMEs that operate in that region. In fact, the focus is on the capital city, Yaoundé. Although this is Cameroon's second largest city, it has a hive of business activities within the SME sector. Of interest will be those SMEs that seek to internationalise their activities. The primary data sets will help to identify the challenges faced by SMEs that have already internationalised. Those SMEs still trying to internationalise are not the focus of the study. However, insights from SMEs that are already internationalised will help those SMEs intending to internationalise. Background information will be obtained from the SMEs with the intention of bringing a better understanding of the historical understandings of the internationalisation process, and the associated challenges.

1.6 Definition of Key Terms

Entrepreneur: is a person who runs their own business with innovative ideas instead of working for others (Figueira-de-Lemos, et al., 2011).

Entrepreneurship: is a broad term which is not only associated with producing and selling; it incorporated innovation, creativity and ability to tackle with unfavourable situations that come alone (Cuervo-Cazurra, 2008a).

Internationalisation: This is defined as the process of increasing the international activity of a firm (Sauvant, et al., 2010). In the current study, the word “internationalization” is used to identify SMEs’ that engage in external movements or foreign operations.

Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs): This are regarded as businesses with that have an assets threshold of income revenues and specific employment threshold patterning to the policy or definition of the country they operate in (Ibeh & Wheeler, 2005; Ibeh, 2003).

Emerging Economy: according to the World Bank definition, international Finance Corporation (IFC) in 1980, these are countries that are regarded to be economically developed when compared with advanced or developed countries, with market stocks demonstrating mature features in industrial countries (Anderson & Gatignon, 1989)

1.7 Brief discussion of Research Methodology

The study combines both qualitative and quantitative methodology, and thus adopts a mixed methods approach. This was adopted to help answer the research questions more comprehensively. In terms of sampling, the study used convenience, and purposive sampling techniques to help arrive at those respondents of interest more effectively and efficiently. Data was collected from across Cameroon’s four major regions (Littoral, South West, North West, and Central Region). For the SMEs that were conveniently selected to answer the questionnaires. This resulted in a sample of 200 manufacturing SMEs across the selected regions. Personalised emails were sent to prospective participants inviting them to take part in the survey. Based on the responds from the manager, 150 questionnaires were returned. However, only 112 were fully completed, and usable.

The estimated Cronbach’s alpha statistic for the 44-item inventory items for the survey instrument was .889. This means that 88.9% of the variability in the composite score of the 44 would be considered as true score variance or internally consistent reliable variance. When

Cronbach alpha was calculated under the pretence that the items all have the same variance, a coefficient of .896 is obtained. This suggests that the 5-point Likert scale items used are reliable.

For the qualitative data, emails were sent to 25 companies inviting them to participate in the qualitative part of the study. Of these, 20 companies accepted. However, 16 were used because the information provided by the other was similar and repetitive.

A mixed method was adopted to help answer the research questions. Philosophically, both positivist and interpretivist approaches were utilised. Primary data was both qualitative and quantitative. The intention was to triangulate the data sets and ensure that the research questions are answered. In undertaking the research, the researcher was guided by the ethical guidelines regarding: (1) informed consent (the degree to which prospective participants are informed in advance); (2) privacy and confidentiality; (3) language (the degree to which the preferred language is used for the interview sessions); (4) deception (ensuring that the respondent by no means are coerced to share information); and lastly (5) accuracy (the extent to which data collected are analyse accurately based on the information provided).

1.8 Structure of the Thesis

Chapter 1: This chapter discuss the background of the study and identifies the research gap. It also outlines the research problem, formulates the research aim, questions, and objectives. The chapter also provides a justification of the study. Key terms are defined, and a brief outline of the methodology provided.

Chapter 2: This chapter critically reviews the relevant academic literature and positions the study within on-going academic debates in the field of small and medium enterprises, and the

internationalisation process. Following from this, gaps in knowledge are identified, and a conceptual framework developed to help position the study more strongly within the identified knowledge gaps. Furthermore, the chapter discusses the contextual issues surrounding the research topic. Secondary data sets are retrieved and analysed in relation to the research topic. Graphs and charts are used to bring understanding on the current situation about SMEs and the internationalisation process. Connections are established with the Cameroonians context. This chapter helps the current study to be practically relevant.

Chapter 3: This chapter discusses the research methodology. It starts by outlining the philosophical debates, then justifying the research philosophy underpinning this study. The chapter also discusses the research approach, research strategy; sampling, pilot study, ethical issues, and outlines how data was analysed.

Chapter 4: This chapter presents results obtained from the primary research. The quantitative results are presented first, and then followed by the qualitative results. The chapter adopts a sequential analysis technique. The quantitative data is analysed using descriptive, associative, and predictive techniques. Qualitative data is organised in accordance with themes that emerged from the analysis. Extracts from qualitative data sets are presented and interpreted accordingly. In other words, these extracts are given meaning.

Chapter 5: This chapter presents the discussion of the findings in conjunction with the literature. Here, insights from the findings are explored further by drawing insights from the literature. The chapter identified similarities and differences between the findings and the literature. Detailed explanations are given to enhance theoretical understanding of the results. This is also followed by developing practical arguments.

Chapter 6: This chapter draws conclusions and makes some managerial recommendations. Research objectives are revisited and the outlines how each of the objectives were addressed. Theoretical contributions are also outlined. The chapter also makes suggestion for future research studies. Finally, the study limitations are acknowledged.

1.9 Chapter Summary

The main aim of the thesis is to address the current framework and process of internationalization while addressing the challenging barriers faced by manufacturing SMEs in Cameroon for low involvement internationalisation process. The research, therefore, intends to determine firm's internationalisation behaviour and domestic oriented behaviours in the African market (with case of Cameroon). Hence, it will analyse on barriers from extant empirical findings on the characteristics, both internal and external amalgamate a proposed theoretical context. The study seeks to make contribution to enhanced understanding internationalisation phenomenon. The next chapter critically discusses the literature.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

This chapter critically reviews the literature. It focuses on identifying gaps in knowledge within the literature surrounding SMEs internationalisation, and drawing insights from relevant theoretical frameworks to bring understanding to the research topic. The first part of the chapter focuses on the historical background of the phenomenon of the internationalisation process.

The chapter establish connections with the literature surrounding SMEs, and firm entry strategies into the international markets. The chapters draw from the Uppsala Model, born global theory, resource-based view, stage theory, international entrepreneurial theory, and network theory to enhance understanding of the research questions.

The chapter also reviews the contextual literature of Cameroon background surrounding the internationalization barriers and factors that facilitate the process of internationalisation. Following from this, the empirical analysis developed a conceptual framework to help position the study more strongly into the literature.

2.1 Historical Background of Internationalisation

From the 1990's foreign investment played an impact as the single external source of income in emerging economies, study shows over 1/2 private finance making 40% of total inflow capital in the markets (Aaby & Slater, 1989). According to (Anderson, et al., 2014) globalisation gave rise to the need to understand the importance of internationalisation, trailing the disappearance of commercial loan from bank in the 1980's, which eased the restrictions of international activities by policy makers in the emerging economies. Hence these economies reversed the balance with provision of incentives to compensate for foreign investment by offering low taxes, subsidies, exemption from import duties and infrastructures for development. Interesting view is derived from the aspect that foreign investment generates

external benefits such as technological transfer (Bell, et al., 2003; Barney, 1991; Calof, et al., 1995)

However, there are no clarity justifying the subsidies and benefits from international investment, aside from capital inflow and employment the risk that SMEs activities are like to face challenges that impact transfer of technology to the domestic enterprises. Hence the introduction of new products and methods makes the domestic market to gain advanced diffuse technologies (Teece, 2006).

Scholars have explored the motivations, and factors affecting the process of internationalisation (Andersson, et al., 2004; Sousa & Coelho, 2008). Others point out that the study of SMEs internationalisation has evolved (McAuley, 2010). Extant studies have focused more on mature firms, whilst little attention has been accorded to the internationalisation of SMEs. Given the high indebtedness of countries such as Cameroon, and their exposure to balance of payment deficits, there is a need to internationalise the activities of SMEs. This will help to boost the local economic development, reduce unemployment, and encourage SMEs to compete in the global market (McAuley, 2010)

Internationalization involves the geographical extension of economic activities across international borders. Potentially the international phenomenon enables domestic business to increase productivity by observing the international investors operations in their markets (Cavusgil, 2004). Human resources also turn to change as the employees in the foreign SMEs shift to the local enterprises. Previous studies suggest that often than not, foreign investors provide on job training as compared to the local counterparts. Therefore, internationalization can only be sensible if the benefits from the FDI complete from the investing companies (Chen, 2006; Cavusgil, 2004).

Historically, Adam Smith is credited for pioneering writings on the internationalisation process (McDougall & Oviatt, 1997; Mtgwe, 2006; Simon, 2009), This is reinforced by suggest that Adam Smith made use of countries as units to evaluate international process, and expounded this concept by advancing the theory of absolute advantage (Johanson & Vahlne, 2006; Ruzzier & Antoncic, 2007). (Andersson, et al., 2004) concurs that the literature has focused on the internationalisation of big multinational companies (MNC), and that there is a dearth of studies focusing on the internationalisation of SMEs.

The term “internationalization” developed to prominence initially in the 1920s as internationalization was more valued than imperialism as the leading business principle when making cross-border relations between market economies (McDougall, et al., 2009). The commercial internationalization process augmented in the post-WWII era and ruled until the early 1950s, when the new phenomenon of internationalization of SMEs began to emerge (Gillespie, et al., 1999).The internationalisation of business progressed in the 1950s after the World War two (WWII).

Here, multinational enterprises examined and exhibited the foreign entry strategy to other markets. (Servais & Rasmussen, 2000). As a result, in most recent theoretical studies, there is a focus on international business of small firms (Suresh & Ramraj, 2012). In fact, small enterprises entering emerging markets have increased enormously (Hutchinson, et al., 2009; Hunt, 2010)

Table 2. 1: Documented literature on international activities

Stages	Major Changes
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1. The first documented literature on international phenomenon was pioneered by Adam Smith in the 17th century (Zineldin, 2007)
2. National based analysis for internationalisation was dominant until the 1950s (Mtgwe, 2006; Ruzzier & Antoncic, 2007)
3. Revision study on firms' internationalisation was carried out in the 1950s (Mtgwe, 2006; Ruzzier & Antoncic, 2007)
4. The use of large multinational corporations as the main unit of study in internationalisation research, excluding SMEs (Mtgwe, 2006; Ruzzier & Antoncic, 2007)
5. (Ruzzier & Antoncic, 2007) then widen the internationalisation study to cover SMEs in the 1970s
6. Rapid growth of small new ventures, born global firms and entrepreneurial activities is the current growth phase of SME internationalisation (McDougall & Oviatt, 1997; Sauvart, et al., 2010)

Source: Authors' own construction

(Hashai, 2011) argues that the three main forces that motivates globalization of business (Freeman & Sandwell, 2008) includes the explosive increment of low-cost technology; slow communication in linking people from one location to another; the excessive increase of international trade due to the steady disassembling of foreign trade barriers. Another key factor is the financial capacity of firm's along-side the increase of growth in restructured economics. The liberal rules that emerged as a result of the fall of socialist system in Central and Eastern Europe ruled by Russia are also key factors (Ford, et al., 1996; Gannon, 1993). Scholars also suggest that the development of emerging markets in Asia, particularly China, has influenced globalization and internationalization (Cardoza & Fornes, 2009). Irrespective of the driving force of globalization, internationalization has added to the credibility of international business activities (Hadley & Wilson, 2003)

SMEs have been previously classified as passive business operations than active players in the international milieu (Tesfom & Lutz, 2006). However, more recent studies suggest that this understanding is changing (Ellis, 2011). Some studies have suggested that since the 1970s,

SMEs have successfully been active participants as they have coordinated business affairs in foreign markets, an important aspect for the growth of the future economies (Anderson, 2002). SMEs activities are often portrayed as being restricted to the regions that they are based (Kiss, et al., 2012). Within this, scholars suggest that SME activities are focused on their home country (Barney, 1991; Bonaccorsi, 1992). In other words, business activities of SMEs are often undertaken within the national boundaries. Nevertheless, in the globalised economy, SMEs are not entirely traditionally localised to their national boundaries, but engage in business activities that transcend geographical boundaries, and have opportunities to provide their products and services to a global market (Gupta, et al., 2017). Within this context, the word “internationalization” is used to identify SMEs’ that engage in external movements or foreign operations.

2.2 The Internationalisation of SMEs

Advanced technology, and trade liberalisation has provided opportunities for firms to engage more actively with the internationalisation process (McAuley, 2010). Previous studies on the internalization of SMEs have focused more on the product operations in the international markets (Welch & Welch, 2009). Within this, the networking of business is understood as an international experience of many enterprises.

For effective foreign expansion, small enterprises are beginning to adopt a strategic approach (Johanson & Mattsson, 1988; Ripollés & Blesa, 2012). Most research on internationalization concentrated on the outward process of expanding business across borders, including exportation, licensing, franchising, and foreign direct investment (Lorenzen & Mudambi, 2013). Hence depicted in figure 2.1, entering a foreign market entails SMEs to develop an international entry plan, as such might be influenced by several factors, mainly the mode of entry, entry time into the selected external market.

Figure 2. 1: SMEs market entry strategy

Source: by author

Other factors that might be important in the entry strategy includes the region and localities of the SMEs either they are based in developed economy or emerging economy, what are their goals and objectives, the capacity to tolerate risks, also the level of human resources, geopolitical, socioeconomic and financial factors just to mention a few.

Although, external expansion is not solely based on the outward effect process but also can be done inwardly, through seldom importation process of products and supplier amongst others, (Kumar, 2012). And yet, very little is mentioned by researchers on the involvement of SMEs on the inward process of internationalization (Sharma & Erramilli, 2004). Scholars are contended that most companies begin their business engage with the inward process as a route to internationalisation (Lorenzen & Mudambi, 2013). This is consistent with the view that internationalisation is the practice by which companies both increase their consciousness of direct and indirect effect of international transactions on their future and create and conduct relations in other nations (Kumar, 2012).

For some scholars, the internationalization of SMEs helps to increase international processes and operations in sequences that involve several stages (McAuley, 2010). Within this context, (Hashai, 2011) define internationalization as a collective process which networks are consistently built, preserved, recognized, destroyed, and disbanded with the intention of attaining a firm's objectives and development of their international business.

However, (O'Farrell, et al., 1998), critique this perspective as being too fragmented because it focuses on the network and relationships built by SMEs. Considering that SMEs operate within their natural business environment, other firms may also seek the same relationships, thereby creating competition. Therefore, SME owners must build relationships in other nations as a means of penetration, integration, and internationalization (Ramamurti, 2004) Thus, for internationalisation to succeed, there must be the international orientation and the international commitment. Wherein international orientation is on companies that from the beginning they are focused on the internationalizing process as such they represent an evaluative dimension.

Internationalization is also described as a process of perceived divergence between external and domestic marketplace in relation to the economic, cultural, political, social, and strategic-market extents (Reid, 1983). As one of the two main concepts of internationalization, international commitment is linked with the needs of the process model used and the size of the foreign market. It positions enterprises on the extremes of no connections (internal firms) and a full obligation (firms obliged to internationalise). Consequently, there is a drift from internationalization meaning to the evaluation of international activities based on the resources needed to expand business (Calof, et al., 1995; Cullen & Parboteeah, 2011; Westhead & Wright, 2001).

This brings in the resource-based view. In fact, the resource-based view helps us to understand that the internationalization of SMEs based on resources in the natural context on businesses

relationships (McDougal, 2007). Hence, the internationalization of SMEs involves the mobilization of significant and dependent resource frameworks that push and trigger a firm's international activities within its usual context (Chen, 2006). Within this context, small and medium sized firms' foreign extension is a process of accumulating, assembling, and enhancing resources for international operations, irrespective of the actual intent of the external activities.

Furthermore, the current frameworks on small enterprise internationalization process have practically presented a market, business, or entrepreneurial activities. According to Welch & Welch (2012), the market perspective on international extension is the diversification of models adopted by big corporations on the internationalization process. On the business perspective, it involves the stage models process of internationalizing.

2.2.1 Brief synopsis of internationalization entry mode

The internationalization entry mode has largely depended on the advanced economies-centric theories patterning to trade and foreign businesses, this has been predominant in the institutional economics (Buckley & Casson M. C., 1985; Buckley, 1989; Buckley & Ghauri, 2004; Dunning, 1988; Dunning, et al., 2007). Academic studies on outward and inward flow of international and foreign investment have been drawn most substantially from enterprises in the advanced markets (Vahlne, et al., 2011; Oliveira & Fortunato, 2006; Buckley, 2011).

While there is as extensive knowledge and growth of emerging SMEs, (Ahmad & Kitchen, 2008) adhere the organization and operations of these enterprises are still at infant stage and posed unanswered questions and challenges. Some of the questions include the differences in SMEs in the emerging economies and advanced economies? Are the challenges faced by both SMEs in emerging economies like advanced economies in the international market? What are the drives that influenced SMEs in this case Cameroon manufacturers to internationalize? What

are some of the main motivators and characteristics that make SMEs to succeed in foreign markets? (Aaby & Slater, 1989; Bigsten, et al., 2004; Ahmad & Kitchen, 2008; Aldrich, et al., 2006).

Recent studies are lacking in the literature as to what are the specific casual mechanisms and channel used by SMEs in their international operations. Most of the summaries are derived from advanced markets and the theories they use in internationalizing, which might not be applicable in every market especially on SMEs in the less developed economies. An argument posed by (Agarwal & Ramaswami, 1992; Sousa & Coelho, 2008) established international theories have not concentrated on the role played by local government at the targeted markets especially in emerging economies. (Philips, et al., 2009), suggest that it is important for these SMEs to decide on which entry strategy to use when entering a targeted market. Several factors determine the foreign entry mode adopted by SMEs as such the degree of risks posed by international market, the market commitment and available resources needed most importantly return investment (ROI) (Dunning, 2002)

One of the international entry mode strategy is foreign acquisition, and this is done through mergers or acquisition (M&As). There has been increment in this method because its way of giving autonomy of power to the foreign investor which intend affects market shares. As such most SMEs use the merging strategy to acquire greater power, hence buying and merging with competitors, suppliers, and other highly related business in similar industry where in they can exercise significant control and competitive advantage (Ojala & Tyrväinen, 2007). Most SMEs aggressive international acquisition and merger has been fast track entry strategy in foreign investment. These enterprises despite their diverse objectives have attained significant goals and includes technological acquisition, brand names and human and natural resources (UNCTAD, 2014)

With an increase in the internationalization of SMEs and businesses across national borders, the discussion and understanding of motives and strategic implication needs to be crucially evaluated. The theoretical frameworks of internationalization entry mode and the decisions to carry on the process need more attention. These decisions are significant particularly on the environmental contingencies of current market liberalization and emerging markets (Fletcher, 2001; Björkman & Forsgren, 2000; Hunt, 2010)

A study by Yip *et al.*, (1988) provided guidelines to enter foreign markets, debating that when a business decides to extend its market beyond borders, it has to make a choice of which international markets it wants to operate. The decision to select a market entails the choice of best country to internationalized base on the enterprise needs (Teece, et al., 1997; O'Farrell, et al., 1998). Once foreign market entry is attained, the next determinant is to adopt a pattern of operations in the foreign market (Bonaccorsi, 1992; Craig & Douglas, 1997) Hence, these guidelines offer generic plans available for enterprises in developing economies.

Previous studies have also found the essence of internationalization process in market selection and foreign operations. Studies also observe that in foreign theories, transactions cost made within the institution in the free market are higher than the internal costs which focus on the products and its low qualities (Rugman, 2005).

The eclectic paradigm was used by Dunning, (1980, 1988, and 2000) to explain the international operations of enterprises in selection of a foreign market. He based his study of internationalization process on the transaction cost theory, a model that accounted for the outsourcing of production and services through the costs of the transaction. The coordination

of the costs, search cost and the contracting costs. This was not just limited to the market prices, but all costs of the operations were considered when making an international decision. He further argued that it is necessary for enterprises to compensate for local knowledge acquired in international market operations (Dunning, 2000).

The response to internationalization from emerging economies to advanced economies is cost-oriented and the approach of low-cost commodity, cheap labour and available resources is a strategic procedure for SMEs (Craig and Douglas, 1997). Importantly, creating value through an approach such as manufacturing standard quality for higher value chain goods that will capture the market, and increase its shares (Craig and Douglas, 1997; Hutchinson, et al., 2005; Sutton, 2014). It is also equally important for businesses to understand the culture to mitigate any obstacles when expanding beyond their geographical scope (Sauvant, et al., 2010) Hence the knowledge and role that culture plays on brand, goods and production from the foreign markets culture and customer behaviour in purchase choice (Calof, et al., 1995)

Apparently, the internationalization process of SMEs is not only limited to the above entry strategy and decisions. Khanna and Palepu (2006) believe that foreign investment should undergo wider strategies by focusing on capitalizing voids in the institution surrounding emerging markets. Based on their assertion, enterprises from less developed economies have the potential to distinctively manage the institutional gaps. This can be exploited when facing foreign SMEs both in the domestic markets, and international markets.

According to (Beach & Mitchell, 1978), internationalization is a phenomenon that is adapted by business organisations through their foreign operations, strategy, structure, and resources in foreign environments. Hence, it compromises regional topographic distance to which the

market is expanding to, the kinds of activities it operates in, different countries beyond its local borders, and the integration of activities from local to foreign. Globalization and migration of customers have been one of the drivers for enterprises to internationalise. Some enterprises internationalise as a source of wealth gain, progress, and success of their business.

2.3 Main Theories of Internationalisation Process

Enterprises employ different strategies with the intention of increasing profitability. This is defined as an inward and outward movement in the international milieu (Brouthers, et al., 2009). Traditionally, a firm’s internationalization is measured (outward movement) as the percentage of external sales to total sales. However, this information does not depict the nature or firm’s capacity to carry out international activities. As such there is no universal cause as to why firms internationalise (Koe, 2013; Chetty & Agndal, 2007; OECD, 2013).

Different theories have been proposed by academic researchers to enable easy mode of foreign entry and internationalization strategy (Vahlne, et al., 2011; Johanson & Vahlne, 2011). These theories have different features amongst them. For this research, figure 2.2 gives a better understanding of these theories. There are four main schools of thoughts, as illustrated in figure 2.2.

Figure 2. 2: Main theories of internationalisation process

Source: Author

Table 2.1 depicts the main approach and theories that are prominently sub-divided into nine main foreign entry theories that are aligned with each of the constructs. This helps to explain the strategic decision process of businesses for successful and competitive growth in the foreign market (Lu and Beamish, 2001; Zhao and Decker, 2004).

Table 2. 2: Theories of internationalisation process and entry mode

Redaction due to copyright restrictions. Original table can be found in Andersen, Ahmad and Chan, 2014.

Source: Andersen, Ahmad & Chan (2014)

The concept of “SMEs internationalization” was primarily introduced by Johanson and Vahlne (2009), and ever since then, there has been several remarkable definitions of the subject. However, there has been a gradual evolution in the research study of internationalization. For instance, studies have focused on exportation rather than macro-economic trend in external markets. Others have focused on the characteristics distinct firm’s behavioural patterns within the international markets (Peng *et al.*, 2008).

Previous studies have also analysed a firm's characteristics, culminating in the development of a conceptual framework of how individual company's methodologies vary for internationalization (Peng *et al.*, 2008). Some scholars argue that the internationalization phenomenon is that a single business organisation is partial to the global environs and the economy as such should be analysed in that context (Peng *et al.*, 2008; Johanson and Vahlne, 2007). Others focus on the human aspects of internationalization process (Zahra and George, 2002).

2.4 International Business Theories and Entry Mode

Previous studies have revealed the importance of SMEs in emerging markets engaging in foreign business activities. Scholars have documented the internationalization process, and entry mode strategy used by those SMEs (Perose, 1995; Mardanov, 2003; Kwon & Konopa, 1993). Studies on internationalization initially focused on economic theories in 1930's (Buckley, 2011). Early theories of internationalisation were introduced in the 1960s and 1970s. The findings from these studies were grouped into different paradigms by (O'Sullivan, et al., 2003) These included the market imperfection paradigm, which gives insight to the internationalization of enterprises and their microeconomic environment. The behavioural paradigm explains the process used in internationalizing. The market failure paradigm reveals the reasoning behind internationalizing.

2.4.1 Paradigm of Market Imperfection

The imperfect market is any market that is not up to the rigorous standards of a market that is hypothetically perfect in terms of competitiveness, as proposed by the Marshallian partial model of equilibrium. A market is said to be imperfect when there is a shortage of information or limited access to knowledge by all actors involved. Another aspect of imperfect market is that prices, productions, and supplies are influenced by certain individual buyers and sellers (Hymer, 1968; Barney, 1991; Caves, 1971).

This school of thought is aligned to two international theories. The first is presented by (Hymer, 1960) the theory of monopolistic advantage. This suggests that the entry of SMEs in international markets is only when the imperfections in the local market is comparatively high. Here, they can also use the licence mode of entry. (Vernon, 1974) theory of product lifecycle is the second of the market imperfection theory. In the early stages of the product lifecycle, businesses will choose to export beyond domestic markets (Cheung, 1987)

Industries operating in an imperfect economy, with small competition and high international barriers, are expected to increase returns. These exist in products market and include (product differentiation, market skills and brands), also in factor markets (managerial abilities, technological advancement).

2.4.2 Monopolistic Advantage Theory

The foreign direct investment started gaining more attention in the 1960s after the research study carried out by Hymer who came up with the monopolistic advantage theory. Hymer's ideas were classified as a distinctive phase on enterprise impact in the world economy (Buckley, 2006). With time, ideas of Hymer shifted from the micro-dynamics to the world economic system that was dominated by MNCs in the western world (Dunning, et al., 2007; Pitelis, 2002).

According to (Hymer, 1976) FDI is a prominent influence for international expansion of firms for two purposes. The first driver for FDI is from home market advantages of firm's intra-transfer of technological, and institutional firm specific resource development. For the retention and increase in profits, businesses undergo international operations which compete with both the local and the foreign host economy (Sharma & Erramilli, 2004; Quer, et al., 2007; Barney, 1986; Jones, et al., 2011) The second motivator for internationalization is to remove conflict barriers by monopolising business operations in the host markets. However, firms are forced to maintain control of activities. Hence, more investment is made in the host market than was

in the optimal plan (Buckley, 2006; Barnat, 2005). The attempt to differentiate the traditional concept of FDI gave control of foreign activities and share of ownership, thus making use of portfolio investment.

The production in foreign markets is costlier for enterprises because of uncertainty encountered in foreign operations. This include currency fluctuation, lack of knowledge, and attention to cost switching. However, Hymer argued that enterprises will have intrinsic advantage from the home market and should exploit the advantage of market imperfection in the host market as its competitive advantage. Thus, product diversification and intangible assets should be explored in foreign operations, and the acquisition of knowledge should be used (Buckley, 1989; Hymer, 1976).

The literature suggests that motivating factors of foreign investment are a result of low cost of production in the host market. Whereas the local businesses are not efficient to compete with other business in same industry, even when faced with cultural, political, and social barriers to enter a new market. In fact, entry into foreign markets is an enterprising way of maximising competitive advantages in the imperfect market. Hence, markets with uneven flow of information and development give the investors advantage over its rivals.

2.4.2.1 Critique of the Monopolistic advantage theory

The theory of monopolistic advantage was the core foundation theory for internationalization and contributed to enterprise expansion theory. However, this theory must be modified to suit the current concept of global venture and international business (Teece, 2006; Buckley, 2006). The theory does not comprehend the process, and states which firms choose to export or carry out their operations. In this sense, it presents a partial evaluation of the ownership dimension of firms (Sharma & Blomstermo, 2003). Also, the theory gives the notion that the use of monopoly on rents through restricted outputs generates exploitable scarcity in the foreign

markets and gives high returns. But the argument is not conclusive as recent studies shows that the development of new products in emerging markets offers higher return in foreign investment (Teece, 2006)

Hymer's research neglected value creation, as it was short in explaining the motives that SMEs expand to acquire resources and cheap labour force (Buckley, 2006). The argument of firms' exploitation in the foreign market through market imperfection, and capitalisation on low cost of production fail to encompass product development. Given technological advancement in the foreign market over time, internationalization becomes a dominance process (Sutton, 2014; Teece, 1977)The role of government organisation was overlooked by the monopolistic advantage theory as it fails to mention the role of policy makers in support to economic development, and the internationalization process of SMEs (Dunning, 2006). Finally, the theory does not pay attention to intra-enterprise conflict and decision-making processes (Pitelis, 2002)

2.4.3 International product life Cycle Theory

Vernon (1966) developed the international life cycle theory to respond to the Hecksher-Ohlin Model. This explained the pattern of foreign trade, though economists and marketers still use the model. The theory suggests that in the early stages of production, the life cycle of the process including the parts, labour, and human resources originate from the invented area. As soon as the product is adopted, used, and expands to global markets, the production eventually shifts from the original point of creation. In most parts, the product turns to be an item imported from the country of origin (Hill, 2007).

Figure2.4 illustrates how the product enters and disappear from a market. Each product is characterised with sales and time. The product goes through stages, from introduction stage, growth maturity and decline.

Figure 2. 3: International product life cycle and international trade

Source: Egu and Aregbeshola, 2017, Adapted from (Vernon, 1966)

The literature suggests that internationalization process has a four-stage pattern of product life cycle, introduction stage, growth stage, mature stage, and decline stages (Kotler, 2016). The production quantities are low at the early stage of introduction because there is no establishment of cost standardization, as enterprises pay more attention on the communication and flexibility control. At this stage developed economies benefit in exporting their products to less developed economies. Meanwhile, the growth stage begins to see an increase in cost standardization as enterprises start cutting prices to increase economies of scale. This stage sees foreign investment activities at moderate income development. Then the product is at mature stage, which makes competition high and see the production of alternate products or rebranding of the original product. The decline and disappearance of the product is the final

stage. At this stage there is low market demand of the product (Moen, 2002; Sharma & Erramilli, 2004).

2.4.3.1 Critique of the international product life cycle theory

The theory gives firm-specifics and product-specific which explains international trade (Mardanov, 2003). There is limited focus on the firm level as attention is given to the country level of trade. However, the attention given to location gives advantage of the host country explaining the relevance in the international decision in their target markets (Kumar and Subramaniam, 1997). The first two stages of the theory were further developed to form a new product stage, maturity stage and standardization stage. Here, firms can profit from primary comparative advantages with good innovativeness (OECD, 2018).

Scholars suggest that the model is too generalised in explaining the international trade pattern adopted by enterprises. The entry mode is more particular with its discerning strategies, ignoring products that are internationalized without going through all four stages. Products that are adopted and sold in foreign markets without experiencing growth and mature stage are also ignored.

Although for this thesis the model is relevant, however, the theory is more time and period dependent, that evolve gradually, and it seem to be more suitable for manufacturing SMEs not service ones. Also, the model is not accurate in representing every product life cycle as there are products with short life cycle that experience international trade through optimal entry mode strategy, most likely international new ventures or born global businesses (Sharma & Erramilli, 2004).

2.4.4 Behavioural paradigm

The behavioural paradigm comprises of theories that view internationalization as collective knowledge. This progresses towards the learning processes, that prompt an enterprise's foreign market entry strategy (Ibeh & Wheeler, 2005)

The behavioural paradigm of internationalisation focuses on both linear and sequential processes that occurs in different phases (Coviello & Cox, 2006). Within this area, the dominant perspectives are drawn from the innovation-related internationalisation model known as the (I-Model), (Klein, 2014; Koe, 2013; Cavusgil, 2004) and the Uppsala Model (Johanson & Vahlne, 2009). The network model is a theory that dominated the internationalisation process of enterprises and has influenced business networks and growth of businesses internationally (Anderson, 2002)

The behavioural paradigm suggests that foreign expansions in targeted markets be done in a gradual pace because of high resource commitment in the long-term. The paradigm gives experiential knowledge to enterprise as competitive advantage in foreign markets. (Erramilli, et al., 2002; Cardoza & Fornes, 2009).

2.4.4.1 The Uppsala Model of Internationalisation

The practical groundwork for the Uppsala theory originated from the findings of four Swedish multinational companies that when started in the 19th century initially commenced their businesses internationally and eventually grew to multinational companies. Knowledge and findings gathered by the researchers indicated that most firms during the process of internationalisation enter emerging markets and other markets through baby steps, based on the knowledge about the markets before expanding (Okpara, 2010; OECD, 2009). According to (Björkman & Forsgren, 2000), these companies initially internationalised while at early stage of business.

The next encountered problems of these Swedish firms were a result of limitation on expatriate's knowledge and decision making to enter foreign markets. Hence, it was bounded by rationality assumptions that encountered problems (Peng et al, 2008). Therefore, the motivations of international actions by a company are to increase the knowledge that will

contribute to the internationalisation process (Peng et al, 2008). Consequently, the Uppsala model prompted the researchers to investigate firm's internationalisation process built on knowledge acquisition, growth, and commitment to enhance the business in foreign markets.

Figure 2. 4: Initial internationalisation model

Redaction due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Johanson & Vahlne, 2009.

Source: (Johanson & Vahlne, 2009)

Figure 2.5 shows the Uppsala model of market knowledge and market commitment at the state which the firms commence their internationalisation process. Drawing from knowledge within the foreign market, the decision makers evaluate the situations and are committed to deciding if the firms should expand. This paves a way for strategy adoption on the process of internationalisation (OECD, 2008). Furthermore, an analysis of the current activities the firm is involved, helps to decide on whether to expand the activities to suit the host market (Ojala & Tyrväinen, 2007)The orientation of the Uppsala model is based on the foundation that internationalisation process of expansion is motivated by the knowledge development when doing business in foreign markets. This provides an opportunity to take advantage on the growth possibilities established in the market (Eriksson & Chetty, 2003). Scholars suggest that knowledge is gained gradually (Singh et al, 2010). As such, internationalisation is a systematic process that occurs on a logical gradual process of change (Singh et al, 2010).

The literature suggests that firms enter the international market with little or low commitment from the starting phase, and the strategies that influences this model of entry is the direct export mode of expansion (Singh, et al., 2010). Although the initial focus of the model is based on the low commitment of the international markets, the model indicates that after the knowledge acquisition and growth, the business later shifts its concerns and interest on the foreign market. If there is a higher interest, they adopt the sales subsidiary and the manufacturing or establish unit of production in the market. Analytically, on the development process of internationalisation, the model assumes that insufficient information on the appropriate practicality of the market and growth. A lack of information is a barrier to expansion (Johanson & Vahlne, 2006)

Furthermore, the core of the model shows that the state aspects determine the existing position of the firm and its feature/ long-term variables that enables the internationalisation process. The change aspect affects the short-term variables of the day to day activities of the firm (Freeman & Sandwell, 2008). The model lays emphasise on the uncertainties that could affect the knowledge acquisition and the market. This requires attention to build in confidence on information gained (Singh et al, 2010)

The firms initially enter a market with short psychic distance from the present market to the host market, and then gradually it grows to other nations with a longer psychic distance due to information gained (Singh *et al.*, 2010). However, differences in language, cultural divergence, contradictory political and organisational systems (Anderson, 2011) are challenges that must be managed. The inadequacy of knowledge and information flow and the psychic distance variance creates tightened risks of uncertainty and firm weakness. However, cohesive adoption of information from neighbouring markets gives a comprehended advancement of the company which make the firms to use less risky entering strategy such as exportation. Time requirements

and further barriers makes the firms develop and adopt different entry modes to more distance markets (Johansson & Valhne, 2009).

2.4.4.1.1 Critical Understandings of the U-Model

Adhering to (Anderson & Gatignon, 1989) the model lacks rigorous methodological approach to provide absolute conceptual and theoretical framework that guide the research findings. Another shortcoming of the model is the fact that it is based on a single pathway for firm's internationalisation process. Hence, information or knowledge development of a market should not be the only basic way for business internationalisation (Anderson, 2000). However, it must be pointed out that the U-model of stage approach is focused on the initial stage of business establishment on internationalisation.

This is essential to study the market through short distance psychic mode before full involvement. It must also be acknowledged that it will be good for a firm to adopt other knowledge or market by fully and directly involving in the market, from the initial stage of creation. Equivalent, to the findings on the research carried out by (Coviello & Munro, 1997; Crick & Jones, 2000), organisation decision and foreign market entrants is concurrent with the domestic market, thus is beyond just knowledge alone. As a matter of fact, with the new trend of born global and new venture firms that from their creation engages in international markets, thus ignoring the domestic market and pay attention to the global market. Thus, from the practical involvement the firms can better understand the market and gain more knowledge. The model is not interactive and coherent to take decisions for the process of internationalisation (Ruzzier & Antoncic, 2007)

Besides lacking other aspects to the expansion process, the model failed in mentioning the managerial competency and expatriates influence on the internationalisation of business activities (Axinn and Mathyssens, 2002). The pioneer founders of the Uppsala model agree

with the opinion that management play a vital role in the development strategy of internationalisation of a firm, alluding to their constraints on the model, they emphasised that its of importance that the managerial discretion and creditability based on strategy intention be incorporated in the model (Johanson & Vahlne, 2011). (Wright, et al., 2007). evaluated the U-model, and found that it was focused on large enterprises, much to the neglect of SMEs.

Scholars argued that knowledge or information is not adopted solely by using psychic distance entry strategies such export, but the contemporary time have brought about advancement in technology, thus the aspect of information technology and media is lacking in the u-model (Brewer, 1993). In fact, (Dunning, 1977). suggested the model be revised to make use of the information technological innovation and the interaction of suppliers and customers, as well as other firms in the international market.

2.4.4.1.2 Critique of Stage Model of SMEs Internationalisation

The contemporary empirical results on internationalisation of small medium enterprises have proven to be neither trail dependent, incremental nor developing (Schultz et al., 2009). Most of the modern SMEs internationalisation studies use the stage model to elucidate why business carries out international expansion activities. Nonetheless, the intermittent stage approach cannot entirely explain the concepts of SMEs international phenomena, including the ‘born global’ and the ‘back-resources’ (SME’s that re-form their international undertakings to the domestic economy) and the ‘born regionals’ (SMEs that are solely focusing their activities in the local market and do not have the potential to move beyond the market) (Acedo & Jones, 2007)An important drawback to the stage approach model and the core target to the critics of the model is on the assumption that the progress of the stage theory is organized in a predictable way (Weiland, 2015)This limits the strategic choices of the international entrepreneur. Another, limitation to the models is that the Uppsala theory is focused on the firm rather than on the business owner (entrepreneur) (Harvie, et al., 2013). Hence, from the above perspective,

the scope of SMEs internationalisation is limited because the owner of the business is known to be the principal essence for the company. In this sense, the entrepreneurial behaviour is very important in the international decisions that affect the company. Additionally, Coviello and Munro (1995) argue that high-tech product small enterprises as the entrepreneurs' control and detect the conventional patterns of the business, thus they do not rely on the stage approach method of internationalisation.

Further to the criticism of the stage approach theory of internationalisation, there is limited focus on the time of the stages along with the structures that operates with them. Predicting the stages and differences with collaboration of the activities is subjective. Rather, it must be perceived as being creative in discovering the differences that occur between stages. On the other hand, innovation theory describes the process change, elaborating on the dimensions of the change and the diversity of approach adopted by various companies in activities development (OECD, 2017)

2.4.4.2 The Business Network Theory

Subsequently, for better understanding of the network approach business theory, the researcher made an explicit evaluation and discussion of important aspects of the theory. The intention was to critically evaluate the theory and contextualise it.

2.4.4.2.1 Contextualising the Business Network Approach

The launch of the Group7 project in the 1970's helped to carry out findings on the industrial market and purchasing (IMP) with attention on long-term collaboration within industrial markets. The research further led to the formation of what is known as the industrial network Approach (INA) also known as the market-as-networks vision (Fisher, et al., 2007; Johanson & Vahlne, 2011)The approach did advocate the interaction of businesses. It proposes that the actors involved in a business should create an established relationship to engage with each

other, hence network creation (Kumar, 2012). Scholars define relationships, associates, relations, and connections between a company and other relevant actors in the business market (Koe, 2013).

Therefore, the inter-connected relationships, creates networks which interlink three or more businesses either directly or indirectly. This is achieved through different ties and strengths of the relationship (Rajesh *et al.*, 2008). However, the process of relationships building of businesses through links and contacts contributes to the success or failure of the business (Cardoza & Fornes, 2009). The relationship could be formulated differently, either through exchanges of natural or human resources (Kumar, 2012). Given the increasingly globalised business environment, the internationalisation of firms benefits from developed communication systems, linkages, and multiple contacts, thereby creating a network with business across borders.

The literature suggests that the network perception examines the business context in a holistic view, focusing on the way in which businesses build their relationships and how they collaborate within the market, consequently addressing the external market embedment of firms to create networks (Zahra, 2005). In this sense, the network approach is used to help assess the process of market entry and inform participatory practices within the network (Servais & Rasmussen, 2000). Here, firms create relationships in the foreign nation networks to help achieve international expansion. This also helps to enhance resource commitment in those firms that already possess (infiltrate) the prevailing networks in different countries (Dimitratos & Plakoyiannaki, 2003). Although not directly involved as partners, the different actors cannot individually control the mode and process of entry (Anderson, 2002).

In the past, the IMP Group has been involved in several studies that stimulated other researchers to get involved with the network business approach. The research encouraged firms to develop

relationships amongst each other, highlighting the complexity of firms' operation through exportation and importation while collaborating as well as competing amongst them.

2.4.4.2.2 A review of Network Approach to Internationalization

Apparently, most research theories related to internationalisation are largely and primarily concerned with the traditional process of determining and organising to enter a market. They tend to focus more on developing the necessary market entry strategies. On the other hand, the network approach theory focuses on the actual entry process as an inseparable part of the networks that already exist in the business (Knight, et al., 2004).

According to the network approach theory, firms achieved the process of internationalisation in the creation of relationships/bonds in the foreign nation networks new to the system (international expansion). The increase in the ties and relations amongst these firms enhance the dedication to be resourcefully committed in the networks that the company is currently positioned (penetration) or linked with already existent networks (Neupert, et al., 2005). These firms' network bonds are not only linked as direct partners but influences their other partners through the enterprise's behaviour (Ford, 1998). In fact, different core players cannot singly handle and totally control the entry process (Anderson, 2000).

The network approach is of the prerogatives that for enterprises to grow, relationships build, and cooperation is much more effective than competing. The oneness or togetherness of businesses can institute resources and comprehend great potentialities effectually (Anderson, 1998). Therefore, most firms' physical assets are locally based in the domestic market but can also be vital actors in an international market network (Björkman & Forsgren, 2000). Knowledge could be acquired through a firm's experiential profile by not necessary undergoing the same experience as the firm (Erikson et al, 1998). As well as learning about the competency, strategies and needs of their partners, a firm also acquires information about the partner's states

of business and the market network it has (Johanson & Vahlne, 2009). Therefore, a distinctive characteristic of internationalisation sequence does change from a gradual extension to a one 'bound' to join the nets (Dawar & Frost, 1999). In contrast, it is important to note that relationships are not only limited to motivating and facilitating but could also inhibit an enterprise internationalisation.

According to the network theory, firms can be broken down into four separate groups based on the environment alienated to the internationalisation process. This group is not exposed to local relationships in the home country that could help to gain access to networks (Hutchison et al., 2007; Hadley and Williamson, 2008; Johansson & Vahlne, 2009). If the firm is bound to export its produce, they will not meet high competition and direct dealings with customers (Ramamurti, 2008) Business actors make the use of representatives, merchants, and international clients to enter the international market. This helps to reduce risks and costs, while capitalising on the knowledge from agents' previous investments in the international market. The business is affected by other counterparts than the company itself. Scholars suggest that the best strategy for internationalising by large firms and multinational enterprises is by acquisition or 'greenfield' mode with huge resources unlike small medium enterprises that do not have large resources (Johansson & Vahlne, 2006).

Apparently, if a firm's key actors, such as its distributors, rivals, clients, are internationally based, it has opportunities for creating indirect cooperation with the external networks. Similarly, the firm has opportunities to establish cooperation in the domestic market. In fact, relations in the local market might motivate the business to extend to the foreign markets (Malhotra, et al., 2009).

The late starter's process of internationalization is influenced by indirect overseas network relationships. With already market competition, it's not easy to penetrate the nearest market to

the home markets, due to that fact that rivalry organisations have comprehensive information and there is existing trend of network that is quite difficult to break through. Thus, it will lead to the enterprise to exploit distant markets; as such emerging markets will be much suitable for internationalising (Chetty & Campbell-Hunt, 2003). The next group is the ‘lonely international’ firms. These are knowledgeable and experienced with relationships in foreign nations.

2.4.5 International Entrepreneurship Theory

The literature suggests that technological advancement, cultural ties and declining of international trade barriers, as well as diversity awareness and cultural growth has set the pace for increase in international business activities (McDougall and Oviatt, 2009). This has also encouraged international entrepreneurship (Zahra and George, 2002).

In fact, international entrepreneurship comprehends the study of cross-border entrepreneurial behaviour that comprises of the exploitation, creation, innovation, and evaluation to enact the opportunities of new products and services (Zahra and George, 2002). Some scholars suggest that international entrepreneurship is a risk-taking behaviour that seeks value creation, and analytical skills to increase organisational values (McDougall and Oviatt, 2000). Others suggest that international entrepreneurship is a process that enacts, evaluate and exploits chances across national borders to make it possible for future growth in products and services (McDougall and Oviatt, 2009).

The literature also suggests that the individual and firm’s entrepreneurship in based on the international market entry strategy (McDougall and Oviatt, 2009). The technological growth, inexpensive services which has seen the quick adoption of information flow and distance communication from country to country, paves the way for the internationalisation of SMEs (Mtgwe, 2006). The existence of multinational markets creates the ease for penetration through

daring managerial value creativity, audacious risk-taking behaviour that is designated to pursue international opportunities (McDougall and Oviatt, 2009).

Another argument of the international entrepreneurship theory is noted to have originated from 2005 from the old-style entrepreneurship folio (O'Sullivan, et al., 2003). The model criss-crosses the entrepreneurship and internationalisation field of research (Zahra and George, 2005). The international entrepreneur theory is a representation of the current extant framework development in the SMEs internationalisation folio (Hitt, et al., 2006a). The wide recognition of the theory amongst researchers has developed several alternate names for the empirical business theory which have been conceptualized and termed differently (McDougall *et al.*, 2003).

Table 2. 3: Terms for international entrepreneurship

	<i>Authors (Source)</i>	<i>Terms</i>
1	McDougall (1988) Zahra & George (2000)	New Ventures
2	McDougall & Oviatt (1994) McDougall et al (1994)	International new venture
3	Railp <i>et al.</i> , (2005), Zahra <i>et al.</i> , (2005), McDougall & Oviatt, (2005)	New venture internationalisation
4	Knights and Causgil (1996) Bell et al, (2000)	Born Global firms
5	Bell et al (2003)	Born-again global
6	McDougall & Oviatt, (2005), McDougall & Oviatt, (1988).	Global start-ups
9	Moan & Servais (2002), Anderson et al, (2003)	Early internationalisation

Source: Author's own construction

2.4.6 Eclectic paradigm

From the supposition given on the five theories integrated in this study, the key variables of interest: (1) size of the firm, (2) ownership framework, (3) the age of the firm, (4) human

resources/capital (i.e. the cumulative level of education of the workers). These variables are embedded in detail subsequently.

Figure 2. 5: Internationalisation variables

Redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Choo & Mazzarol, 2001.

Source: Choo & Mazzarol (2001, pp.167)

2.4.6.1 Ownership structure and international propensity

The focus within this area is the connection between the ownership framework of the SME and its effect on the internationalisation process of the firm. Studies have focused more on the relationship of family-owned business and corporate ownership, exploring whether these have an impact that will lead to internationalisation of SME products (Fernández and Nieto, 2006). Patterning to the influence of the independent ownership (e.g, the CEO sole controller of business) and the corporate ownership (subsidiary or minor ownership) and the influence it has on the SME international investment (Gupta *et al*, 2017). Additionally, there has been some analysis focused on public proprietorship of business (civic limited liability), the private business ownership (personal limited liability), and the role it has on the internationalisation propensity of small enterprises (Luostarinen, 1979; Axelsson & Easton, 1992). Some scholars have focused on organisational investors and their scope of influence for SMEs to undertake international activities (Suresh & Ramraj, 2012)

Furthermore, investigation on wholly domestic businesses as opposed to the partial domestic ownerships (i.e. firms with internationally owned and locally owned branches) has been impacting upon the export propensity of SMEs (Zineldin, 2007; Abor & Harvey, 2008). The current study seeks to examine the influence and the role of wholly domestic firms and partially domestic firms on the internationalisation process of manufacturing SMEs in Cameroon. This is unlike previous studies, that had a focus on the influence of ownership framework (e.g. the public ownership, corporate ownership and private ownership) on the international decision (Calof, et al., 1995)

The essential synergy that occurs between the foreign investors and the local firms have a positive effect on the SME's internationalisation propensity (Lu & Hébert, 2005). This encourages the development of policies that attracts foreign partnership in the host market. For instance, tax allowances, investment incentives and the lifting of high duties (Amato and Amato, 2007). Therefore, the current studies sub-theme of ownership structure may help to produce results that can influence policies aligned to the attraction of investment to Cameroon. According to (Lu & Hébert, 2005). the essence of foreign investment is to augment the local firms in terms of resource capacity, development of technologies, human capital, managerial expertise, global network chain, distribution networks, and international markets know-how. Whilst the benefits from the resource capacity mentioned are beneficial, the investors also gain from the host market (Zhang, et al., 2009). The local indigenous firms stand to benefit because SMEs comprise 80% of the economy.

Classifying the gains attained by the host country, SMEs benefit from the relationship and networks from foreign organisations. These benefits are in the form of productive spill-overs and international spill-overs. Similarly, competition between the international investors and the local firms will bind the local firms' capacity and creative spill-overs. On the other hand, foreign investor's activities such as networking, and alliances, will directly affect the ability of

the local host firms to take part in international activities international spill-overs (Rugman, 2010).

Previous studies suggest that the international investors will attract the local indigenous firms to get involved in international activities (Kneller & Pisu, 2007). Within this, studies conducted in British manufacturing SMEs between 1992 and 1999 found that the international effect is not directly influenced by UK indigenous SMEs. In fact, the export decision of the UK's domestic firms was not directly influenced by the relationships and alliances they created with the multinational firms (Kneller & Pisu, 2007). Similarly, Barrios et al (2003) found that between 1990 and 1998, Spanish firms produced results like the UK based firms, thereby confirming foreign MNC's international behaviour. On the contrary, (Fisher, et al., 2007). found that the activities of the local firm's exportation spill-overs are affected by the structure of the firms. Some studies have found that international firms are negatively affected by the (Kneller & Pisu, 2007) international propensity and the intensity of Irish enterprises (Okpara & Wynn, 2007) found an association between the activities carried by MNCs and international propensity.

In Indonesia, studies analysed the influence of international ownership structure of the external propensity of Indonesian SMEs (Simon, 2009) It was found that the exportation of plants by the manufacturing sector was likely to encourage internationalisation than the wholly owned local plants. In a similar vein, studies on Ugandan enterprises with international connections and external ownerships were found to be more internationally focused than their counterparts that are owned domestically (Niringiye, et al., 2010). In Cameroon, firms' internationalisation activities were found to be associated with that foreign ownership structure (Rankin, et al., 2006; OECD, 2009; Niringiye, et al., 2010)

According to the OECD (2013), it is important for a government to set policies that will attract foreign investors. There is a need for policies that will attract foreign investors in Cameroon.

In fact, policies that attract investors provide an opportunity for investors to allocate dividends and capital interest on foreign debts (WEF, 2016). For instance, Cameroon has policies such as the industrial free zone (IFZ), which allows SMEs to have 35% Cameroon equity ownership. The IFZ also include an array of incentives such as 10-year free taxation policy and 15% of corporate tax when extended to the 11th year (Moen and Servais, 2002). Further, there was a suspension of pending audits of licensing from 1996 to 1999 for a 3-year duration, which encouraged enterprises that are fully involved in international activities with over 80% of their output, granting those licences by the NOIFZ (National Office for Industrial free Zone). Moreover, in 2003 Cameroon lifted taxes and levies on SMEs and declared them an IFZ (MINEPAT, 2010). This encouraged a huge amount of foreign direct investment activities in Cameroon.

2.4.6.2 Firm Size and International Propensity

The resource-based view and the stage theory of international business focus on the essence of the ownership of materials and stocks, the size of a business/firms or the industrial capacity of the business (Cavusgil, 2004; Hall & Cook, 2009). The RBV and the stage theory suggest that the bigger the size of a firm, the more likely the firm's involvement in international activities. This is because of a huge resource base and the capabilities that will enable them to internationalise (INS, 2011)

The RBV focuses more on the bulk as well as the nature of the firms, internal material stocks, whilst the stage theory is more concerned with the bulk of the firm's ability to be involved in international activities as an outcome of its resources (Hall and Cook, 2009). However, a substantial amount of resources is important to determine a firm's international capacity and business growth (Welch & Welch, 2009). That illustrates a synthesis of prior research predicting the international propensity of firms before 1992 (Bonaccorsi, 1992)

Table 2. 4: Impact of firm size on international behaviour

Authors, publication date and overall explanation	Main Results	Experiential support
Ried (1983), a review on the studies carried on 21 samples of the size of firm and international behaviour	The size of a firm, is predicted to be directly related to the international/non-international variable	Three studies supported the hypothesis developed in the main results out of four
Gemunden (1991) a comprehensive review on 50 cases, illustrating 30 based on the size as one of its independent variables.	the size of firm is related to the export/non-export variable	11 out of the 12 results from the studies carried out support the hypothesis developed
Miesenbock (1988), overall studies on 200 research findings.	The firm size and international propensity indicate a positive relationship among each other	The hypothesis developed in the research indicated 20 of the results were supportive to the empirical findings

Source: Adopted and Adjusted from Bonaccorsi (1992, pp.607)

Some of the studies found a relationship between the size of the firm and its international behaviour while others did not. Additionally, the empirical study carried out on Italian enterprises gives an insightful meaning of the association between firm size and a firm's involvement in international activities (Bonaccorsi, 1992). Others found no association between firm size and its propensity to internationalise (Hall and Cook, 2009). Reid (1983) argued that the size of a firm is not valuable in terms of influencing international propensity. Others suggest that the larger the size of the firm, the more likely it is to be involved in international activities than smaller enterprises (Hall and Cook, 2009). Similarly, Phillips (2012) in attempt to understand the impact a firm size has on the internationalisation, conducted a study on 380 manufacturing SMEs in Australia. It was found that firm size has little or no effect on the international behaviour of a firm.

Paradoxically, although the size of a firm represents the productive capacity of a business, it might not be depicting factors that determine a firm's internationalisation. On the contrary, some studies have found that firm size has significance in the internationalisation process (Hall and Tu, 2004). For instance, Hall and Tu (2004) conducted a study of 42721 plants in the UK and found a positive relationship between a firm's exportation and its size. Similarly,

(Hutchinson, et al., 2005) conducted a study of 2822 plants from 49 various industries in the USA. It was found that there is a positive relationship between a firm's size and international behaviour. They propose that a minimal employable force of 20 employees should be the threshold of a firm that intends to carry out international activities (Hutchinson, et al., 2005). Scholars suggest that the key driver for internationalisation is the fixed cost element of international business (McDougall & Oviatt, 1997).

(Hutchinson, et al., 2005), are of the view that the cost dimension related to the international business is justifiable and asserts the importance of a firm's size. A firm's productivity is also important to consider before engaging in international business (Obokoh, 2008). Consequently, economies of scale on fixed cost expectations make it debatable that the size of the company is a valuable factor that predicts the international activities. The economies of scale expectation indicate the effect of standard cost less on bigger firms than small firms. For instance, the larger involvement in terms of activities or sales levels and increase market share. Within this context, firms in Cameroon are generally very small. The literature suggests that 85% of the firms in Cameroon are small medium firms. Considering this, the connections between the firm's size and the propensity to internationalise needs further investigation within the context of Cameroon.

2.4.6.3 Age of Firm and Internationalisation Propensity

Previous studies suggest that the international activities of firms can be associated with the period the firm has been in existence (Hall, 2007). The stage theory and RBV theories assert that a firm's age influences the internationalisation propensity (Hall, 2007). Both the RBV and the stage theories assert that resources depict the firm's performers in the sector of the industry, be it locally or internationally. The stage theory emphasises upon the importance of prior empirical knowledge in the international business. It also recognises the long-term period for practical experiential knowledge to be acquired by a firm. This implies that the older firms

have high capacity, huge resources, and human capital than a new firm in same the industry (Hutchison, 2007). These are important resources that are needed for the internationalisation process.

Scholars suggest that the size of the firm and the ownership framework influence the internalisation process (Zahra, 2005). However, this varies across firms and industries. For instance, a study conducted on born global or international new ventures suggests that it is not usual for a firm to have presence in the international market at the inception stage (Zahra, 2005). Therefore, the presence of these firms in foreign markets is contrary to the view that there is a positive relationship between the age of a firm and n its propensity to internationalise (McDougall, et al., 2009) suggests that it is unlikely for firms to internationalise at a very young stage of their initial creation. In a similar vein, (Babatunde, 2002)conducted a study on the export behaviour of manufacturing SMEs in the textile and garment sector of Ghana. There was not much evidence that supported the relationship between the age of a company and its export propensity.

Similarly, a study conducted Moen and (Servais & Rasmussen, 2000)focused on Norway, Denmark, and France, and found that there is limited confirmation on the effect of a firm's age on its internationalisation propensity. A study conducted by Aced and Jones (2007) focused on the cross-national examination of Finland, Ireland, and Norway in connection with the gradual international development assumption based on the stage theory. The results failed to support the gradual hypothetical influence of a firm's age on export propensity. Chen (2006) also attained similar results.

The international propensity of firms' is not determined by the age or how long they have been in existence, data from the study on Swedish firms goes to prove that the age of a firm does not affect the international behaviour (Anderson et al., 2004). As they age over the years, firms

experience the structural inertia, which makes them comfortable in the local market, and yet, are hesitant to take internationalisation (OECD, 2013; Williamson, 2008).

The effect of globalization has meant that the stage theory has to be revisited in terms of the period to which firms are to wait so as to gain necessary experience that will enable them to engage in international activities (Brouthers & Nakos, 2004). Globalization has made it possible for business owners to counteract the inurement of gradualism, the stage model, and provided an opportunity for firms to have a constant stream of valuable and reliable knowledge. Thus, age of the firm is not significant in the decision to internationalise a business (Braun & Clarke, 2016). In fact, age is not a valuable determinant to the internationalisation of a firm (Hall and Cook, 2009). The networks created, and a tie developed also makes it possible for firms to access a wide range of resources. These resources are vital for firms that embark on internationalisation. Yet, the stage theory focuses on a slow method of resource acquisition and knowledge development (Ruzzier & Antoncic, 2007).

However, (Brouthers & Nakos, 2004) reviewed a sample of studies conducted in Greece and found that a firm's age is related to an increased level of international business involvement. Similarly, (Anderson, 2002) found that manufacturing SMEs in the USA revealed a positive relationship between age of a firm and the propensity to engage in international business. Insights were obtained from a sample of 20 manufacturing SMEs. Considering this, the older and more experienced a firm is, the more likely it is to engage in international activities. It must be pointed out that a firm's years of experience and existence in an industry helps to generate a wealth of knowledge and other resources.

2.4.6.4 Human Capital Resource and Internationalisation Propensity

The literature suggests that the human capital resource is closely connected to the owners or managers' deposition and their role on the business' international behaviour (Okpara & Wynn,

2007; Mardanov, 2003). In a similar vein, (Oliveira & Fortunato, 2006) reviewed the dimensions of a businesspersons' human resource. This included the entrepreneur's international abilities and expertise, their international awareness, international business trips, managerial know-how, orientation of the external environment and the risk that are involved.

Hall and Cook, (2009) suggest that the human capital resource of an entrepreneur has different dimensions. Firstly, the lack of education or a certain level of degree alienated to intellectual capacity. Secondly, prior experience on business has a role or effect on the entrepreneurial dimension. Thirdly, possible leadership characteristics, in terms of managerial experience are related to international focused firms. The question of the entrepreneur's effect on international business has received a lot of attention, especially on the human capital aspect. This has addressed questions related to the level of education, gender and the age or experience that the businessperson has (Abor & Harvey, 2008)

However, other researchers focused on investigating the human resource dimension of the managerial team from the business-owner firm and its role within the internationalisation process (Ayittey & Goerge, 1992; Cuervo-Cazurra, 2008b; Calof, et al., 1995). Another group of scholars also focused on the role of human capital on the overall workforce of the businessperson's firm and it is influenced on the international propensity (Anderson, 2000). This research is informed by the understanding that the employees experience and skills competence is naturally related to their educational level. Following from this, the highly oriented and educated the employees are the more likely the entrepreneur business will engage in international activities (Aldrich, et al., 2006; Quer, et al., 2007)

Given this theoretical background, it is reasonable to assume that the age, gender, the level of education as well as the composition of the managerial team are the main factors that influence the internationalisation process of a firm. It must also be understood that the success of a

business and its international activities is an outcome of the skilled set of the employee's contributions as well as the managerial team.

The theory of knowledge spill-over has influenced the workforce on human capital and speeds up the international market decisions made by firms (O'Farrell, et al., 1998). The knowledge spill-over theory is transferable from one firm to another. This offers direct and indirect ways for firms to carry out their activities. For instance, technical innovative ideas, product knowledge creation, routines and regular institutional process can all contribute to the success of a firm's international activities. This has a positive influence on the host firm's international behaviour and decision to expand their activities across national borders.

The literature suggests that the impact of knowledge and its spill-over could be from within the industry, operates in a cluster, and geographically linked (O'Farrell, et al., 1998) In fact, the main primary form of knowledge influence on a firm is by mobilising the employees within the same environmental region (Fable et al., 2002). Similarly, Lee et al (2000) are of the view that the workforce mobility from one company to another facilitates the spread of knowledge. Following from this, the acquisition of knowledge benefits the nation through regional gains. Relating it to the international propensity, the acquisition of knowledge by employees helps to spread tacit information to firms, and this has a positive impact on the internationalisation decision.

2.4.7 The Born Global Theory

Born Global theory was first introduced in the early 19th century, which has been used as a standard term for quick growth and development for small and medium size enterprises as a way of internationalising their businesses (Chen, 2006). The theory has been studied and defined in many ways, but the pioneering explanation was given by Chen (2006). However, prior to the emergence of the Born Global theory, there have been other names given to fast

growing firms. For instance, Phillips et al., (2009) explored companies that internationalised at a fast pace and called these companies 'innate exporters. Later, it was found that high-tech start-ups indulge in the international market from inception. Meanwhile, (Fayolle & Liñán, 2014) embarked on a study to evaluate 310 Australian companies that are fully focused on exportation. They categorized the companies into the Traditional Exporters and the Born Global enterprises. It was the initial preliminary usage of the word "Born Global", which identified business exporting firms that carry out 75% of sales, from inception in the first 2 years of creation. These also focus on international activities in the life span of the business. Scholars have reviewed the born global concept and introduced the term "International New Ventures" (Oviatt and McDougall, 2009).

For a comprehensive understanding of the Born Global concept, it is essential that the study surrounding the internationalisation phenomena of the born global theory be examined for extensive understanding on how it managed to mitigate the challenges encountered by SMEs. Sub-sequentially, the arrival of the new milieu of business operation by born global or global start-ups (Welch and Welch, 2009), adopted by firms prior to the arrival have been challenged. Proponents of born global especially contrast the stage approach way of expanding beyond borders, with early internationalisation firms or instant internationalisation from inception, and argue that this enhances the business and gain market shares (Knight and Cavusgil, 1996; Meon and Servais, 2002).

An obvious observation is that most high-technological business belongs to this rather recent internationalization phenomenon. Unlike the stage approach such as the Upsala model, the born global theory explains that firms from initial stage of creation are entirely internationally focused, as such the process to which they internationalize do not involve a long stage (Lorenzen & Mudambi, 2013). For instance, these companies create a multiplicity of markets

concurrently with the use of entrepreneurial and pro-active schemes for the exploitation of opportunities in a quick responsive manner (O'Farrell, et al., 1998)). Plausibly, the born global firms are often on a smaller scale of business and are very lucrative and innovative with a high potential to achieve extreme growth (Jolly et al, 1992).

In respect to the study, it will be of good explanation for the readers to comprehend the actual role of the born global market, as it is noticeable that they are most companies that deal with high-tech or innovative technology identifies as global start-ups. But in recent times, other companies from different sectors particularly the manufacturing sector have joined the born global group of internationalizing by targeting niche markets (Moen and Servais, 2002).

Whereas there is an increase of different category of firms that globally internationalised from initial creation and are contributing to the global economy (Moen and Servais, 2002). The justification for the increase of born global firms and global start-ups in the world today is explained by (i) Liberal rules and new trade barriers for entry into international markets; (ii) the advanced managerial skills of human resource alongside computer and technological enhancement; and (iii) the development of international entrepreneurs, owners of business, as everyone can become with little skills and not much capital. These entrepreneurs have the focus of internationalizing (Moen and Servais, 2002).

However, the managers of these global start-ups do not only have the problems of creating a new business, but also, they are faced with the internationalisation challenges. Hence, the managerial competency must be such that, they are able to communicate an international strategy that cut across individual staff and are fully supported for the implementation. It is also crucial to take advantage of opportunities that the international market brings. It is equally essential that they can identify competitiveness in the foreign market and be decisive.

Moreover, the flexibility and adaptability of small firms serves as an advantage (Vahlne, et al., 2011)

Success in small enterprises is often attributed to global start-ups. These rely mostly on the network and relationship that have been established by managers and other business actors (Oviatt and McDougall, 2005). The business owners (entrepreneurs/managers) who can create influential connections with clients, suppliers and even competitors create a competitive advantage for their companies (McDougall, 2009). Thus, international entrepreneurship is an important field (Anderson and Wictor, 2003; Oviatt and McDougall, 2005).

2.4.8 Resource Based View (RBV)

The fast pace of globalisation meant that companies must change from using the slow incremental method of internationalising (Gupta et al, 2017). As such, the universal use of the incremental approach became out-dated. Therefore, this gave rise to opportunities for patenting and legally protecting strategic assets such as human or material resources. The resources also included finance, production lavatories, information/data, scholarly property, or technical skills, and were perceived as strategic resources for internationalisation. (OECD, 2013)The RBV approach helps us to understand the internationalisation process of firms through the accessibility and convenience of resources in the foreign markets. Meanwhile, the contingency theory focuses on the period, context, and complexity of the resources (Baum, et al., 2011).

The resource-based theory supports a firm's principal competitive advantage and relies on highly talented and effective workforce to advance for competitors to copy. Consequently, the RBV provides an essential theoretical base for understanding the internationalisation process. This is a resource upon which relationships and networks can be created and understood within the host country and the domestic market (Ibeh & Wheeler, 2005). On the other hand, the contingency theory focuses on the idea that there is no best or single approach to organising

and managing a business. Therefore, business owners should not rely on a model to maintain the organization; rather they should develop a unique managerial strategy that suits a situation. Scholars suggest that it is of essence that great relationship be established between the shareholders and the management of the business to make sure the company is successful (McDougall, et al., 2009)

According to (OECD, 2018) organizations that indulge in niche products target international markets and carry out international activities at early stage of creation. They adopt this approach because of the challenges and limitations within the domestic markets. However, some firms produce niche product for deliberate use in the global market (Bigsten & Söderbom, 2006).

Although, small firms experience a shortage of products and resources, they are most likely to internationalise than the MNCs. This is because international entrepreneurs are fully equipped and make use of technological developments. Crick and Spence (2005) call for a further study on how small enterprises can tackle overwhelming shortage of resources and still manage to internationalise. Regarding small international enterprises, the networks, RBV and the contingency theories consider the eventual challenges and the complex environmental factors.

Consequently, studies after the resource base view drift attention and focus on internationalization behaviour of SMEs. As such, the study is enriching with knowledge that is fundamentally focused on the SMEs literature (EuropeanCommision, 2008)

Scholars suggest that SMEs accounts and responds to internationalisation stimuli positively because of its advantage of unique resources (Brouthers et al., 2009). Thus, the importance of the RBV variables on SME's internationalisation involves the internal resource variable of the firm. These resources could be either tangible or intangible (Amato and Amato, 2007). The stillness and limitless characteristics of the resources indicates the peculiarity of SMEs

competitive advantage (Hall & Cook, 2009). The researcher further investigated the resource theory (Weshtead *et al.*, 2001.). It was found that the basic assumption of the RBV is unchangeable. Yet, the business environment is not static.

However, the RBV theory, like the stage, network, and other internationalisation theories, has a broad application to the internationalisation of SMEs. For instance, the literature surrounding SMEs internationalisation focuses on export strategies of small enterprises (McDougall et al, 2009; Westhead et al, 2001; Ibeh, 2003; Ruzzier et al, 2006). Some studies critic stage theories, which overlook the managerial and ownership effect of SMEs international behaviour analyses (Ruzzier et al., 2006). On the other hand, they are of the perspective that the RBV considers SME's ownership influence in examining the international behaviour of SMEs (McDougall et al., 1999; Ibeh, 2003;). Figure 2.2 illustrates the relationship between the RBV theory and SMEs international behaviour.

Figure 2. 6: Resource based framework

Redaction due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in McDougall et al, 1994.

Source: McDougall et al, (1994, pp.345)

2.4.9 Contingency Theory

The contingency theory is grounded in the fact that an organization international growth is contingent on a broad range of market or business specific factors. Thus, firms have different

ways to which they can internationalise, that could be acquisition, product relocation and search of affordable labour nations, strategic relationships, and mergers in different environments (Moen and Servais, 2002). Small firms have the advantage to skip stages and benefit from the psychic distance and born global approach. Therefore, in response to the dynamic growth in the global milieu, SMEs have an opportunity to internationalise, and adopt a variety of approaches to compete effectively in the international markets (Zahra, 2005).

Consequently, neither the external level programmes set in place are enough for the existing internationalised firms to improve their international activities and growth performance. Some scholars are contended that a small business responds positively to stimulus such as internal resource capacity, subjective managerial or owner aspiration that promotes the business from just being domestically focused into becoming internationally drawn through foreign entry and global growth (Ibeh, 2003; Sousa et al., 2008). Nonetheless, some scholars suggest that the effective growth of SMEs in the international arena were developed on research carried out on the internationalisation process of emerging market firms. These studies focused on economies in Europe, Asia, and North America.

2.5 Barriers of Internationalisation

Some scholars have focused on the general barriers of internationalisation (Hutchinson *et al.*, 2009). They did not focus on perceptions but were more attentive to the actual challenges encountered by firms within the internationalisation process (Tesfom & Lutz, 2006). In fact, international barriers are defined as any challenges that hinder the ability of SMEs to initiate, create and sustain international activities beyond borders (WorldBank, 2013; Tesfom & Lutz, 2006).

Hutchinson et al., (2009) conducted a study on the UK's retail sector. This was based on 12 SMEs, and the challenges that they faced within the context of internationalisation. Similarly,

OECD (2009), conducted a study focused on the internationalisation barriers of SMEs. Below is a breakdown of the internal and external barriers of internationalisation that were identified.

2.5.1 Internal Barriers of internationalization

1. Company Characteristics: the strength of a company is drawn from its internal resources.

Therefore, the characteristics of a firm in terms of the size, age, management skills are important considerations for internationalisation.

2. Knowledge and information Barrier: the importance of knowledge and information is that it gives the opportunity for firms to wilfully participate international markets (McDougall, 1989) However, it is not that simple for firms as they confront difficulties in carrying out research in the international market. Although firms have a methodical approach to internationalisation, they are often faced with challenges related to quality, comparability, source, authenticity of information.

3. Managerial Barriers: the challenges that SMEs face in the process of initiating international activities, is because of the human resource competences. In this sense, the manager in-charge of international marketing, international business, and international strategy must be experienced and equipped with knowledge. However, there are certain problems that makes the internationalisation process difficult and these are: the managerial attitude towards employees and international process (Andersson, 2000; Zahra et al, 2000), inadequate international exposure and skills (Brouthers, et al., 2009) and a lack of commitment and relationship sustainability (Ahmad & Kitchen, 2008).

4. Financial Barriers: the capital and firm's income determine its internationalisation process. The cost for operating abroad is very expensive and is a challenge for most firms. Inadequate resources are also a challenge for firms to internationalise (Zahra et al, 2006).

2.5.2 External Barriers of internationalization

1. Market Barriers: the market awareness, plays a vital role in the international strategy of a firm, and an unfavourable environment will be a backdrop for company growth. According to OECD (2009), the government regulations encourages firms' export behaviour. Thus, it attracts investors into the market. However, countries with stringent rules pose trouble to SME that wish to internationalise. Another aspect is the cultural diversity, in other words, the psychic distance (Ellis, 2011). The domestic market also offer competition for the newcomers (Tesfom & Lutz, 2006)**2. Industry Specific:** the industry the SMEs operates in, is also another challenge, because there is high competitiveness, especially in the manufacturing sector as companies want to produce products that meet global standards (Chetty & Campbell-Hunt, 2003). Additionally, technological advancement has made it difficult and challenging for firms to compete and adapt in the industry.

3. Competitive rivalry: the difficulties SMEs face is the competition from their compatriots. A lack of established presence in the host market, the firms find it hard to access channels of distribution. Moreover, SMEs from underdeveloped countries like Cameroon find it hard to keep up with the competition because of insufficient funds, and human resource skills (Buckley, 2011; Andersson & Florén, 2008)

4. Consumer Barriers: consumer perception of product quality gave birth to consumer barriers. Thus, quality of product and the standard must be acceptable at a global level. Another challenge is because of the country in which the product is manufactured. Some consumers have stereotypical views about products from some countries. These views affect buying perceptions (Zahra, 2006).

2.6 Current Economic Trend in Cameroon

According to the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2018), Cameroon has three main sectors, that is, the service sector, agriculture, mining, and other

natural resources (OECD, 2004). The services sector is made up of three sub sectors including restaurant and hotels services, other commercial services, and governmental services. Within this, according the manufacturing sector accounts for 16% of the country's GDP and provides an opportunity for increased growth in the country (OECD, 2004). The combined services sector accounts for 43% of the country's GDP employing over 60% of the labour force (OECD, 2014). This is also the leading contributor to the country's GDP (OECD, 2014).

Secondly, agriculture is one of the leading contributors to Cameroon's economy and is made up of sub-sectors such as cultivation of cocoa, coffee, tea, vegetables, and other crops. Other subcategories involve cattle rearing, poultry production and fish farming activities. Mechanized farming is not widespread, and farmers lack the mechanized tools for large scale production, thereby resulting in low productivity supported by underdeveloped subsistence farming methods. This sector accounts for 22% of the country's GDP and employs about 35% of the work force. There are missed opportunities for food processing, an area that could be utilised by SMEs to produce products that are destined for the international market.

The mining sector and other natural resources is a major sector which is supported by Cameroon's GDP. Oil and gas exploration have consistently funded government revenue until the recent erratic fluctuations in oil prices. Major oil exploration companies are foreign based. Their investment is focused on extracting the raw material. It is important to note that the processing of these raw materials is done in foreign countries, and not Cameroon. This is cause for concern as there are missed opportunities to empower local small and medium enterprises, as illustrated by the 11% contribution to GDP from this sector (OECD, 2014).

2.6.1 Cameroon's Development Framework after Independence

Cameroon has a negative net export which has increased by approximately 365% in the past twenty years. This has had a negative impact on the country's balance of payments. Due to the

net export deficit, Cameroon has sought to attract more foreign investors. The structural adjustment program (SAP) was implemented in 1990 and stretched for a 17-year period to 2007 and revised to 2013. Within SAP, tariffs were related. Similarly, the requirements for capital transfers out of the country were relaxed. The SAP covered two phases. The first phase was between the year 1990 and the year 2000. The second phase was between the year 2000 and the year 2013. The intention of SAP was to address the depression Cameroon faced between the years 1984 and 1985. This was a result of the fall in oil prices.

In 2011, the Cameroonian government announced vision 2035, designed to steer the country to becoming an emerging economy. The 1st phase sought to open the Cameroon market and improve the ease of doing business. Phase two was concerned with stimulating exports and allocating resources to more productive sectors of the economy. It is within this area of stimulating exports that the activities of SMEs in the manufacturing sector are of importance. For this study, the focus must not be just about exports, but internationalising the activities of SMEs. This view is reinforced by the intention to build infrastructure and improve investment in capital intensive projects. Within this context, the manufacturing capacity of industry is enhanced, thereby improving exports and global presence. This global presence is not just through exports, but by the internationalisation of SMEs.

2.6.2 Export Manufacturing and Diversification in Cameroon

In the period until the 1990's, Cameroon's export consisted of raw materials of oil and gas, as well as other mineral resources. Most of these exports were unprocessed, meaning that there was a missed opportunity to conduct processing within Cameroon. For instance, unprocessed agricultural products such as cocoa, coffee, banana and rubber found its way into the export market. The missed processing opportunity meant missed opportunities to create jobs within Cameroon.

The implementation of the SAP focused more on creating manufacturing firms such as CHOCOCAM, ALUCAM, STEELCAM, MICHELIN, and ELF Petroleum alongside most of state corporations that were privatized like HEVECAM, SONEL to AES Sonel, and SNEC to CAMWATER. The intention was to promote and encourage efficiency in the manufacturing industry (Njimanted, Taku and Mbohjim, 2015). And yet, a lot of products were still exported unprocessed. This is cause for concern. To encourage manufacture export in Cameroon, the Franc CFA was devalued by 50% with the aim of making imports expensive and export cheaper. The intention was to help Cameroonian products compete at the international market. The government later enacted an Investment Charter in 2002 to further boost the competitiveness of the manufacturing firms, with the intention of attaining rapid economic growth.

The export diversification policy in Cameroon was encouraged by the structural reforms, economic liberalization, and privatization. Within this, some state-owned enterprises were privatised, and meant the demise of state monopolies and allowing free market factors to determine prices without government interference. To improve market access for Cameroon's export, focus was on agricultural products (Cocoa, Coffee, Banana, Rubber, Mineral resources (Petroleum and aluminium) and Forestry rubber (UNCTAD, 2014)

At the end of the year 2000 the World Bank along with IMF agreed to a debt reduction program for Cameroon under the highly indebted poor countries (HIPC) initiative (World Bank, 2016). This reduced Cameroon's debt burden in financing loans under the SAP. There was a focus on investing to improve the economy. Within this, there was a focus on the manufacturing sector and exports.

In 1990 towards the end of the first tranche of the SAP (1990 – 2000), the total amount of export for non-traditional export commodities rose to \$44.6 million representing about 7.6%

of total export earnings for the year. A further increase of \$50.5 million represented 9.4% of total export earnings in 2003. This increase in exports led to optimism for the country. From the year 2000 onwards, programs to improve and encourage exports were implemented. The intention was to augment manufacturing exports and improve the middle-income status of the citizenry in Cameroon. The investment charter implemented under the auspices of the Cameroon Chamber of Commerce aimed to ease requirements of doing business and encourage foreign investment in the manufacturing sector. This had a positive impact on the export capacity of the country (World Bank, 2016).

Other export led programs included agricultural competitiveness projects funded by the International Development Association (IDA). These focused on the production of rice, maize, broilers, and pork. This helped to increase the production of rice by 25%, maize by 15% (World Bank, 2013). In addition, in the year 2004, Cameroon signed the Millennium Challenge Corporation (MCC). The MCC's scheme was offered by the US government as a bilateral scheme and sought to transform Cameroon's agricultural output through internationalization (MCC GOV). This presents opportunities for SMEs in the food manufacturing sector.

Despite Cameroon's push to improve its export and its balance of payment, its manufacturing export involvement and performance is still very low, as illustrated in table 3.1. This indicates that there are still untapped potential and opportunities within Cameroon's manufacturing sector. It is the contention of this study that SME manufacturing can capitalise on this to internationalise their activities with the intention of contributing to improving the performance of Cameroon's manufacturing exports.

Figure 2. 7: Manufacturing exports by industry

Redaction due to copyright restriction. Original figure can be found at World Integrated Trade Solutions, 2010.

Source: World integrated trade solutions (2010)

Compared to Congo and Ivory Coast, Cameroon has the lowest result as exporter of manufactured goods. It is not clear why Cameroon lacks behind in exports among most African countries. Implicitly, it is argued that the reason for Congo's export supply being above those of Cameroon and Ivory Coast stems from a few factors. According to data from observatory of economic complexity (OECD, 2018), while Cameroon and Togo's manufacturing intensity are denominated in in Agriculture and Petroleum sub-sectors, that of Congo is spread across industries that are vital to the international economy

In addition, the International Monetary Fund (IMF, 2016) has posited that the export manufacturing output of Cameroon is not an indication of the amount of export-led policies implemented so far. For example, the total export as a percentage of GDP for Cameroon has dropped between the year 2002 and the year 2016, as illustrated in figure 3.2.

Figure 2. 8: Cameroon's exports/GDP

Redaction due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at World Bank, 2015.

Source: World Bank (2015)

In figure 2.8, the vertical axis represents the cost of exports in percentages, while the horizontal axis is the years. Following from this, between the year 2002 and 2007, the industrial exports of Cameroon as a proportion of GDP declined. And yet, over the same period, there was an increase in foreign direct investment. It remains a paradox that that despite the growth in FDI as well as increased export-led strategies, the global involvement and development among I Cameroon's organizations continues to decline. This is cause for concern. This suggests that there is a problem of low export performance and involvement amongst firms in Cameroon. It is unclear why few firms choose to export whilst most others remain focused on the domestic market.

Although Cameroon's present international manufacturing involvement and performance is low, the country has opportunities to grow its exports by encouraging SMEs to produce for the international markets (IMF, 2017). Apparently, the landscape for competition in the foreign or external markets was carried out by most big firms in the past (McDougall and Oviatt, 2000).

Though there is an increase of global participation of African business, there is still a dearth of studies that focus on the internationalisation of SME business activities.

2.6.3 Foreign Direct Investment Manufacturing industry

The global market of foreign direct investment (FDI), as illustrated in figure 3.3 reveals an increase in the emerging economies small medium enterprises (SMEs) as one of the valuable ones among them (Sauvant et al, 2009). The OECD-APEC carried out research in the 2007 focused on removing barriers to SMEs access to foreign markets. That led to a general realisation of the factors affecting the internationalisation process of SMEs. As a result, there has been a drive to deepen understanding on barriers affecting the internationalisation of SMEs (OECD, 2013).

Figure 2. 9: Global FDI outflows by economic groups

A large black rectangular redaction box covers the area where Figure 2.9 would be. At the bottom of this box, there is a white rectangular area with a red border containing the text: "Redaction due to copyright restriction. Original figure can be found at UNCTAD, 2009."

Redaction due to copyright restriction. Original figure can be found at UNCTAD, 2009.

Source: UNCTAD (2009)

While most FDI activities have been from one Asian country to another, there has also been investment from European nations (Estonia, Chile, Slovenia, and Russia) and the United States. There was a steady increase in international investment from the mid-1980s to the year 2000 (UNCTAD, 2015). Whilst the rest of the world experienced FDI growth, on the African continent, FDI was on the decline. This is cause for concern. However, there is an increase in global participation of African business. From the year 2014, the African involvement in

foreign investments saw growth change from 0.2% in 2004 to 13% (UNCTAD, 2015). This was for the total FDI outflow investment (UNCTAD, 2015).

Figure 2. 10: FDI inflows by economic groups

Redaction due to copyright restriction. Original figure can be found at UNCTAD.

Source: UNCTAD (2015)

Figure 2.10 illustrates an increase in FDI outflows within developing economies. By the year 2018, FDI inflows rose to \$400 billion (UNCTAD, 2018).

Figure 2. 11: FDI inflows and outflows by economies

Redaction due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at UNCTAD, 2015.

Source: UNCTAD (2015)

Over half of FDI outflows in emerging and developing economies are in equity. On the contrary, in advanced economies, FDI outflows are in the form of reinvested earnings. This

may be a result of barriers to enter international markets from a developing economy perspective ((WEF, 2016).

2.6.4 Standard of Comparison of Sub-Saharan internationalization

Africa's largest economies is sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) includes South Africa, Angola, Ghana, and Nigeria. On the other hand, Cameroon is the largest in central Africa (CEMAC). In the 2016, the growth in Africa was revised substantially by IMF, reflecting difficult macroeconomic challenges. In Nigeria for example, due to the temporary disruption of oil production, inflation and currency shortage, electricity shortage and weak investor confidence, the growth had to be revised. In South Africa, policy uncertainty affected international trade. This resulted in a flat rate of GDP in 2016 with a minor recovery in 2017.

The increase of internationalization has led to several measures, which include the reduction of trade barriers, and improved integration of international activities. This is a growth strategy that can be used by SMEs around the world (Bigsten et al., 2004). And yet, in Cameroon, and in the literature, there is a dearth of studies that focus on the internationalisation of SMEs as a growth strategy.

2.6.4.1 Current Challenges and Major Trends of Africa Internationalization

One of the major challenges of internationalisation for Africa's SMEs is the low GDP per capita. For instance, Africa's GDP per capita in 2013 was \$3,221, as compared to \$29,570 for Europe, \$31,533 for Oceania, \$27,249 for Americas and \$8,622 for Asia (World Bank, 2013). And yet, the general trend of international operations of SMEs spurred from the boom of globalization. In fact, globalisation has largely affected SMEs as opposed to the larger firms. Of interest is that SMEs have the highest share in the international market (UNCTAD, 2011, OECD, 2009). This is an opportunity that can be capitalised by SMEs within the manufacturing sector in Cameroon. And yet, there is no clear strategy on the internationalisation of SMEs from Cameroon. This is of concern.

Failure to realise the internationalisation opportunities is often attributed to political instabilities and civil wars in Cameroon in recent years. For example, the destruction and wreckage of bridges, roads, communication equipment's, burning of houses, uprooting of people force to flee as refugees in Nigeria and other countries (United Nation, 2017).

The literature suggests that a firms' internationalisation is essential for a country's economic growth (Hausmann et al., 2007). Consistent with this, the growth in the economies of most industrialised nations over the past three decades is a result of their abilities to attain sustainable manufactured output and internationalisation (Teal, 2008). The idea of producing and distributing products and services globally has also helped to improve living standards in some countries. This has also helped firms to produce products and services that meet internationally recognised quality standards.

The ability to meet these international quality standards has often been used as a source of competitive advantage by large multinational firms. Within this, the literature finds that the sub-Saharan African (SSA) economic trade standard is highly dependent on international activities (export and import) of unprocessed raw materials that slow the nations' economic growth (Babatunde, 2002). Hence, there are missed manufacturing opportunities. Further studies suggest that the average international SMEs are more productive than their counterparts that are domestically oriented (Teal, 2008; Johanson & Vahlne, 2007, King et al., 2010).

(INS, 2011) conducted a study involving of 36 African nations. The focus was on internationally focused manufacturing firms. It was found that manufacturing led to an increase in market share and the rise in GDP (Erramilli, et al., 2002). After attaining their independence, most African countries became more focused on importation and substituting industrialised firms' policy (King et al., 2010). However, the industrial developed itinerary

did not last for long and then collapsed due to poor performance, and a failure to internationalise the manufactured products (Rankin et al., 2006).

Although Africa's population constitute the second largest continent in the universe with 15% after Asia its contribution to the worlds manufacturing international growth is only 1.5% (King et al., 2010). Within this, the countries that are largely manufacturing products with international focus are Botswana, Swaziland and South Africa exporting approximately \$100US per capita of manufactured goods between the 1990's and the early 2000's. Cameroon's contribution is less than \$10US per capita (King et al., 2010).

2.7 Proposed Conceptual Framework

A critical review of the contingency theory, the resource-based view, stage theory, and international entrepreneurship theory bring insights that can help to enhance our understanding of the internationalisation process of SMEs. The literature suggests that the factors that determine the internationalisation decision of SMEs are consistent from the external and internal challenges (Cardoza & Fornes, 2009; McDougall et al., 2007). Others suggest that significant aspects that influence and facilitate the process of internationalisation are related to the internal capacity and resources of the firm rather than the exterior factors (Braun and Clarke; 2016; Ibeh, 2003; Westhead et al., 2004). Although the macro level of internationalisation policies is important, they are not the only factors that constitute the ultimate barriers that prevent the internationalisation process of SMEs (McDougall et al., 2007; Williamson, 2008).

Figure 2. 12: Proposed conceptual framework

Source: Author's own construction

Neither are the external level programmes set in place are enough for the existing internationalised firms to improve their international activities and growth performance. As such, a small business responds positively to stimulus such as internal resource capacity, subjective managerial or owner aspiration. This promotes the business from just being domestically focused into becoming internationally drawn through foreign entry and global growth (Ibeh, 2003; Sousa et al., 2008). Whilst extant studies have focused more on the internationalisation process of SMEs in Europe, Asia, and North America (Ibeh, 2003), much to the neglect of the internationalisation process of SMEs from emerging economies such as Cameroon.

Due to socio-economic differences in the context of emerging economies and developed economies, there is need for more studies that bring insights about the internationalisation process of SMEs from less developed economies. Considering this, the current study extends the international operations of the research on SMEs by drawing insights from the Cameroon context. Unlike previous studies that were informed by single theories (Figueira et al., 2011; Williamson, 2008; Johansson & Valhne, 2009), the current study draws insights from multiple theoretical perspectives. The proposed integrated theoretic approach consists of the combination of the stage theory (Uppsala theory), network theory, born global theory, resource-based view theory, and international entrepreneurship theory.

The rationale supporting the integrated theoretical context for the research is guided by the understanding that the internationalisation of firms is complex and cannot be fully understood by drawing from a single theoretical framework. In this sense, it is imperative that the complexity of the process of international behaviour of firms be explored using integrated theories. This is unlike previous studies that have been informed by single theories (Coviello et al., 2011; Crick and Spence, 2005; Coviello & Cox, 2006).

Notwithstanding, the aforementioned argument that included previous researches using a single theory for the base of their research findings (Coviello et al., 2011; McDougall & Oviatt, 2007; Johanson & Vahlne, 2009; Bell, 1995; Leonidou, 2004, Williamson, 2008), the current study considers the influencing factor of the external environment when analysing the international behaviour of SMEs. In this sense, insights from the contingency theory help to supplement other theoretical understandings with the intention of establishing a comprehensive understanding of the internationalisation process of SMEs from Cameroon.

When it concerns the international barriers, there is a limitation to the theories apply to the barriers affecting SMEs internationalisation process in developed countries. What is known are

the barriers affecting the internationalisation of SMEs from more developed countries? And yet, much has been written about the internal and external factors that determines the entry strategy of international firms (Cavusgill & Zou, 2004; Leonidou, 2004; Tesfom et al., 2006). This is a result of theoretical models that are rooted in the internal and external environmental aspects. Considering this, we know more about the internal and external environmental aspects of the internationalisation of SMEs from more developed countries.

Therefore, it is important to create a framework that helps to understand the internationalisation process of SMEs from an emerging economy such as Cameroon. The proposed integrated approach benefits from theoretical triangulation, by drawing the best out of each of the theoretical understandings. This helps to enrich our understanding of the internationalisation process of SMEs. Thus, the conceptual framework adopted for the current study provide a robust strategic method in understanding the international barriers affecting the internationalisation process of SMEs within the context of an emerging economy such as Cameroon.

2.7.1 Issues to be Address from the conceptual framework

The conceptual framework points out the factors affecting manufacturing SMEs to internationalise. This is consistent with the focus of the study on the barriers affecting the internationalisation process of SMEs. Considering this, the proposed framework helps to understand : (a) the gradual process of SMEs international behaviour; (b) the psychological orientation as to why firms internationalise only to countries nearest to their borders; (c) the effort put in place by business organisations to utilise resources to achieve its global activities; and (d) the drive towards internationalisation influenced by the internal factors or resources with little external consideration on the challenges from the external environment.

Another aspect that needs to be investigated is the RBV theory. It lacks focus on the external environment of the internationalisation process of SMEs. Also, the RBV has not been able to account for the relevance of the macro-environment within the international markets, and external behaviours of SMEs. It is equally important to understand partnered network resources that help to enhance business operations. The literature suggests that SMEs are lacking in this area.

2.7.2 Justification of the Proposed Integrated Conceptual Framework

Previous studies on the internationalisation of SMEs have been focused on single theoretical insights (Coviello et al 2010; Bell, 2003; Moen and Servais, 2002), rather than being informed by multiple theoretical views. Considering this, it is crucial to integrate different theories to bring better understanding to the internationalisation process of SMEs. As such, the current study is informed by multiple theories to help bring better understanding to the internationalisation activities of SMEs. Insights are drawn from works conducted by different researchers (Tesform, 2006; Crick et al., 20011; Coviello & Martin, 2006; Hall and Cook, 2009). These authors used more than one conceptual outline. Considering this, the current study is contended that adopting more than one theoretical framework is crucial to give a holistic view and an understanding of the internationalisation characteristics of SMEs.

The use of multiple theoretical concepts in the study helps to bridge some of the limitations of using a single theory. Example of research studies prior to the current thesis that has used an integrated framework to address the issue. These include, firstly, McAuley (2010), who made use of RBV, contingency, and network theories. Coviello & Cook (2006), integrated the FDI, Uppsala, and Network theories. Finally, Hall & Cook (2008) used the stage and RBV theories.

Informed by previous studies, the current study used five integrated theoretical concepts to address the topic of the barriers affecting the internationalisation process of SMEs within the manufacturing sector in Cameroon. Individually, the theoretical frameworks have been used by researchers, such as, (McDougall et al, 2009; Bell et al., 2003; McAuley 2010; Zhang et al, 2009; Knight and Cavusgil 2004; Ruzzier & Antonnic 2007; as well as Moen and Servais, 2002), among others. The integrated frameworks are outlined in a way that they address the factors and barriers of internationalisation, thereby providing an efficient and a holistic robust study.

The use of the micro-environment and the contingency theory is to better achieve and understanding that shed lights in the barriers and challenges in the foreign market and other uncontrollable variables. These include external factors such as firm characteristics, product characteristics, industry barriers, market barriers and the macro-environment. The use of the contingency theory is to supplement the integrated theories to evaluate external influences from the environment on the international activities of SMEs.

2.8 Themes developed from the Integrated Conceptual Framework

The research developed themes that are summarised to compare the differences and similarities of the various integrated framework proposed. The emergent themes are illustrated in table 2.5.

Table 2. 5: Integrated framework

Theory	Author	Acronyms	Alternate names	independent Variables	Dependent Variable	Originated field of study
Stage Theory	Johanson & Vahlne (2009)	N/A	Upssala Model/Process theory	Psychic distance, firms' characteristics (size, age) domestic focus and market knowledge	International propensity and firm performance	International business studies

Network theory	Johanson & Mattson (1988)	N/A	Connection/Relationship theory	Informal and formal relationship resource (Information, training and capital etc.)	International propensity and firm performance	Sociology
International Entrepreneurship theory	McDougall & Oviatt(1994)	IE	International New Venture/born global	IE characteristics (risk-taker, innovative, global expertise, visionary)	International propensity and firm performance	Entrepreneurship study
Resource Based view	Barney (1991)	RBV	Resource based theory (RBT)	Micro tangible and intangible resources	International propensity and firm performance	Strategic management study
Contingency theory	Lorsh & Lawrence (1967)	N/A	Agency theory	Environmental factors example (economic, social, government, industry structure etc.)	International propensity and firm performance	Organisational science
THEMES	UPPSALA THEORY	RBV THEORY	NETWORK THEORY	IE THEORY	CONTINGENCY THEORY	
Market entry decision	Takes time after establishment in domestic market	Firms internal strength and resource	Informal and formal relationship and how much resource they have	From initial creation due to unique entrepreneurial expertise	The state of the Macro environment determines the entry decision	
Market Mode	Exportation	Could be export, franchise, license, depending on available resource	Joint venture, partnership, franchise depending on the relationship created	Inception through, export trade, direct sales, online marketing depending on individual behaviours	Whole-subsiary, license, due to the external environment in the host market and the organisation	
International sustainability	Not linear	Firms internal resource determines the sustainability	depending on the relationship created	depending on individual entrepreneur behaviour	Relationship between the organisation and the external environment determines if the firm can sustain internationalisation.	
International growth pace	slowly	Could be slow and could be fast, depends on the resource	Depends on the network relationship, so fast/slow	Inceptions, so it's fast	Fast pace however, certain circumstances is slow as result of the connection between the firm and external environment (eg government)	
Owner/managerial or organisational focused	Organisational focus	Both organisational and managerial	Both organisational and managerial	Entrepreneurial focus/managerial	Both organisational and managerial and environmentally focused	

Influence from environmental factors	Not real	No	Environmental effect	Environmental effect	Environmental effect
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Source: Author's own construction

2.8.1 The Sectorial impact and International Propensity

The external environment has an impact to the internationalisation process. As such, it is important to understand internationalisation within the context of the external environment. Previous studies amplify the importance of the external environment on SME internationalisation (Calof & Beamish, 1995; Zhao and Zou, 2002; Chetty & Agndal, 2007; Sousa et al., 2008). Researchers have focused on the domestic market features, international propensity, sectorial size, and industry factors (Chetty & Agndal, 2007; Sousa et al., 2008). Following from this, the current study draws insights from different manufacturing areas including textiles and garments, leather, rubber, machine sectors, wood, and other sub-sectors.

2.8.2 Domestically Focused SMEs (Non-International Behaviour)

This section of the literature addresses the behaviour of SMEs that have non-international behaviours. However, it is not only limited to non-internationalised SMEs, but also those SMEs that have internationalised and then stopped after facing some challenges (Leonidou, 1995; William, 2006). Whilst studies focus on the internationalisation of firm's behaviour, there is little attention on non-international business organisations (William, 2006). There is a dearth of studies on the non-internationalised and domestic focused firms in comparison with the export behaviour of most firms. The current study focuses on the barriers to internationalisation of SMEs. The literature suggests that there is a bias towards the internationalised firm's behaviour than domestic firms' behaviour (Leonidou, 1995). Studies also suggest that the domestic and non-export firms have a perception on the international environment and that some of the challenges that business faces in the initiation of international business do not encourage them get into the internationalisation process (Sutton, 2014)

According to Hall & Cook, (2009), the variables of firm's age, size and managerial capability are important in the international market. In this sense, when comparing the firms that internationalised to those that are domestically focused, variables that should be considered included size, number of employees, and so forth.

The domestically focused firms contribute very little to the gross domestic product, and the employability growth ratio in comparison with internationalised firms (Hall & Cook, 2009). Therefore, in order for these firms to contribute to economic growth, the policy makers must create policies and programmes that will encourage SMESs to internationalise (Whistead et al., 2003; Hall & Cook, 2006). Some scholars evaluate domestic non-international firm's perceptions about international barriers (Yang et al., 2006). For instance, (Zhao & Decker, 2004) identified the rationale behind the magnitude of difficulties perceived when doing international business.

However, many domestically focused firms encounter challenges that hinder their propensity to engage in international activities. A summary of the barriers that are encountered and perceived by non-international firms and the firms that have internationalised are illustrated below. These have been adapted from (Suresh & Ramraj, 2012)

Table 2. 6: International barriers

DOMESTIC FIRMS	LIKELY INTERNATIONALISE FIRMS
1. Size and Age of the firm	1. Lack of funds
2. Inadequate knowledge on international market and opportunities	2. Lack of international experience
3. Fear of the unknown in the international market	3. International competitiveness
4. High cost of international trade and tariffs barriers	4. High market cost
5. Lack of products to internationalise	5. Product standard and adaptation face from competitors
6. Inadequate finances	6. Lack of Governmental incentives
7. Inexperience or low managerial experience on international business	7. Limited market knowledge and low access channel of distribution

(Westhead & Wright, 2001) focused on the challenges encountered in the international business by small firms. These factors, as identified, are both internal and external.

2.9 Encouraging non-international SMEs to internationalise

Drawing from the literature, practitioners and policy makers can draw insights on how to engage in international activities. It is important to understand the triggers and motivators for firms to expand internationally (Leaonidou et al, 2007). The literature also suggests that it is important for SMEs to conduct research, acquired knowledge about their host market before attempting extension (Williams, 2008). Here, the focus is on the international stimuli and the factors that trigger businesses to engage international activities (Zahra, 2006; Anderson, 2009). The current study takes the view that the trigger for international behaviour is from internal (within). This means internationalisation is triggered by the need for corporate development (internal active behaviour) as well as the need to accumulate inventory (external responsive behaviour).

There are studies that emanated from the need to understand factors that stimulate internationalisation activities. For instance, (Leonidou et al, 2007) insightful findings on SMEs export behaviour through a synthesis of 40 different factors from 1974-2005. Further, (William 2008) focused on the international behaviour of 20 Caribbean SMEs. In a similar vein, (Hutchison et al, 2007) acknowledges that the internal active behaviour for firms was as result of brand identity, experience in the international market, profit from extra sales, specialised managerial interest, skills and possible business growth. The internal responsive factor revolves around domestic market saturation, domestic stagnation, urges to reduce domestic market dependency, excess capacity utilisation, and the need to clear extra inventory (Hutchison et al., 2007). On the other hand, the external active factor revolves around network contacts after trade fairs, attractive international market identification, knowledge/ information

on international market, as well as support from the government (William, 2008). The stimulation from the external responsive behaviour resulted from a highly competitive internal market, encouraging foreign exchange rate, overwhelming product demands from international customers, as well as the distance/proximity of the host market (Leaonidou et al., 2007). Interestingly, regardless of industry type, and the geographical location, the factors for internationalisation of firms are similar (Leaonidou et al., 2007; William, 2008; Hutchison et al., 2007).

Barney (1991) argued that the international stimuli are generally from within. In this sense, the internal factors encourage internationalisations. It is worth noting that previous studies focused on the internationalisation of SMEs in other countries other than Africa (Leaonidou *et al.*, 2007; William, 2008; Hutchison *et al.*, 2007). There is a need for research that focuses on the internationalisation of SMEs from African countries, with focus on factors affecting the internationalisation process.

2.10 Extant Theoretical Framework

Thus far, the literature has focused on the contingency theory, the resource-based view and the stage/process theories amongst others. It is through the lens of these theoretical understandings that the internationalisation process of SMEs has been understood. The literature suggests that the factors that determines the internationalisation decision of SMEs are consistent with external and internal challenges (Coviello and Munro, 2010; McDougall Oviatte, 2009).

Studies also suggest that the most significant aspects that influence and facilitate the process of internationalisation are more aligned to the internal capacity and resources of the firm rather than the exterior factors findings (Johanson and Vahlne, 2007; Bell, 1995; Reuber and Fischer, 1997; Williamson, 2008). Although the macro level of internationalisation policies is

important, they are not the only factors that constitute the ultimate barriers that prevent the internationalisation process of SMEs (McDougall *et al.*, 2009; Williamson, 2008).

Due to socio-economic differences in the context of emerging economies to that of developed economies, there are limitations in the literature to comprehend the internationalisation process of SMEs. Extant studies have focused more on the internationalisation of SMEs from more developed economies, much to the neglect of SMEs from poorer economies. As such, our understanding of the internationalisation process of SMEs must be contextually embedded.

Hence, the need to understand the internationalisation process of SMEs from Cameroon. Unlike previous studies that used a single theoretical context (Coviello and Munro, 2010; McDougall and Oviatte, 2009; Johanson and Vahlne, 2007; Bell, 1995; Reuber and Fischer, 1997; Williamson, 2008), the current study adopts an integrated theoretical approach to give a better understanding to the internationalisation process of SMEs in Cameroon. The proposed integrated theoretical context consists of a combination of the stage theory (Uppsala theory), network theory, born global theory, resource-based view theory, as well as the international entrepreneurship theory.

The rationale for using the integrated theoretical context for the research is guided by the argument that the internationalisation phenomenon of firms is complex phenomena, and benefits from multiple theoretical frameworks. In this sense, using an integrated theoretical approach helps to enrich understanding of the internationalisation process of SMEs. Further, using an integrated theoretical approach helps the study to be enriched by the benefits of theoretical triangulation. According Hutchison *et al.*, (2007) SMEs international activities presents complexity and it is much more vigorous and interactive process that cannot be singly evaluated by a theoretic framework for a full integration of the whole study field. For these reasons, the current study is informed my multiple theoretical perspectives.

(Mtgwe, 2006)) categorized internationalisation concepts in the field into four dimensions, including, firstly, the traditional internationalisation theories. These include the concept of complete advantage, the theory of relative advantage, and Heckscher-Ohlin influence section theory. Secondly, the initial market limitation theories. These include the foreign direct investment theory and internationalisation product life cycle theory. Thirdly, the later market limitation theories, these include. Portfolio theory, internationalisation theory, heterogeneous theory, and resources benefit theory. Finally, internationalisation theory these include the incremental theories, the network theory, and the international entrepreneurship theory. In a similar vein, (Ruzzier & Antoncic, 2007) categorized global business theories into two dimensions.

These include the internationalisation theory; the transaction cost theory; the eclectic paradigm; and the subsequent theory is a proposal of connections among dependent and independent variables for the research. To suggest that the nature of the SMEs affects the manager this is important in understanding the environmental characteristics. Even so, the speed and scope to which internationalisation could be done by an SME is affected not only by environmental characteristics and managerial abilities but also by the nature of the SMEs (Dimitratos & Plakoyiannaki, 2003)

The idea of internationalization has changed in the past three decades. (Johanson & Vahlne, 2011) defined internationalization as a practice in which the companies gradually increase their international participation. They suggest that internationalization is the invention of a series of incremental choices. (Vahlne, et al., 2011) discussed internationalization as a dynamic concept, the process increasing involvement in international operations. They draw our attention to both sides of inward and outward orientation and emphasise that this must be involved in a broader concept of internationalization. Beamish (1990) provides an alternative definition by which

businesses increase awareness of direct and indirect effects of international connections and establish and conduct relations with other nations (Jones *et al.*, 2011). These descriptions designate the idea of internationalization from different dimensions.

Some scholars also suggest that the internationalization is a practice that contains many incremental results and strategies (Jones *et al.*, 2011). Others suggest that internationalisation encompasses many outward and inward produces, service, or resource conveying across domestic boundaries. Further studies suggest that internationalization is influenced by a series of factors that come from the firms and environments (Phillips *et al.*, 2009). The current study adopts the view that internationalization is the process of adapting exchange transaction modality to international markets (Phillips *et al.*, 2009). This definition includes both entry mode strategy and international market selection.

Findings carried by (Terjesen, *et al.*, 2013) on the connectivity of firm characteristics and intent to internationalise indicated an optimistic relationship between the variables. An observation of assertiveness and perception has a direct influence on enterprises intentions to expand business operations internationally (Terjesen, *et al.*, 2013) Related research also draws an assertion of time that a business has been in operation in correlation with the experience from the manger. This has a direct effect on capacity to handle internationalisation (Hutchinson, *et al.*, 2005)

Conversely (Chen, 2006) denote that internationalisation of a firm is not limited to its characteristics of management but impacted by the environmental characteristics. These characteristics could be knowledge of the foreign market, technological strength, and knowledge on competitiveness on rivalry firms (Calof, *et al.*, 1995)Although these characteristics are the intriguing variables for firms internationalising, they are also barriers for the process. This view is consistent with that of the (OECD, 2016), and the (European

Commission, 2013) when they point out that SMEs undergo ineffective internationalisation process due to weakness and loopholes in their strategies.

2.11 Chapter Summary

This chapter critically reviews the literature on internationalisation process. The literature reveals the studies have focused more on the international behaviour of SMEs and neglected the non-international SMEs behaviour. The literature has also brought some understanding on the factors or barriers that influence international activities of a firm. However, these insights are drawn from studies that have been conducted in other countries other than African countries.

Drawing from a range of theoretical frameworks, the current study develops an integrated conceptual framework that is informed by variables from five key theories. The contextual literature reveals that Cameroon's export performance is very low. Within the contextual literature, there is silence of the role played by SMEs within the export performance. Further, export activities of SMEs are relegated to a category of secondary theoretical interest. The focus of SME manufacturing has been on the domestic market, rather than the international market. Yet, the same SMEs have potential to manufacture products that can meet international standards. Therefore, there is a greater to understand and facet the internationalization growth process of Manufacturing SMEs in Cameroon. The next chapter discusses the research methodology.

CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

The study combines both qualitative and quantitative methodology, and thus adopts a mixed methods approach. This was adopted to help answer the research questions more comprehensively. The chapter starts by discussing the research paradigm, and in the process, revealing the researcher's paradigmatic orientation and stance. The strategies and research design are also discussed. In a similar vein, data collection methods are presented and justified. This is followed by a discussion of the data analysis plan and addresses issue of validity and reliability. The ethical issues surrounding the study are also discussed.

3.1 Purpose of Research

Despite increased activities across borders by SMEs, very little focus is place on SMEs in developing economies, much to the neglect of SMEs in developing economies. Further, theories of internationalisation have continued to focus on the context of SMEs in developed economies, thereby ignoring the contextual issues of those SMEs in developing countries such as Cameroon. The failure of previous studies to capture the contextual understandings of internationalisation of SMEs in developing economies has proven to be a theoretical weakness in the field.

The contextual literature reveals that Cameroon's international performance is very low. Within the contextual literature, there is silence of the role played by SMEs in foreign investment. Further, foreign activities of SMEs are relegated to a category of secondary theoretical interest. The focus of SME manufacturing has been on the domestic market, rather than the international market. Yet, the same SMEs have potential to manufacture products that can meet international standards. Therefore, there is great degree of facet on the internationalization growth process of Manufacturing SMEs in Cameroon

The purpose of the study aims to determine the process of internationalization and the challenges faced by small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) within the context of Cameroon. In this regard, the study attempts to answer the overarching questions: if Cameroon manufacturing SMEs adopt similar internationalization paths as other emerging economies using specific variables and frameworks significant to the Cameroon market? The Uppsala model amongst others is essential in market entry strategy. While developing some guidelines that can help SMEs to internationalise their products. The intention is to provide insight into the internationalisation process of SMEs from Cameroon.

Deriving from Zahra 2006 and Anderson 2009 studies on SME's entering new markets, the research questions prompting this research focused on manufacturing SME's in Cameroon are the following:

1. What does the literature say about the internationalisation process of SMEs, and what are the gaps in knowledge?
2. What are manager's perceptions on market entry mode?
3. What are the internal and external factors that affect the internationalisation of SMEs?
4. What guidelines can be developed to help SMEs in Cameroon to overcome international Barriers?

An organization's knowledge of its existing market is going to directly impact on how the organization studies and understands the opportunities and challenges in its market and may influence their decision on entering a new market whether domestic or foreign. When SMEs consider entering a market, existing activities within the market may affect decisions regarding committing into the market quickly or gradually (Moen, 2002)

Other organizations can approach internationalization by strategically exploiting their assets that provides them with an advantage. Capitalizing on the location attractions that the host country provides when compared to other countries and leveraging the government policies promoting

the establishment of international businesses, and also having access to important institutional infrastructure that when combined will ensure a smooth internalization. Overall, it is likely that the same SME would have the same outcome as they enter different foreign markets, as the components in the proposed model are interrelated. As such, it is very important when carrying out this research to be able to develop a theory on the mode of entry for SME's as they internationalize.

Although, in principle the various internationalization frameworks can complement one another, rather than competing it would provide better synergy if the following three frameworks are integrated; Uppsala internationalization model, international product life cycle network theory with the Eclectic paradigm, international entrepreneurship, born global, Contingency theory and resource-based view theory

3.2 Research philosophy

Social science identifies two major research approaches, that is, quantitative and qualitative. (McAuley, 2010) suggest that when a study is based on probabilities, and is not certain of the truth, it is quantitative, objective, and measurable. On the other hand, qualitative research is subjective, and based on social contexts. Scholars suggest that reality can be understood on objective or subjective terms (Goshe, et al., 2012).

The paradigm of a research is very important, and it establishes the beliefs and ideologies of the study and the person carrying out the study on how the universe is perceived. (Sterne, et al., 2016) suggest that an individual's view is contextualised based on their understanding. Research paradigms are regarded as a diverse way relating to aspects of the universe and beyond. (Sterne, et al., 2016) proposed four research paradigms.

The study is informed by both positivist and interpretivist paradigms. It must be pointed out that the interpretivist or constructivist paradigm acknowledges that reality is an exploring process that is relative and subjective, and that reality comprises of human thought as products are liable to change (Zaza et al., 2012). The reason for using the constructivist research paradigm is to provide an in-depth understanding of the internationalisation process of SMEs in Cameroon. The researcher also draws insights from the positivist paradigm to help obtain responses from a larger sample size, and measure variables that have been identified from the literature.

3.3 Research Problem

Understanding the internationalisation process, and how enterprises tackle the challenges of export barriers, international market growth, are of concern. Given the growing global competition, and rising unemployment in Cameroon, it is imperative that a framework be developed to help manufacturing SMEs internationalise their activities, with the intention of achieving growth, and creating employment. Whilst the available research has focused more on a large-scale patterning of internationalisation barriers in a fragmented manner, the current study uses a multi-disciplinary integrative framework for internationalisation to address the research problem.

3.4 Research Design and Methods

The study is focused on the most crucial themes that surround the internationalization behaviour and the non-international behaviour of SMEs. Therefore, the approach is in four phases. In phase one, the focus was on providing a rationale of the study area. The research problem is then positioned within the literature. Finally, the empirical research method and analysis are outlined. The second phase focused on using secondary data sets from OECD, APEC, World Bank and other credible sources. This involved analysing the secondary data

sets in line the research questions. The third phase focused on analysing the qualitative data set. Interview transcripts are analysed using thematic analysis. The fourth phase involved bringing all the different parts of the research together and writing up the thesis.

The alignment of data sources to the research questions is as illustrated in table 3.1.

Table 3. 1: Alignment of research questions

Research Question	Data Source	Approach
What does the literature say about the internationalization process of SMEs, and what are the gaps in knowledge?	Academic journals, books etc.	
What are the perceptions of managers on internationalization, and how do these perceptions impact on the internationalization process of SMEs in Cameroon?	Survey	Deductive
What are the internal and external factors that affect the internationalization of SMEs?	Survey Interviews	Deductive Inductive
What guidelines can be developed to help SMEs in Cameroon to overcome the challenges identified, and internationalize their activities?	Survey Interviews	Adductive

To answer each of the research questions, insights were obtained from different data sources.

Research design is inclusive of all aspects that are necessary and involved in conducting the research. This includes the tool or framework used in collecting and analysing data (Johnson & Christensen., 2004). In fact, the research design signifies “an overall understanding of selected method and the rationale for the choice” (Taket, 2010)). The literature suggests that research methods are precise models for carrying out findings on a field directly or indirectly

and these include interviews, observation, surveys, and evaluation of participants' responses (Fugard and Potts, 2015).

Scholars also propose five research strategies which are, case studies, experiments, questionnaires, and archival analysis (Kothari, 2004; Strauss & Corbin, 1994). Considering this, and the nature of the research questions, the current study adopts a mixed method approach. The reason for the choice of the mixed method is because it provides a guide of direction for data collection and analysis through the quantitative and qualitative approaches. In this study, the qualitative approach uses in depth interviews, whilst the quantitative approach uses the survey method. A better understanding of the adopted research design is explained in the subsequent paragraphs.

3.4.1 Qualitative Research Approach

Previous studies suggest that the qualitative approach gives a vigorous, long-term choice making process for foreign market entry mode such as franchising, exportation and importation to be thoroughly verified according to respective firms' settings (Zaza et al., 2012; Stern *et al.*, 2016). The use of the qualitative method of research in this study helps to gain a deeper understanding of contextual issues affecting the internationalization of SMEs in Cameroon. The participating firms in this category were purposefully selected.

Emails were sent to 25 companies inviting them to participate in the qualitative part of the study. Of these, 20 companies accepted. However, 16 were used because the information provided by the other was similar and repetitive. Data collection using this method was stopped when saturation was reached. Interviews were tape recorded. Each interview lasted for between 45 and 90 minutes. Observational notes were also jotted down as freshly as possible.

3.4.2 Quantitative Approach

The quantitative approach was also utilised. Previous studies suggest that the quantitative approach is essential to obtain several opinions that can be generalizable to the entire

population (Hong, 2018). To attain a high response rate the online platform was also used to collect data. Other questionnaires were sent using the postal system. This helped to ensure a wider reach and collect data from the four major regions in Cameroon. The data was collected over 2 months, during spring of 2018. Respondents were selected from the list of SMEs held by the Chamber of commerce in Cameroon. Questionnaires were sent to 200 decision makers in different SMEs. Respondents were first contacted by email to invite them to take part in the survey. These emails were personalised to help build rapport and trust. A cluster sampling technique was used to ensure sufficient coverage. Within this, international focused SMEs were selected using judgemental and convenient sampling techniques. The survey population was defined as SMEs involved in internationalisation process and meets the criteria according the European definition (European, 2013).

Of the 200 questionnaires distributed, 148 were returned. Of these, only 112 were usable. Though the response rate was 74%, the usable questionnaires constituted 56% of the distributed questionnaires. Given that Cameroon face many challenges in terms of travel, and internet accessibility, this rate is reasonable. Had questionnaires been administered in a personal interviewing format, more responses would have been obtained. However, the researcher could not be on the ground to collect data because of the risks posed by the warring political parties in Cameroon.

The questionnaire measured variables that were informed by the literature. Consistent with previous studies, a 5-point Likert-scale was used to measure the variables of interest to this study. The questionnaire used was bilingual to help accommodate both the French and English-speaking areas of Cameroon. There was no loss of meaning or information as the researcher in fluent in both English and French

A pilot study was conducted to test the survey instruments. This comprised of 15 respondents, 8 English speaking, and 7 French speaking. This helped to make minor modifications to the wording of the survey instruments. The pilot study also helped to confirm the data analysis plan. However, results from the pilot study have not been used in this study because of the modifications that were made to the survey instruments.

3.5 Data collection

The literature suggests that data collection helps to ensure that the research is reliable and valid (Ramamurti, 2012; Welch et al., 2009). Scholars also suggest that qualitative and quantitative data sets can be combined in a single study (Denscombe, 2014). In fact, different means of collecting data helps to achieve the benefits of triangulation (Ramamurti, 2012; Welch & Welch, 2009). Proponents for mixed research methods suggest that international business studies show more credibility and reliability when mixed methods are used (Brown, et al., 2014) Data was collected using various means available.

- Journal articles; documents and materials relating to SME internationalization. This also included government reports, national and international media, reports from the World Bank (WB), International Chamber of Commerce (ICC), and the e World Economic Forum (WEF, 2016). Other in-country chamber of commerce and internationalisation associations (Cameroon chamber of commerce, industry, mines and crafts, and international trade publications.
- In person survey Likert scale questionnaire responses (Appendix)
- Materials and publications from public and private institutions being studied with this research, and SME's official opinions
- Qualitative interviews with SME owners or managers, as well as field notes that I wrote down during and after the interviews.

3.5.1 Research survey

This research survey is subject to certain limitations below.

- It assesses SME's only from four regions in Cameroon.
- The objective is not to highlight person views of respondents of SME's as regards to existing political issues that affect internationalisation strategies, experience and day to day activities. Instead the study is aimed at analysing and understanding the data gathered from the sample surveyed with the sole objective of understanding the internationalization process, its catalyst and challenges.
- Although the internationalization of SME's considers various geo-political and socio-economic aspects, considering target countries economic, political and trading policies that may affect the internationalisation strategy at the micro and macro-economic level, the data collected was only for a selected population surveyed.

The survey method was used because it is an economical way to conduct an effective measurement by reaching a wider population. Further, the survey was also selected to help make the results generalizable to a wider population. Scholars also suggest that the survey method helps to obtain quicker responses (Descombe, 2017). The survey made use of self-administered questions. Each questionnaire took about 15 to 20 minutes to complete.

Conferring with (Yin, 2003) the survey is appropriate for respondents to ensure consistent measurement. Further, the questions provided response choices. This helped the respondents to complete the questionnaire within 20 minutes. However, (Bryman & Bell, 2014) suggest that closed ended question form a little bias, as not all the choices provided by the questionnaire include a wider response. The questions are pre-determined, meaning that responses are confirmed to the pre-determined categories or answer choices.

Quantitative data was analysed using descriptive and associative analysis. Here, frequency checks were conducted to determine any missing values, and identify usable questionnaires. Patterns of data were also determined. Data obtain in this category was presented using tables, pie charts, and bar graphs. After screening the data using descriptive analysis, correlation analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between variables. The statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS), was used to help with the data analysis. Drawing from the correlation analysis, hypothesis was tested, and an outcome of each test determined (Yin, 2003).

3.5.2 Interview Process and Transcript Analysis

Given the limitations of the survey method, the researcher also used semi-structured interviews to help obtain information to answer the research questions. These interviews were completed in about 30 to 45 minutes. The literature suggests that the interview method gives a valuable advantage which helps to probe respondents' thought processes and evaluate the oral information with the use of nonverbal cues at same time (Bains, 1956; Bartlett & Ghoshal, 1987; Fayolle & Liñán, 2014).

Qualitative data analysis process included studying the transcripts repeatedly to obtain an understanding of the general themes (critical Incident). These were triangulated with the notes derived from the interview. This procedure helped the researcher to obtain deeper insights. According to (Andersson & Florén, 2008), coding the transcript through open coding is vital to the research. Meanwhile (Slotte-Kock & Coviello, 2010) proposed a technique which categorized international stimulating factors that should be adapted. Hence, international dimension stimuli factors guide the classification of the critical incident which enacts the internationalisation initiation that was identified during the interview (Simon, 2009).

Once the process of the interview had taken place, it was of importance for the researcher to build rapport and trust with the participants. Significantly, the process was guided with sequential questions, asking the respondent to clarify their points without interrupting the process too much, enabling that there was a great communication stream between both parties. As such, for the understanding of the major factors and motivation of firm's internationalization process there the researcher used a lot of probing techniques to obtain deeper insights.

Prior to conducting the interviews, the researcher was aware of the associated limitations. For instance, scholars argue that qualitative data is subjective (Sterne, et al., 2016; Yin, 2003; Simon, 2009). Others suggest that interviews depend on the interviewer skills (Creswell, et al., 2011). Failure to create a relationship with the participant may affect the result of the interview (Creswell, et al., 2011). Inconsistency has been an issue that limits the interview process. Despite the shortfalls of interviews, the researcher was able to obtain detailed information. These shortfalls were also overcome by the advantages of the survey method used for the quantitative part of the study.

3.6 Sampling Method

For the qualitative part of the study, a convenience and purposeful sampling approach was adopted. The intention was to purposefully reach at those respondents that were more knowledgeable about the internationalization of SMEs from Cameroon. For the quantitative part of the study, a stratified sampling approach was adopted. Respondents were drawn from the four main regions of Cameroon (Littoral, South West, North West, and Central Region). Within this, participating firms were conveniently selected. The intention was to reach at those respondents who volunteered to share their views, and who could respond within a given time limit.

3.6.1 Sample size

Data was collected from across Cameroon's four major regions (Littoral, South West, North West, and Central Region). For the SMEs that were conveniently selected to answer the questionnaires. This resulted in a sample of 200 manufacturing SMEs across the selected regions. Personalized emails were sent to prospective participants inviting them to take part in the survey. Based on the responds from the managers, 150 questionnaires were returned. However, only 112 were fully completed, and usable.

Table 3. 2: Sample size

Data source	Quantity
Survey	112
Semi-structured interviews	16

Emails were sent to 25 companies inviting them to participate in the qualitative part of the study. Of these, 20 companies accepted. However, 16 were used because the information provided by the other was similar and repetitive. Data collection using this method was stopped when saturation was reached. Interviews were tape recorded. Each interview lasted for between 45 and 90 minutes.

3.7 Research Validity and Reliability

The criteria surrounding a good research validity and reliability are that of thoroughness, and credibility. The criterion for credibility includes, (1) internal, (2) external, (3) objective, and (4) reliable. (Strauss, 1987)

3.7.1 Data Validity

To ensure data was accurately collected and is in line with the view of the interviewees and not that of the researchers. An internal and external validity system was applied interview

transcripts were exactly as respondents, being aware of the patterns of inter-connection been different from what I had expected. Also, four possible types of safeguards were implemented to ensure validity (Strauss & Corbin, 1994)

3.7.1.1 Internal Validity

The literature suggests that internal validity seeks to justify the claims of the research evidence (Goshe, et al., 2012; Sterne, et al., 2016). Construct validity was used to measure the actual concepts used in the study. (Zaza, et al., 2000), suggest that construct validity can be done through convergent validity, face validity, and divergent validity.

3.7.1.2 External Validity

One of the key views of a positivist research study is based on if the research findings can be generalised. Therefore, external validity is preliminary based on whether the research results can be accepted and compared with units of analysis in comparable settings. A sample of 112 respondents was used to help make the results more generalisable to the target population.

3.7.1.3 Objectivity

The normal assumption of a good research is the positive objective of systematic pursuit of knowledge by researchers. Consequently, the research philosophy provides an external objective of information which emphasises that researchers are detached and have a neutral stance on the investigated phenomenon (hence, research value). The value of the research becomes valid and is not threatened. The results are not biased. This was achieved by the quantitative part of the study.

3.7.2 Reliability

Reliability refers to whether the measured variables can remain consistent over time. A reliable research is concerned with the extent to which the findings can be replicated and recreated in different settings (Creswell *et al.*, 2013). A 5-point Likert scale was used with an inventory

of 44 items to measure the different research constructs. When all the 44-item inventories are tested at the same time, the case processing summary indicates that all the 112 respondents provided a response to the 44 items.

The estimated Cronbach's alpha statistic for the 44-item inventory was .889. This means that 88.9% of the variability in the composite score of the 44 would be considered as true score variance or internally consistent reliable variance. When Cronbach alpha was calculated under the pretence that the items all have the same variance, a coefficient of .896 is obtained. This suggests that the scale is reliable (Anderson, 2002; Axinn & Matthyssens, 2002). The reliability statistics are illustrated in more detail in chapter 5.

3.8 Ethical considerations

The study made use of data collected from different academic journals. These were already available in the public domain, and some had to be accessed using passwords obtained from the university library. Primary data was collected using the interview and survey methods. Before embarking on any primary data collection, prepared all the ethical clearance materials such as participant information sheet, consent forms, risk assessment, research instruments, and a research protocol. These were presented to the university's ethical committee for consideration and approval. Ethical clearance was granted in writing.

In undertaking the research, the researcher was guided by the ethical guidelines regarding: (1) informed consent (the degree to which prospective participants are informed in advance); (2) privacy and confidentiality; (3) language (the degree to which the preferred language is used for the interview sessions); (4) deception (ensuring that the respondent by no means are coerced to share information); and lastly (5) accuracy (the extent to which data collected are analyse accurately based on the information provided).

1) Informed consent

A participant information sheet was prepared and distributed together with the letter of invitation. This gave respondents more time to read and become aware of the study. The intention was to make them aware and give them sufficient information before they decide to take part in the study. Consent was obtained in writing. In other words, participants signed a consent form before taking part in the study.

2) Privacy and confidentiality

Participants were also informed that their responses would be private. Their identities would not be disclosed to anyone. In this sense, respondents were assured of privacy and confidentiality. Respondents were assured of anonymity in the reporting of the results. They were also advised that participation was voluntary, and that they could withdraw their consent at any time.

3) Language

Cameroon has two official languages, that is English and French. However, there are also other local ethnic dialects. The researcher's first language is English, and the study was written in English. However, the research instruments were in both French and English to ensure inclusion of participants from different regions of Cameroon. Those responses obtained in French were then translated by the researcher into English. This approach of using both English and French helped to get respondents from different regions of the country.

4) Deception

Still in line with privacy policy, the study ensured the firms lists of names, the name of the owners, the participant for the questionnaire, the interview participants, their contacts, positions and their age/gender will be treated with confidentiality. Their identities remained concealed in the reporting of the results. Pseudonyms have been used instead.

5) Accuracy

Data was reported accurately. The researcher was bound by ethical guidelines to report the information accurately, and by no means intended to fabricate or omits information. Statistical information was collected from the different respondents, and then reported using statistical techniques. Information was also presented used charts. Qualitative data was also reported accurately and interpreted using established techniques. Emergent themes were illustrated using extracts that were obtain from the respondents. In this sense, there was accuracy in the reporting of the results.

3.9 Chapter Summary

This chapter has presented the research methodology. A mixed method was adopted to help answer the research questions. Philosophically, both positivist and interpretivist approaches were utilized. Primary data was both qualitative and quantitative. The intention was to triangulate the data sets and ensure that the research questions are answered. The researcher obtained ethical clearance from the university. In conducting the research, the researcher was guided by the ethical principles. The next chapter presents the results of the study.

CHAPTER FOUR: RESULTS

4.0 Introduction

The chapter presents the findings of the study. The results are analysed sequentially. Firstly, reliability statistics are presented, and then followed by a detailed analysis of the results from the survey. Descriptive statistics and associative statistics are used to analyse the data. Results are presented using tables, charts, and graphs. Statistical tests for non-parametric

statistics are used to test the relationship between variables of interest. The last part of the

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	Number of Items
.889	.896	44

results
presents the
qualitative

results. Drawing from both the quantitative and qualitative data sets, a conclusion is drawn.

4.1 Reliability Test

A reliability test was conducted to check the internal consistency of the measuring instrument. To achieve this, the Cronbach alpha test was used. In the absence of reliability, it is impossible to have any validity associated with the scores of the scales. In this sense, Cronbach alpha is helping to determine whether it is justifiable to interpret scores that have been aggregated in this study. A 5-point Likert scale was used with an inventory of 44 items to measure the different research constructs. When all the 44-item inventories are tested at the same time, the case processing summary indicates that all the 112 respondents provided a response to the 44 items.

The estimated Cronbach's alpha statistic for the 44-item inventory is .889. This means that 88.9% of the variability in the composite score of the 44 would be considered as true score variance or internally consistent reliable variance. When Cronbach alpha is calculated under the pretence that the items all have the same variance, a coefficient of .896 is obtained, as illustrated in table 4.1. This suggests that the scale is reliable.

Table 4. 1: Overall reliability statistics

The item total statistics table informs us about the reliability of the scale used if an item is deleted. This has been used by the researcher to drop from further analysis any items that render the scale unreliable. This means that only items that help the scale to be more reliable were retained. As illustrated by table 4.2 (see appendix 3), the Cronbach's alpha statistic is above .8 for all the variables, and there is no need to delete any of the items as the reliability coefficients change very little if any of the items is deleted.

Reliability Test for each of the sub-scales

Within the 44-item inventory of items, there are 8 sub-scales each measuring a different research construct. Reliability analysis was then conducted for each of these sub-scales, and their associated items. The results are as illustrated by table 4

Table 4. 2: Research construct's reliability

Research Construct	Reliability Statistics			
	Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	Number of Items used	Number of items dropped
Impact of international knowledge, experience, and information on the internationalisation process	.551	.562	5	0
Human resource barriers affecting the internationalisation process	.446	.446	2	1
Financial barriers	.891	.891	2	1
Product barriers	.467	.470	5	0
Government Bureaucratic Barriers	.446	.446	2	2
Exogenous Barriers	.667	.679	8	0
Factors and criteria that are valuable for domestic market	.381	.381	2	2
General factors of influence	.575	.574	9	0

Research Construct 1: Impact of international knowledge, experience, and information on the internationalisation process.

Table 4. 3: Research construct 1 reliability

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.551	.562	5

There were five items used to measure this construct, and the reliability coefficient obtained was .551. This means that 55.1 % of the variability in the composite score of the 5 items would be considered as true score variance or internally consistent reliable variance (see table 4.5 in appendix 3).

Table 4.5 illustrates the item statistics (see appendix 3). Here, they all have mean scores within close range because they items were measured using a 5-point Likert scale. As such, the mean scores for each item would be expected to be within the range of the 5-point Likert scale. The standard deviations are roughly the same, and that is why the two estimates for reliability are corresponding.

The item total statistics table informs us about the reliability of the scale used if an item it deleted (see table 4.6 in appendix 3). For instance, if the item “international market research” is deleted, the Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient would reduce to .454. As illustrated by table 4.8, the Cronbach’s alpha statistic is .551 if all the items for this construct are considered together. Therefore, there is no need to delete any of the items as the reliability coefficients change very little if any of the items is deleted.

Research Construct 2: Human resource barriers affecting the internationalisation process

Table 4. 4: Research construct 2 reliability

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.343	.342	4

There were four items used to measure this construct, and the reliability coefficient obtained was .343. This means that 34.3 % of the variability in the composite score of the 4 items would be considered as true score variance or internally consistent reliable variance. This score is very low. After deleting two items, as indicated by the total item statistics, an improved reliability coefficient of .446 was obtained.

Table 4. 5: Reliability when items deleted

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.446	.446	2

Table 4. 6: Item statistics

Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Shortage of trained personnel	1.7500	1.00000	112
Low managerial exposure	1.7054	1.02789	112
Inexperienced on international activities	1.9464	1.01199	112
Lack of structure plan and execution	1.6964	1.02086	112

The inter-item correlation matrix illustrated in table 4.10 (see appendix 3), helps to understand the scale more deeply. It can be observed that the correlations are not that high. For instance, the inter-item correlation between lack of structure plan and execution, and inexperienced on international activities is negative (-.042). Theoretically, all these items should be interrelated

with each other positively because they are all supposedly measuring the same thing. This pattern of correlation suggests the items used are not totally measuring the same phenomena. Because of the low inter-item correlations, a Cronbach alpha of .343 was initially obtained. As such, other items had to be dropped to help obtain an optimal Cronbach alpha statistic of .446 (see table 4.11 in appendix 3).

Considering the low reliability coefficient, items “inexperienced on international activities” and item “lack of structure plan and execution” were deleted. This helped to improve the reliability of the scale.

Table 4. 7: Item total statistics

Item-Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Shortage of trained personnel	5.3482	3.761	.203	.083	.254
Low managerial exposure	5.3929	3.178	.359	.136	.053
Inexperienced on international activities	5.1518	4.220	.073	.030	.399
Lack of structure plan and execution	5.4018	4.062	.108	.041	.362

Table 4. 8: Item total statistics if item deleted

Item-Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Shortage of trained personnel	3.4018	2.495	.230	.083	.318
Low managerial exposure	3.4464	2.177	.325	.111	.124
Lack of structure plan and execution	3.4554	2.647	.160	.036	.446

Though items “*inexperienced on international activities*” and item “*lack of structure plan and execution*” were deleted, the reliability coefficient remained low, at .446. This suggests that this construct must be viewed within the context of other constructs. When this is done, and improved reliability coefficient of .889 is obtained.

Table 4. 9: Reliability statistics

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.446	.446	2

Research construct 3: Financial barriers

Table 4. 10: Research construct 3 - reliability statistics

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.618	.638	3

There were three items used to measure this construct, and the reliability coefficient obtained was .618. This means that 61.8 % of the variability in the composite score of the 3 items would be considered as true score variance or internally consistent reliable variance. This score is acceptable. After deleting two items, as indicated by the total item statistics, an improved reliability coefficient of .618 was obtained. However, when some items are deleted, it was found that the reliability coefficient increases to .891, as illustrated in table 4.16 below.

Table 4. 11: Reliability statistics

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.891	.891	2

The item total statistics of the retained items are illustrated in table 4.17.

Table 4. 12: Item statistics

Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Shortage of funds for international operations	1.7946	.96924	112
Lack of government aid	1.8125	.99123	112

Table 4. 13: Inter-item correlation matrix

Inter-Item Correlation Matrix		
	Shortage of funds for international operations	Lack of government aid
Shortage of funds for international operations	1.000	.804
Lack of government aid	.804	1.000

The inter-item correlation matrix of the two items retained is as illustrated in table 4.18.

Table 4. 14: Item total statistics

Item-Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Shortage of funds for international operations	1.8125	.983	.804	.646	.
Lack of government aid	1.7946	.939	.804	.646	.

Table 4.19 shows the optimal level, and the two items were retained. The scale statistics are as illustrated in table 4.20.

Table 4. 15: Scale statistics

Scale Statistics			
Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
3.6071	3.466	1.86169	2

Research construct 4: Product barriers

There were five items used to measure this construct, and the reliability coefficient obtained was .467. This means that 46.7 % of the variability in the composite score of the 5 items would be considered as true score variance or internally consistent reliable variance. This score is acceptable.

Table 4. 16: Product barriers-reliability statistics

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.467	.470	5

The item total statistics shows a mean within the limits of the five-point scale across all the five items, and the associated standard deviations, as illustrated in table 4.22.

Table 4. 17: Item statistics

Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Problem on product quality	1.7768	1.11266	112
Packaging standards	1.8125	.99123	112
Global product standards	1.7500	1.00000	112
Low stock production	1.7054	1.02789	112
Product branding problem	1.9464	1.01199	112

The inter-item correlation matrix is illustrated below, and there are lower scores between some of the variables, as well as negative scores in some parts. This in part explains a low reliability coefficient obtained.

Table 4. 18: Inter-Item correlation matrix

Inter-Item Correlation Matrix					
	Problem on product quality	Packaging standards	Global product standards	Low stock production	Product branding problem
Problem on product quality	1.000	.190	.055	.210	-.003
Packaging standards	.190	1.000	.189	.131	.259
Global product standards	.055	.189	1.000	.287	.031
Low stock production	.210	.131	.287	1.000	.158
Product branding problem	-.003	.259	.031	.158	1.000

The inter-item correlation matrix illustrated in table, helps to understand the scale more deeply. It can be observed that the correlations are not that high. For instance, the inter-item correlation between some items is negative, and some correlation coefficients are very low. Theoretically, all these items should be interrelated with each other positively because they are all supposedly measuring the same thing. This pattern of correlation suggests the items used are not totally measuring the same phenomena. Because of the low inter-item correlations, a Cronbach alpha of .467 was initially obtained.

Table 4. 19: Item Total statistics

Item-Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Problem on product quality	7.2143	6.206	.183	.079	.460
Packaging standards	7.1786	5.896	.328	.133	.357
Global product standards	7.2411	6.311	.229	.110	.425
Low stock production	7.2857	5.737	.338	.143	.347
Product branding problem	7.0446	6.530	.175	.092	.460

The item total statistics indicates that if any of the items are deleted, there would be not much change in the correlation co-efficient. As such, all the 5 items were retained. However, it is important to note that when these 5 items are considered in combination with other items on other constructs, the correlation coefficient is .889. Therefore, it is important to understand this construct within the context of other constructs, and not in isolation.

Research construct 5: Government Bureaucratic Barriers

There were four items used to measure this construct, and the reliability coefficient obtained was .343. This means that 34.3 % of the variability in the composite score of the 4 items would be considered as true score variance or internally consistent reliable variance. This score is too low and not acceptable.

Table 4. 20: Bureaucratic barriers - reliability statistics

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.343	.342	4

Some items had to be deleted with the intention of retaining those items that help to produce a high correlation coefficient. As such, two items were deleted, and the result is as illustrated in table 4.26. There were two items retained produced a reliability coefficient of .446. This means that 44.6 % of the variability in the composite score of the two items would be considered as true score variance or internally consistent reliable variance. This score is too low and not acceptable. However, it is important to note that when these 2 items are considered in combination with other items on other constructs, the correlation coefficient is .889. Therefore, it is important to understand this construct within the context of other constructs, and not in isolation.

Table 4. 21: Reliability statistics

Table 4.26: Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.446	.446	2

The selection of items to delete was informed by the item total statistics as illustrated in table.

The items to be dropped were selected using the item total statistics as illustrated in table 4.27.

Table 4. 22:Item total statistics

Item-Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
International promotion program	5.4018	4.062	.108	.041	.362
Support to overcome international barriers	5.3482	3.761	.203	.083	.254
Inadequate governmental sponsorship	5.3929	3.178	.359	.136	.053
Poor diplomatic support	5.1518	4.220	.073	.030	.399

The items retained are as illustrated in table and the associated mean and standard deviations are also indicated. This is within the range of the 5-point Likert scale that was used to measure the items in this construct.

Table 4. 23: Item statistics

Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Support to overcome international barriers	1.7500	1.00000	112
Inadequate governmental sponsorship	1.7054	1.02789	112

The inter-item correlation matrix is illustrated in table 4.29. This shows a low correlation coefficient between the items retained. Therefore, it is not surprising that a low reliability coefficient was obtained.

Table 4. 24: Inter-Item correlation matrix

Inter-Item Correlation Matrix		
	Support to overcome international barriers	Inadequate governmental sponsorship
Support to overcome international barriers	1.000	.287
Inadequate governmental sponsorship	.287	1.000

Research construct 6: Exogenous Barriers

There were eight items used to measure this construct, and the reliability coefficient obtained was .667. This means that 66.7 % of the variability in the composite score of the eight items would be considered as true score variance or internally consistent reliable variance. This score is acceptable.

Table 4. 25: Exogenous barriers-reliability statistics

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.677	.679	8

The item statistics are as illustrated in table. The mean and standard deviation fall within the range of the 5-point Likert scale that was used.

Table 4. 26: Item statistics

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
International trade policy	1.6964	1.02086	112
Trade regulations	1.7946	.96924	112
High domestic values	1.7500	1.00000	112
Exchange rate fluctuation	1.7054	1.02789	112
Inflation rate	1.9464	1.01199	112
International trade taxes	1.6964	1.02086	112
High interest rate	1.7946	.96924	112
Political instability	1.7679	1.00433	112

Though there was an opportunity to delete some items to help attain a higher reliability coefficient, this option was not used because the changes would have been very minimal, as illustrated in table. As such, all the eight items were retained.

Table 4. 27: Item total statistics

Item-Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
International trade policy	12.4554	15.800	.361	.	.649
Trade regulations	12.3571	15.457	.443	.	.630
High domestic values	12.4018	15.288	.445	.	.628
Exchange rate fluctuation	12.4464	16.141	.311	.	.661
Inflation rate	12.2054	17.462	.152	.	.697
International trade taxes	12.4554	15.800	.361	.	.649
High interest rate	12.3571	15.457	.443	.	.630
Political instability	12.3839	15.266	.445	.	.628

The inter-item correlation matrix is as illustrated in table 4.33. Were it not for some of the negative and low correlation coefficients, the reliability coefficient would have been much higher than .667. The inter-item correlation matrix is illustrated in table 4.33 (see appendix 3).

Research construct 7: Factors and criteria that is valuable for domestic market

There were four items used to measure this construct, and the reliability coefficient obtained was .217. This means that 21.7 % of the variability in the composite score of the four items would be considered as true score variance or internally consistent reliable variance. This score is not acceptable. As such, some items had to be deleted to improve the scores.

Table 4. 28: Reliability statistics

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.217	.230	4

Two items were deleted, and the reliability coefficient obtained is as illustrated in table 4.34. This means that 38.1% of the variability in the composite score of the remaining two items would be considered as true score variance or internally consistent reliable variance. This score is still acceptable.

Table 4. 29: Reliability statistics when items deleted

Table 5.44: Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.381	.381	2

Items that were selected for deletion were determined using the item total statistics, as illustrated in table 4.35.

Table 4. 30: Item total statistics

Item-Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Change in political system	9.3571	3.655	.149	.024	.105
Economic climate change	7.7589	4.527	.103	.062	.177
Competitive rivalries	9.2857	4.098	.042	.022	.272
Change in government regulations	7.7768	4.301	.144	.059	.128

The item statistics of the two items retained are as illustrated in table 4.37.

Table 4. 31: Item statistics

Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Economic climate change	3.6339	.94912	112
Change in government regulations	3.6161	.97948	112

The inter-item correlation matrix shows a very low correlation. This explains why the reliability coefficient is low (.381). Though this is low, it is important to note that when these 2 items are considered in combination with other items on other constructs, the correlation coefficient is .889. Therefore, it is important to understand this construct within the context of other constructs, and not in isolation.

Table 4. 32: Inter-item correlation matrix

Inter-Item Correlation Matrix		
	Economic climate change	Change in government regulations
Economic climate change	1.000	.235
Change in government regulations	.235	1.000

Research construct 8: General factors of influence

There were nine items used to measure this construct, and the reliability coefficient obtained was .575. This means that 57.5 % of the variability in the composite score of the nine items would be considered as true score variance or internally consistent reliable variance. This score is acceptable.

Table 4. 33: Reliability statistics

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.575	.574	9

The item statistics are as illustrated in table 4.49. The mean and standard deviation fall within the range of the 5-point Likert scale that was used

Table 4. 34: Item statistics

Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Political legal factors	1.7946	.96924	112
Cultural factors	1.7679	1.00433	112
Firm's level of technology	2.0357	1.22238	112
Distribution structure	3.6339	.94912	112
Age of firm	3.6161	.97948	112
Cultural similarities	1.7500	1.13503	112
Market similarities	1.7679	1.02212	112
International relationship/network	1.7054	1.01908	112
Entrepreneurial/managerial expertise	2.0714	1.36041	112

Though there was an opportunity to delete some items to help attain a higher reliability coefficient, this option was not used because the changes would have been very minimal, as illustrated in table 4.41 (see appendix 3). As such, all the eight items were retained. However, it must be noted that the reliability coefficient would have been much higher than .575 were it not for some items with negative correlation coefficient, and very low correlation coefficients as illustrated by the inter-item correlation matrix (see table 4.41).

In summary, the overall estimated Cronbach's alpha statistic for the 44-item inventory is .889. This means that 88.9% of the variability in the composite score of the 44 would be considered as true score variance or internally consistent reliable variance. When Cronbach alpha is calculated under the pretence that the items all have the same variance, a coefficient of .896 is obtained. This suggests that the scale is reliable. However, when some constructs are considered in isolation, lower levels of reliability are attained. Therefore, in this study, the

research constructs are understood within the context of the other research constructs, and not in isolation.

4.2 Descriptive analysis

This section presents the descriptive analysis of the survey results. Firstly, results of demographics are presented and then followed by tests for association between variables.

4.2.1 Demographics

Figure 4. 1: Gender

Figure 4.1 presented the classification of information related to the participants' gender. The largest portion of the sample indicated that there were male 59.80%, followed by those who revealed that there were female 40.18%.

Figure 4.1 illustrates the age of the participating firms. Most of the participating firms indicated that they were less than 10 years old (42.86%). This was followed by 25% who indicated being 10 to 15 years of age. The next category was 16-20 years of age with 11.61%. This was followed by 8.04% that were in the 26-30 years category. Lastly, the remainder of the firms, 4.46% were in the 30 years and above category.

Figure 4. 2: Age of the firm

In terms of the level of education of the respondents, most of the respondents, 38.39% indicated that they were holders of a bachelor’s degree qualification. This was then followed by 27.68% of the respondents who indicated that they have Diploma or HND certificate. In addition, 17.86% of the respondents revealed that they have primary education and below. This was then followed by 16.07% who indicated that they have obtained master’s degree and above. The level of education of the respondents is graphically depicted in figure 4.2

Figure 4. 3: Level of Education

The experience of owners in the industry was also ascertained. It was found that 40.18% of the respondents were in the 0-5 years’ experience category. This was followed by the 6-10 years’

experience category and the 11-15 years' experience category with 20.54% of the respondents each. In addition, 10.71% of the respondents had industry experience that ranged from 16 to 20 years. Lastly, 8.04% of the respondents had industry experience that was in the 20 years and above category. This is illustrated in figure 4.4.

Figure 4. 4: Owners' experience

The number of employees working in the respondent's company was also determined. It was found that 36.61% of the respondents indicated that they had between 11-50 employees. This was followed by the 51-100 employees' category with 26.79% of the respondents. Further, 13.39% of the respondents indicated that they employed between 0 and 10 people. Finally, 11.61% of the respondents indicated that they employed between 101 and 150 people. Similarly, another 11.61% indicated that they also employed between 151 and 250 people. This is illustrated in figure 4.5.

Figure 4. 5: Number of employees

Figure 4.6 presented the classification of information related to the respondent's firm industry sector. The largest portion of the sample indicated that they were in the wood industry (29.46%). This was followed by the agriculture sector with 26.79%. In addition, 25.89% of the respondents indicated that they were in the textiles industry. This was followed by 11.61% of the respondents who reported that they were in the metal industry. Only 6.25% of the respondents reported that they were in the oil industry.

Figure 4. 6: Firm industry sector

Figure 4. 7: Region of operation

Respondents were also asked to indicate the regions of the country their firm operates its international activities. It was found that 26.79 of the respondents operated in the Littoral region. This was followed by 22.32% who indicated that their firms operate in the Northwest region. In addition, 13.39% of the respondents indicated that their firms operate in the CEMAC zone. Furthermore, 11.61% of the respondents indicated that their firms operated in the Southwest region. Another 8.93% indicated that their firms operate in the rest of Africa. Only 6.25% of the respondents indicated that their firms operated in the rest of the world. This is illustrated in figure 4.8

Respondents were also asked to indicate their main suppliers and clients of products that they manufacture. It was found that 49.11 of the respondents operated indicated that their main suppliers and clients were SMES. This was followed by 20.54% who indicated that their main suppliers and clients were very small medium enterprises. Only 16.07% cited the government firms as their main supplier or clients. A further 14.29% of the respondents indicated that their main suppliers and clients were MNCs. This is illustrated in figure 4.8

Figure 4. 8: Client and supplier base

Figure 4.9 shown above present’s individual responses for existing international opportunity for the respondent’s firms. In fact, respondents were presented with a statement that “there is existing international opportunity” for their companies. Only 9.82% of the respondents strongly agreed, whilst 15.18% agreed. Those neutral to the statement were 11.61%. Many of the respondents (33.04%) disagreed that there is an existing international opportunity, whilst 30.36% strongly disagreed.

Figure 4. 9: Existing international opportunity

Figure 4. 10: Internationalisation speed

Respondents were also asked to describe the internationalisation speed of their company. Most of the respondents (75.89%) indicated that the internationalisation speed was slow. This was followed by 14.29% of the respondents who indicated that it was medium. Finally, 9.82% of the respondents indicated that the internationalisation speed was high or rapid. This is illustrated in figure 4.10.

4.2.2 Knowledge and International Experience Barriers

The sections that follow provide diagrammatic representations of how participants responded to the individual questions. The above table show results on knowledge and international experience barriers. The results show that more than half of the participants agreed that there is a shortage of knowledge on foreign market opportunities (21.4% + 59.8%). Similarly, 82.2% of the respondents share the view that there is a shortage of knowledge on perspective buyers, international agents, and suppliers. Further, 83% of the respondents agree that there is lack of research in international market. Similarly, 74.1% of the respondents share the view that there is a shortage of information on international product pricing. Finally, 81.3% of the respondents

indicated that there are language and communication difficulties. Each of the variables is discussed here in turn.

Table 4. 35: Knowledge barriers

Variable	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Shortage of knowledge on foreign market opportunities	3.6%	8.9%	6.3%	21.4%	59.8%
Shortage of knowledge on perspective buyers, international agents and suppliers	0.0%	12.5%	5.4%	28.6%	53.6%
Lack of research in international market	0.9%	9.8%	6.3%	25.0%	58.0%
Shortage of information on international product pricing	8.9%	12.5%	4.5%	25.0%	49.1%
Language and communication difficulties	1.8%	9.8%	7.1%	28.6%	52.7%

Respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which they agreed or disagreed with the statement that there is a shortage of knowledge on foreign market opportunities. As illustrated in figure 5.12, 59.82% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 21.43% agreed. Only 6.25% were indifferent. More noticeably, 3.57% strongly disagreed whilst 8.93% disagreed.

Figure 4. 11: Foreign opportunities

Figure 4. 12: Agents, suppliers, and buyers

Respondents were also presented with an evaluative statement stating that there is a shortage of knowledge on perspective buyers, international agents, and suppliers, to which they had to indicate the extent to which they agreed or disagreed. The results illustrated in figure 5.13, indicated that 53.57% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 28.57% agreed. Only 5.36% were indifferent. More noticeably, none of the respondents strongly disagreed, whilst only 12.50% disagreed.

Figure 4. 13: International market research

Respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which they agreed or disagreed with the statement that there is a lack of research in international market. As illustrated in figure 4.14, 58.04% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 25% agreed. Only 6.25% were indifferent. More noticeably, 0.89% strongly disagreed whilst 9.82% disagreed.

Furthermore, respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which they agreed or disagreed with the statement that there is a shortage of information on international product pricing. As illustrated in figure 5.15, 49.11% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 25% agreed. Only 4.46% were indifferent. More noticeably, 8.93% strongly disagreed whilst 12.50% disagreed.

Figure 4. 14: Product pricing

Furthermore, respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which they agreed or disagreed with the statement that there are language and communication difficulties. As illustrated in figure 5.16, 52.68% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 28.57% agreed. Only 7.14% were indifferent. More noticeably, 1.79% strongly disagreed whilst 9.82% disagreed.

Figure 4. 15: Communication difficulties

5.2.3 Human Resources Barriers

Table 4. 36: Human resources barriers

Variable	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Shortage of trained personnel in the international market	2.7%	6.3%	5.4%	34.8%	50.9%
Low or no managerial international exposure	3.6%	6.3%	1.8%	33.9%	54.5%
Inexperience managerial(owner) on development on international activities	1.8%	10.7%	5.4%	44.6%	37.5%
Lack of structure plan and execution of international activities	1.8%	8.9%	3.65	28.6%	57.1%

The above table show results on human resources barriers. The results show that more than half of the participants agreed that there is a shortage of trained personnel in the international market (34.8% + 50.9%). Similarly, 88.4% of the respondents share the view that there are low or no managerial international exposure. Additionally, 82.1% of the respondents reported that inexperience managerial (owner) on development on international activities is a human resources barrier. Finally, 85.7% of the respondents reported that there is a lack of structure plan and execution of international activities. Each of the variables is discussed here in turn.

Respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which they agreed or disagreed with the statement that there is a shortage of trained personnel in the international market. As illustrated in figure 5.16, 50.89% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 34.82% agreed. Only 5.36% were indifferent. More noticeably, 2.68% strongly disagreed whilst 6.25% disagreed.

Figure 4. 16: Shortage of trained personnel

Respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which they agreed or disagreed with the statement that there is low or no managerial international exposure. As illustrated in figure 4.17, 54.46% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 33.93% agreed. Only 1.79% was indifferent. More noticeably, 3.57% strongly disagreed whilst 6.25% disagreed.

Figure 4. 17: Low managerial exposure

Figure 4. 18: Inexperienced on international activities

Respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which they agreed or disagreed with the statement that there is inexperience managerial (owner) on development on international activities. As illustrated in figure 5.16, 37.50% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 44.64% agreed. Only 5.36% were indifferent. More noticeably, 1.79% strongly disagreed whilst 10.71% disagreed.

Figure 4. 19:Lack of structure, plan, and execution

Respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which they agreed or disagreed with the statement that there is a lack of structure plan and execution of international activities. As illustrated in figure 5.17, 57.14% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 28.57% agreed. Only 3.57% were indifferent. More noticeably, 1.79% strongly disagreed whilst 8.93% disagreed.

4.2.4 Financial Barriers

The above table show results on financial barriers. The results show that more than half of the participants agreed that there is a shortage of fund for firm to self-finance international operations (38.4% + 46.4%). Similarly, 82.2% of the respondents share the view that there is strict requirement for credit loan from bank. Additionally, 84.83% of the respondents are of the view that there is a lack of government aid to finance international activities. Each of the variables is discussed here in turn.

Table 4. 37: Financial barriers

Variable	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Shortage of fund for firm to self-finance international operations	1.8%	7.1%	6.3%	38.4%	46.4%
Strict requirement for credit loan from bank	2.7%	10.7%	4.5%	25.9%	56.3%
Lack of Government aid to finance international activities	2.68%	6.25%	6.25%	39.29%	45.54%

Figure 4. 20: Shortage of funds

Respondents were presented with an evaluative statement stating that there is a shortage of funds for international operations. As illustrated in figure 5.17, 46.43% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 38.39% agreed. Only 6.25% were indifferent. More noticeably, 1.79% strongly disagreed whilst 7.14% disagreed.

Respondents were presented with an evaluative statement stating that there are strict bank loan requirements. As illustrated in figure 5.18, 56.25% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 25.89% agreed. Only 4.46% were indifferent. More noticeably, 2.68% strongly disagreed whilst 10.71% disagreed. Further, respondents were presented with an evaluative statement stating that there is a lack of government aid to finance international activities. As illustrated

in figure 4.22, 45.54% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 39.29% agreed. Only 6.25%% were indifferent. More noticeably, 2.68% strongly disagreed whilst another 6.25% disagreed.

Figure 4. 21: Strict bank loan requirements

Figure 4. 22: Lack of government aid

4.2.5 Product Barriers

Table 4.45 show results on product barriers. The results show that more than half of the participants agreed that there is a problem in product quality (82.2%). Similarly, 84.8% of the respondents share the view that the product is no able to meet international packaging standards. Additionally, respondents were presented with an evaluative statement pointing out that the product is unable to meet global product standards, and 85.7% of the respondents shared this view. Respondents also shared the view that there is a lack of ability to produce large quantity that meets market demand, as reported by 88.4% participants. Finally, respondents were presented with an evaluative statement pointing out there is a product branding problem, and this was supported by 82.1% of the respondents.

Table 4. 38: Product barriers

Variable	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Problem in product quality	2.7%	10.7%	4.5%	25.9%	56.3%
Unable to meet international packaging standard	2.7%	6.3%	6.3%	39.3%	45.5%
Unable to meet global product standards	2.7%	6.3%	5.4%	34.8%	50.9%
Lack of ability to produce large quantity that meets market demand	3.6%	6.3%	1.8%	33.9%	54.5%
Product branding problem	1.8%	10.7%	5.4%	44.6%	37.5%

Respondents were presented with an evaluative statement stating that there is a problem with product quality. As illustrated in figure 5.18, 56.25% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 25.89% agreed. Only 4.46% were indifferent. More noticeably, 2.68% strongly disagreed whilst another 10.71% disagreed (see figure 4.23).

Figure 4. 23: Problem of product quality

Figure 4. 24: Packaging standards

Respondents were presented with an evaluative statement stating that the product is not able to meet international packaging standards. As illustrated in figure 5.24, 45.54% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 39.29% agreed. Only 6.25% were indifferent. More noticeably, 2.68% strongly disagreed whilst another 6.25% disagreed.

Figure 4. 25: Global product standards

Respondents were presented with an evaluative statement stating that the product is not able to meet global product standards as illustrated in figure 4.25, 50.89% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 34.82% agreed. Only 5.36% were indifferent. More noticeably, 2.68% strongly disagreed whilst another 6.25% disagreed.

Figure 4. 26: Low stock production

Respondents were presented with an evaluative statement stating that there is lack of ability to produce large quantity that meets market demand. As illustrated in figure 4.26, 54.46% strongly

agreed with the statement whilst 33.93% agreed. Only 1.79% was indifferent. More noticeably, 3.57% strongly disagreed whilst another 6.25% disagreed.

Figure 4. 27: Product branding problem

Respondents were presented with an evaluative statement stating that there is a product branding problem. As illustrated in figure 5.19, 37.50% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 44.64% agreed. Only 5.36% were indifferent. More noticeably, 1.79% strongly disagreed whilst another 10.71% disagreed.

4.2.6 Bureaucratic barriers

Table 4. 39: Bureaucratic barriers

Variable	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Lack of international promotion program	1.8%	8.9%	3.6%	28.6%	57.1%
None or very little support to overcome international barriers	2.7%	6.3%	5.4%	34.8%	50.9%
Inadequate sponsorship by government to support private businesses	3.6%	6.3%	1.8%	33.9%	54.5%
Poor diplomatic support	1.8%	10.7%	5.4%	44.6%	37.5%

The above table show results on government bureaucratic barriers. The results show that more than half of the participants agreed that there is a lack of international promotion program (85.7%). Similarly, another 85.7% of the respondents share the view that there is none or very little support to overcome international barriers. Further, 88.4% of the respondents agree that there is inadequate sponsorship by government to support private businesses. Finally, 82.1% of the respondents indicated that there is poor diplomatic support. Each of the variables is discussed here in turn.

Respondents were presented with an evaluative statement stating that there is a lack of international promotion program. As illustrated in figure 5.20 57.14% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 28.57% agreed. Only 3.57% were indifferent. More noticeably, 1.79% strongly disagreed whilst another 8.93% disagreed.

Figure 4. 28: International promotion program

Figure 4. 29: Support to overcome international barriers

Respondents were presented with an evaluative statement stating that there is none or very little support to overcome international barriers. As illustrated in figure 5.28, 50.89% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 34.82% agreed. Only 5.36% were indifferent. More noticeably, 2.68% strongly disagreed whilst another 6.25% disagreed.

Figure 4. 30: Inadequate governmental sponsorship

Respondents were presented with an evaluative statement stating that there is inadequate sponsorship by government to support private businesses. As illustrated in figure 5.29, 54.46% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 33.93% agreed. Only 1.79% was indifferent. More noticeably, 3.57% strongly disagreed whilst another 6.25% disagreed.

Figure 4. 31: Poor diplomatic support

Respondents were presented with an evaluative statement stating that there is poor diplomatic support. As illustrated in figure 5.22, 37.50% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 44.64% agreed. Only 5.36% were indifferent. More noticeably, 1.79% strongly disagreed whilst another 10.71% disagreed.

4.2.7 Exogenous barriers

Table 4.47 above shows results on exogenous barriers. In this category, respondents agreed with all the evaluative statements as illustrated by international trade policy (85.7%); trade regulations (84.8%); high domestic values (85.7%); exchange rate fluctuation (88.4%); inflation rate (82.1%); international trade taxes (85.7%); high interest rate (84.8%); and political stability (84.8%).

Table 4. 40: Exogenous barriers

Variable	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
International trade Policy	1.8%	8.9%	3.6%	28.6%	57.1%
Trade regulations	1.8%	7.1%	6.3%	38.4%	46.4%
High domestic Values	2.7%	6.3%	5.4%	34.8%	50.9%
Exchange rate fluctuation	3.6%	6.3%	1.8%	33.9%	54.5%
Inflation rate	1.8%	10.7%	5.4%	44.6%	37.5%
International trade taxes	1.8%	8.9%	3.6%	28.6%	57.1%
High interest rate	1.8%	7.1%	6.3%	38.4%	46.4%
Political Instability	2.7%	6.3%	6.3%	34.8%	50.0%

Figure 4. 32: International trade policy

When presented with an evaluative statement on international trade policy, 57.14% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 28.57% agreed. Only 3.57% were indifferent. More noticeably, 1.79% strongly disagreed whilst another 8.93% disagreed.

Figure 4. 33: Trade regulations

When presented with an evaluative statement on trade regulations, 46.43% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 38.39% agreed. Only 6.25% were indifferent. More noticeably, 1.79% strongly disagreed whilst another 7.14% disagreed.

Figure 4. 34: High domestic values

When presented with an evaluative statement on domestic values, 50.89% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 34.82% agreed. Only 5.36% were indifferent. More noticeably, 2.68% strongly disagreed whilst another 6.25% disagreed.

Figure 4. 35: Exchange rate fluctuation

When presented with an evaluative statement on exchange rate fluctuation, 54.46% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 33.93% agreed. Only 1.79% was indifferent. More noticeably, 3.57% strongly disagreed whilst another 6.25% disagreed.

Figure 4. 36: Inflation rate

When presented with an evaluative statement on inflation rate, 37.50% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 44.64% agreed. Only 5.36% were indifferent. More noticeably, 1.79% strongly disagreed whilst another 10.71% disagreed.

Figure 4. 37: International trade taxes

When presented with an evaluative statement on international trade taxes, 57.14% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 28.57% agreed. Only 3.57% were indifferent. More noticeably, 1.79% strongly disagreed whilst another 8.93% disagreed.

Figure 4. 38: High interest rate

When presented with an evaluative statement on interest rates, 46.43% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 38.39% agreed. Only 6.25% were indifferent. More noticeably, 1.79% strongly disagreed whilst another 7.14% disagreed.

Figure 4. 39: Political instability

When presented with an evaluative statement on political stability, 50% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 34.82% agreed. Only 6.25% were indifferent. More noticeably, 2.68% strongly disagreed whilst another 6.25% disagreed.

Figure 4. 40: Reason for remaining domestic

Respondents were also asked to indicate the reason for their company to remain in the domestic market. The majority (36.61%) indicated experience gained over time as a major factor. This was followed by 21.43% who reported that low financial involvement was a factor to remain in the domestic market. Further, 16.96% indicated that competitive advantage was a motivating

factor to remain in the domestic market. Additionally, 16.07% reported that cultural awareness was a factor. Only 8.93% cites other factors. This is illustrated in figure above.

5.2.8 Factors valuable for the domestic market

The above show results on factors and criteria valuable for the domestic market. The results show that more than half of the participants are in support of a change in political system of the government (73.2%). Economic climate change factor was supported by only 13.4%. Competitive rivalries variable was supported by 70.6%, whilst change in government regulations was supported by only 14.3%. Each of these factors is presented here in turn.

Table 4. 41: Factors valuable for domestic market

Variable	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Change in political system of the Government	6.3%	8.9%	11.6%	28.6%	44.6%
Economic climate change	8.9%	64.3%	13.4%	8.0%	5.4%
Competitive Rivalries	6.3%	10.7%	12.5%	28.6%	42.0%
Change in government regulations	8.9%	64.3%	12.5%	8.0%	6.3%

When presented with an evaluative statement on change in political system, 44.64% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 28.57% agreed. Only 11.61% were indifferent. More noticeably, 6.25% strongly disagreed whilst another 8.93% disagreed.

Figure 4. 41: Change in political system

Figure 4. 42: Economic climate change

When presented with an evaluative statement on economic climate change, 5.36% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 8.04% agreed. Only 13.39% were indifferent. Consistent with this, 8.93% strongly disagreed whilst most of the respondents (64.29%) disagreed.

Figure 4. 43: Competitive rivalry

When presented with an evaluative statement on competitive rivalries, 41.96% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 28.57% agreed. Only 12.50% were indifferent. More noticeably, 6.25% strongly disagreed whilst another 10.71% disagreed.

Figure 4. 44: Change in government regulations

When presented with an evaluative statement on change in government regulations, only 6.25% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 8.04% agreed. Only 12.50% were indifferent. In a similar vein, 8.93% strongly disagreed whilst another 64.29% disagreed.

4.2.8 General Factors of influence

Table 4. 42: General factors

Variable	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Political/Legal factors	1.8%	7.1%	6.3%	38.4%	46.4%
Cultural Factors	2.7%	6.3%	6.3%	34.8%	50.0%
Competitive advantage	8.9%	17.0%	16.1%	21.4%	36.6%
Firm's level of technology	6.3%	8.9%	11.6%	28.6%	44.6%
Distribution structure	8.9%	64.3%	13.4%	8.0%	5.4%
Size of the Firm	6.3%	10.7%	12.5%	28.6%	42.0%
Age of the firm	8.9%	64.3%	12.5%	8.0%	6.3%
Cultural similarities	3.6%	8.9%	6.3%	21.4%	59.8%
Market similarities	0.0%	12.5%	5.4%	28.6%	53.6%
International relationship/network	0.9%	9.8%	6.3%	25.0%	58.0%
Entrepreneurial/Managerial expertise	8.9%	12.5%	4.5%	25.0%	49.1%
Environmental awareness	8.9%	17.0%	13.4%	21.4%	39.3%

The table above show results on general factors of influence. In this category, respondents agreed with all the evaluative statements as illustrated by Political legal factors (84.8%); cultural factors (84.8%); competitive advantage (58%); firm's level of technology (73.2%); distribution structure (13.4%); size of the firm (70.6%); age of the firm (14.3%); cultural similarities (81.2%); market similarities (82.2%); international relationship or network (83%); entrepreneurial or managerial expertise (74.1%); and environmental awareness (60.7%).

Figure 4. 45: Political legal factors

When presented with an evaluative statement on political legal factors, 46.43% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 38.39% agreed. Only 6.25% were indifferent. More noticeably, 1.79% strongly disagreed whilst another 7.14% disagreed.

Figure 4. 46: Cultural factors

When presented with an evaluative statement on cultural factors, 50% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 34.82% agreed. Only 6.25% were indifferent. More noticeably, 2.68% strongly disagreed whilst another 6.25% disagreed.

Figure 4. 47: Competitive advantage

When presented with an evaluative statement on competitive advantage, 36.61% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 21.43% agreed. Only 16.07% were indifferent. More noticeably, 8.93% strongly disagreed whilst another 16.96% disagreed.

Figure 4. 48: Firm's level of technology

When presented with an evaluative statement on a firm's level of technology, 44.64% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 28.57% agreed. Only 11.61% were indifferent. More noticeably, 6.25% strongly disagreed whilst another 8.93% disagreed.

Figure 4. 49: Distribution structure

When presented with an evaluative statement on distribution structure, only 5.36% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 8.04% agreed. Only 13.39% were indifferent. Further, only 8.93% strongly disagreed whilst the majority of 64.29% disagreed.

Figure 4. 50: Size of firm

When presented with an evaluative statement on size of the firm, 41.96% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 28.57% agreed. Only 12.50% were indifferent. More noticeably, 6.25% strongly disagreed whilst another 10.71% disagreed.

Figure 4. 51: Age of firm

When presented with an evaluative statement about the age of the firm, only 6.25% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 8.04% agreed. Only 12.50% were indifferent. Further, only 8.93% strongly disagreed whilst a majority of 64.29% disagreed.

Figure 4. 52: Cultural similarities

When presented with an evaluative statement about cultural similarities, 59.82% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 21.43% agreed. Only 6.25% were indifferent. More noticeably, 3.57% strongly disagreed whilst another 8.93% disagreed.

Figure 4. 53: Market similarities

When presented with an evaluative statement about market similarities, 53.57% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 28.57% agreed. Only 5.36% were indifferent. More noticeably, 12.50% disagreed.

Figure 4. 54: International relationship/network

When presented with an evaluative statement about international relationships or networks, 58.04% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 25% agreed. Only 6.25% were indifferent. More noticeably, 0.89% strongly disagreed whilst another 9.82% disagreed.

Figure 4. 55: Entrepreneurial / managerial expertise

When presented with an evaluative statement about entrepreneurial or managerial expertise, 49.11% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 25% agreed. Only 4.46% were indifferent. More noticeably, 8.93% strongly disagreed whilst another 12.50% disagreed.

Figure 4. 56: Environmental awareness

When presented with an evaluative statement about environmental awareness, 39.29% strongly agreed with the statement whilst 21.43% agreed. Only 13.39% were indifferent. More noticeably, 8.93% strongly disagreed whilst another 16.96% disagreed.

Figure 4. 57: Internationalisation process

Respondents were also asked to identify a factor that described their company’s process of international expansion, or a process that they would use. The majority (44.64%) indicated international entrepreneurship. This was followed by 22.32% who highlighted the network or relationship model. Further, 16.96% indicated the born global policy. Additionally, 8.93% suggested the transaction cost approach. Only 7.14% indicated the Uppsala model of internationalisation. This is illustrated in figure 4.57.

Figure 4. 58: International activities

Respondents were also asked about the kind of international activities their company was involved in in the external market. The majority (57.14%) indicated that they are involved in

exporting. This was followed by 25.89% who highlighted that they were involved in importation. Further, 11.61% indicated that they were involved in licensing. Additionally, 4.46% reported that they were involved in franchising. Only 0.89% indicated that they were involved in alliances. This is illustrated in figure 4.58.

4.3 CHI-SQUARE TESTS

Chi-square tests were conducted to test the association between variables of interest to this study. It should be noted that the chi-square only looks at the presence of an association but says nothing about the direction or strength of the association. This helps to better understand variables of interest, and their association with other variables of interest within the context of the research questions.

4.3.1 Association between Gender and Educational Level

Table 4. 43: Case processing summary

Case Processing Summary							
		Cases					
		Valid		Missing		Total	
		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Gender * Educational Level		112	100.0%	0	0.0%	112	100.0%

Table 4. 44: Gender vs education

Gender * Educational Level Crosstabulation						
		Educational Level				Total
		Primary education and below	Diploma/HND Certificate	Bachelor certificate	Master degree and Above	
Gender	Male	14	15	26	12	67
	Female	6	16	17	6	45
Total		20	31	43	18	112

The observed counts for gender and educational level of the participants are presented in table 4.51. There is a need to determine whether those observe differences are enough for the association to be significant. The results of the associated chi-square test are illustrated below.

Table 4. 45: Chi-Square tests

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.907 ^a	3	.406
Likelihood Ratio	2.910	3	.406
Linear-by-Linear Association	.020	1	.888
N of Valid Cases	112		
a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 7.23.			

It emerges that zero cells have expected counts of less than 5. The assumption is that this should not exceed 20%. In this case, it is 0.0%, and does not violate the chi-square assumptions.00. The Pearson chi-square statistic is 2.907. However, the result is not significant, as indicated by the likelihood ratio of 2.910 and an associated p value of 0.406. This is greater than 0.05. In other words, the gender of the respondents is completely independent of their educational level. In this case, there is no need to further analyse the symmetric measures.

Table 4. 46: Symmetric measures

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.161	.406
	Cramer's V	.161	.406
N of Valid Cases		112	

4.3.2 Association between firm industry sector and growth process

Table 4. 47: Case processing summary

Case Processing Summary

	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Firm Industry sector * Growth process	112	100.0%	0	0.0%	112	100.0%

Table 4. 48: Industry sector vs growth

Firm Industry sector * Growth process Cross-tabulation					
Count					
		Growth process			Total
		Slow	Medium	High/Rapid	
Firm Industry sector	Wood	27	1	5	33
	Textile	24	5	0	29
	Agriculture	19	5	6	30
	Metal	10	3	0	13
	Oil	5	2	0	7
Total		85	16	11	112

The observed counts for firm industry sector and growth process are presented in table 4.55.

There is a need to determine whether those observe differences are enough for the association to be significant. The results of the associated chi-square test are illustrated in table 4.56.

Table 4. 49: Chi-Square tests

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	14.834 ^a	8	.062
Likelihood Ratio	19.846	8	.011
Linear-by-Linear Association	.138	1	.710
N of Valid Cases	112		

a. 10 cells (66.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .69.

It emerges that 10 cells have expected counts of less than 5. The assumption is that this should not exceed 20%. In this case, it is 66.7%, and violates the chi-square assumptions. The Pearson chi-square statistic is 14.834. However, the result is significant, as indicated by the likelihood

ratio of 19.846 and an associated p value of 0.011. This is less than 0.05. In other words, the firm industry sector of the respondents is not independent of their growth process.

Table 4. 50: Symmetric measures

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.364	.062
	Cramer's V	.257	.062
N of Valid Cases		112	

4.3.3 Association between firm industry sector and client and supplier base

Table 4. 51: Case processing summary

Case Processing Summary						
	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Firm Industry sector * Client and Supplier base	112	100.0%	0	0.0%	112	100.0%

The observed counts for firm industry sector and client supplier base are presented in table 4.59 (see appendix 3). There is a need to determine whether those observe differences are enough for the association to be significant. The results of the associated chi-square test are illustrated in table 4.60.

Table 4. 52: Chi-Square tests

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	13.232 ^a	12	.352
Likelihood Ratio	16.827	12	.156
Linear-by-Linear Association	.945	1	.331
N of Valid Cases	112		
a. 12 cells (60.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.00.			

It emerges that 12 cells have expected counts of less than 5. The assumption is that this should not exceed 20%. In this case, it is 60%, and violates the chi-square assumptions. The Pearson chi-square statistic is 13.232. The result is significant, as indicated by the likelihood ratio of 16.827 and an associated p value of 0.156 this is more than 0.05. In other words, the firm industry sector of the respondents is independent of the client and supplier base.

Table 4. 53: Symmetric measures

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.344	.352
	Cramer's V	.198	.352
N of Valid Cases		112	

4.4 Correlational Analysis

Table 4. 54: Correlation analysis

		Correlations								
		Knowledge	HR Barriers	Financial Barriers	Product Barriers	Bureaucratic Barriers	Exogeneous Barriers	Domestic Market	General Factors	
Spearman's rho	Knowledge	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.354**	.179	.333**	.354**	.334**	.168	.700**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	.059	.000	.000	.000	.076	.000
		N	112	112	112	112	112	112	112	112
HR Barriers	HR Barriers	Correlation Coefficient	.354**	1.000	.335**	.834**	1.000**	.857**	.244**	.497**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000	.000	.	.000	.009	.000
		N	112	112	112	112	112	112	112	112
Financial Barriers	Financial Barriers	Correlation Coefficient	.179	.335**	1.000	.666**	.335**	.646**	.093	.334**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.059	.000	.	.000	.000	.000	.330	.000
		N	112	112	112	112	112	112	112	112
Product Barriers	Product Barriers	Correlation Coefficient	.333**	.834**	.666**	1.000	.834**	.845**	.162	.469**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.	.000	.000	.087	.000
		N	112	112	112	112	112	112	112	112
Bureaucratic Barriers	Bureaucratic Barriers	Correlation Coefficient	.354**	1.000**	.335**	.834**	1.000	.857**	.244**	.497**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000	.000	.	.000	.009	.000
		N	112	112	112	112	112	112	112	112
Exogeneous Barriers	Exogeneous Barriers	Correlation Coefficient	.334**	.857**	.646**	.845**	.857**	1.000	.307**	.606**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.	.001	.000
		N	112	112	112	112	112	112	112	112
Domestic Market	Domestic Market	Correlation Coefficient	.168	.244**	.093	.162	.244**	.307**	1.000	.606**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.076	.009	.330	.087	.009	.001	.	.000
		N	112	112	112	112	112	112	112	112
General Factors	General Factors	Correlation Coefficient	.700**	.497**	.334**	.469**	.497**	.606**	.606**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.
		N	112	112	112	112	112	112	112	112

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

A Spearman correlation analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between the research constructs. A significant and positive relationship was found between knowledge and human resource barriers ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient =.354*); knowledge and product barriers ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient =.333*), knowledge and bureaucratic barriers ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient =.354), knowledge and exogenous barriers ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient = .334), as well as knowledge and general factors ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient=.700*). All the significant relationships were positive, and all were at the 0.01 level, 2 tailed. However, the relationship between knowledge, financial barriers, and the domestic market factors was not significant.

Significant relationships were also found between human resources barriers and financial barriers ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient =.335*), human resources barriers and product barriers ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient =.834), human resources barriers and bureaucratic barriers (correlation coefficient = 1); human resources barriers and exogenous barriers ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient = .857**); human resources barriers and domestic market factors ($p=.009$, correlation coefficient = .244**); as well as human resources barriers and general factors ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient = .497**). All the significant relationships were positive, and all were at the 0.01 level, 2 tailed.

Similarly, significant relationships were also found between financial barriers and product barriers ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient = .666**); financial barriers and bureaucratic barriers ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient = .335**), financial barriers and exogenous factors ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient = .646**), financial barriers and general factors ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient = .334**). All the significant relationships were positive, and all were at the 0.01 level, 2 tailed.

However, the relationship between financial barriers and domestic market factors was not significant. Furthermore, significant relationships were found between product barriers and bureaucratic barriers ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient = $.834^{**}$); product barriers and exogenous barriers ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient = $.845^{**}$); product barriers and general factors ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient = $.469^{**}$). All the significant relationships were positive, and all were at the 0.01 level, 2 tailed. However, the relationship between product barriers and domestic market factors was not significant.

A significant relationship was found between bureaucratic barriers and exogenous barriers ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient = $.857^{**}$); bureaucratic barriers and domestic market factors ($p=.009$, correlation coefficient = $.244^{**}$); as well as bureaucratic barriers and general factors ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient = $.497^{**}$). All the significant relationships were positive, and all were at the 0.01 level, 2 tailed.

The study revealed a significant relationship between exogenic barriers and domestic market factors ($p=.001$, correlation coefficient = $.307^{**}$); exogenic barriers and general factors ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient = $.606^{**}$). Further results also revealed a significant relationship between domestic market factors and general factors ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient = $.606^{**}$). All the significant relationships were positive, and all were at the 0.01 level, 2 tailed.

4.5 Ordinal Regression Analysis

Ordinal regression analysis was conducted to determine whether the variables of interest are predictable. The intention is to establish a deeper understanding of the phenomena under investigation.

4.5.1 Knowledge and International Experience Barriers vs. growth process

The case processing summary is as indicated in table above. There were no missing values recorded. All the 112 respondents were accounted for (n= 112), as illustrated in table 4.63 (see appendix 3).

Table 4. 55: Model fitting information

Model Fitting Information				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept Only	141.877			
Final	106.452	35.426	19	.012

Link function: Logit.

Model Fitting Information was tested to determine whether the model can help to improve our ability to predict the outcome. This is statistically significant with a p value of 0.012. This is less than 0.05 and is a good finding as to how well the model fits the data. This suggests that the model gives us realistic predictions than if we just guessed based on the marginal probabilities for the outcome categories.

Table 4. 56: Goodness of fit

Goodness-of-Fit			
	Chi-Square	Df	Sig.
Pearson	173.163	133	.011
Deviance	97.686	133	.991

Link function: Logit.

Table 4.65 illustrates the goodness-of-fit. Here, we would like to fail to reject the null hypothesis. In other words, we are looking for significant values greater than 0.05. In this regard, the Pearson p value is 0.011, and the deviance p value is 0.991. The result is consistent with the model.

Table 4. 57: Pseudo R-square

Pseudo R-Square	
Cox and Snell	.271
Nagelkerke	.356
McFadden	.221
Link function: Logit.	

The above table shows the r square. Here, the r-square of interest is the Nagelkerke, which is .356. This tells us that the model explains 35.6% of the variance in the dependent variable.

Table 4. 58: Parameter estimates

Parameter Estimates								
		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
							Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Threshold	[Q10 = 1.00]	-20.020	2.238	80.038	1	.000	-24.406	-15.634
	[Q10 = 2.00]	-18.494	2.247	67.755	1	.000	-22.898	-14.090
Location	[Q11b=1.00]	-2.169	1.022	4.502	1	.034	-4.173	-.165
	[Q11b=2.00]	-2.113	.989	4.568	1	.033	-4.051	-.175
	[Q11b=3.00]	-.417	1.252	.111	1	.739	-2.870	2.036
	[Q11b=4.00]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
	[Q11c=1.00]	-19.898	.963	427.098	1	.000	-21.785	-18.011
	[Q11c=2.00]	-19.054	.980	378.385	1	.000	-20.974	-17.134
	[Q11c=3.00]	-18.825	1.202	245.159	1	.000	-21.181	-16.468
	[Q11c=4.00]	-19.248	.000	.	1	.	-19.248	-19.248
	[Q11c=5.00]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
	[Q11d=1.00]	1.121	1.242	.815	1	.367	-1.313	3.554
	[Q11d=2.00]	.479	1.261	.144	1	.704	-1.993	2.951
	[Q11d=3.00]	2.971	1.458	4.154	1	.042	.114	5.828
	[Q11d=4.00]	1.619	1.386	1.365	1	.243	-1.097	4.336
	[Q11d=5.00]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
	[Q11e=1.00]	-1.654	1.611	1.054	1	.305	-4.811	1.504
	[Q11e=2.00]	-2.033	1.687	1.452	1	.228	-5.339	1.274
[Q11e=3.00]	-4.003	2.403	2.774	1	.096	-8.713	.707	
[Q11e=4.00]	-.506	1.717	.087	1	.768	-3.872	2.859	

[Q11e=5.00]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[Q11a=1.00]	.644	1.528	.177	1	.674	-2.351	3.638
[Q11a=2.00]	.501	1.527	.107	1	.743	-2.493	3.494
[Q11a=3.00]	.350	1.568	.050	1	.823	-2.724	3.424
[Q11a=4.00]	.753	1.535	.241	1	.624	-2.256	3.763
[Q11a=5.00]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
Link function: Logit.							
a. This parameter is set to zero because it is redundant.							

For the parameter estimates, of knowledge and international experience barriers, these are illustrated in the above table for question the agents, suppliers and buyers' variables, the results mixed, with statistically significant results of 0.034 and 0.033. There is also a result not statistically significant as indicated by the p value of 0.739. For the international market research variable, the results are statistically significant. Further, for the product pricing variable results are not statistically significant as indicated by p values of 0.367; 0.702 and 0.243. However, a p value of 0.042 was also obtained in part. This presents mixed results. In a similar vein, for the communications difficulties variable, the results are not statistically significant as indicated by p values of 0.768, 0.096, 0.228, and 0.305. Similarly, for the foreign opportunities variable, results are not statistically significant as indicated by p values of 0.624, 0.823, 0.743, and 0.674.

The reference variable for agents, suppliers and buyer's variable is set at 11b=4 and has a zero-estimate value. The estimates are then compared to the reference level. The estimates obtained for this variable are -2.129; -2.113; and -.417. This indicates that a lower cumulative score is more likely because it is lower than the reference variable. Similarly, the parameter estimates for the international market research variable are -19.898; -19.054; -18.825; and -19.248. This indicates that a lower cumulative score is more likely because it is lower than the reference variable. On the contrary, the parameter estimates for the product pricing variable are 1.121; .479; 2.971; and 1.619. All these are positive indicating that a higher cumulative score is likely

as these are higher than the reference variable. The parameter estimates for the communication difficulties variable are all negative as illustrated by -1.654; -2.033; -4.003 and -.506. This indicates that a lower cumulative score is likely as these are lower than the reference variable. Finally, the parameter estimates for foreign opportunities variable are all positive as illustrated by .644; .501; .350; .753. These indicated that a higher cumulative score is likely as they are greater than the reference variable.

Table 4. 59: Test of Parallel Lines

Test of Parallel Lines ^a				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Null Hypothesis	106.452			
General	94.441 ^b	12.010 ^c	19	.885
The null hypothesis states that the location parameters (slope coefficients) are the same across response categories.				
a. Link function: Logit.				
b. The log-likelihood value cannot be further increased after maximum number of step-halving.				
c. The Chi-Square statistic is computed based on the log-likelihood value of the last iteration of the general model.				
Validity of the test is uncertain.				

The table illustrates the test of parallel lines. The intention was to test the assumption of proportional odds. Ordinarily, we would like this to be greater or equal to 0.05. In our case, the p value is 0.885, and this is greater than 0.05. Therefore, the results are consistent with the assumption of parallel lines. This is a good result for the variables under consideration.

4.5.2 Human Resources Barriers vs. growth process

The case processing summary is as indicated in table above. There were no missing values recorded. All the 112 respondents were accounted for (n= 112), as illustrated in table 4.49 (see appendix 3).

Table 4. 60: Model fitting information

Model Fitting Information				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	Df	Sig.
Intercept Only	117.946			
Final	92.713	25.233	16	.066
Link function: Logit.				

Model Fitting Information was tested to determine whether the model can help to improve our ability to predict the outcome. This is not statistically significant with a p value of 0.066. This is more than 0.05. This suggests that the model does not give us realistic predictions than if we just guessed based on the marginal probabilities for the outcome categories.

Table 4. 61: Goodness of fit

Goodness-of-Fit			
	Chi-Square	Df	Sig.
Pearson	83.786	96	.809
Deviance	74.419	96	.950
Link function: Logit.			

Table 4.71 illustrates the goodness-of-fit. Here, we would like to fail to reject the null hypothesis. In other words, we are looking for significant values greater than 0.05. In this regard, the Pearson p value is 0.809, and the deviance p value is 0.950. The result is consistent with the model.

Table 4. 62: Pseudo R-square

Pseudo R-Square	
Cox and Snell	.202
Nagelkerke	.265
McFadden	.157
Link function: Logit.	

Table above shows the r square. Here, the r-square of interest is the Nagelkerke, which is .265 this tells us that the model explains 26.5% of the variance in the dependent variable.

For the parameter estimates, of human resources barriers, these are illustrated in the table. For question shortage of trained personnel in the international market variable, the results are not statistically significant as illustrated by p values of .997 for the variables. For the Low or no managerial international exposure variable, there are mixed results with p values of 0.018; 0.061; 0.998; 0.158. Only one result in this category is statistically significant, that is, with a p value of less than 0.05. In a similar vein, inexperience managerial (owner) on development on international activities variable, the results are statistically significant as indicated by p values of 0.00 for 3 variables in this category.

Table 4. 63: Parameter estimates

Parameter Estimates								
		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	Df	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
							Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Threshold	[Q10 = 1.00]	32.095	5238.427	.000	1	.995	-10235.033	10299.224
	[Q10 = 2.00]	33.453	5238.427	.000	1	.995	-10233.676	10300.581
Location	[Q12a=1.00]	18.677	5238.427	.000	1	.997	-10248.452	10285.805
	[Q12a=2.00]	18.002	5238.427	.000	1	.997	-10249.127	10285.130
	[Q12a=3.00]	21.593	5238.427	.000	1	.997	-10245.535	10288.722
	[Q12a=4.00]	18.527	5238.427	.000	1	.997	-10248.601	10285.656
	[Q12a=5.00]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
	[Q12b=1.00]	-3.113	1.310	5.645	1	.018	-5.680	-.545
	[Q12b=2.00]	-2.370	1.263	3.519	1	.061	-4.846	.106
	[Q12b=3.00]	-19.830	7258.441	.000	1	.998	-14246.114	14206.454
	[Q12b=4.00]	-2.144	1.520	1.991	1	.158	-5.123	.834
	[Q12b=5.00]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
	[Q12c=1.00]	16.965	.840	408.230	1	.000	15.319	18.611

[Q12c=2.00]	17.162	.840	417.087	1	.000	15.515	18.809
[Q12c=3.00]	16.563	1.247	176.433	1	.000	14.119	19.007
[Q12c=4.00]	16.977	.000	.	1	.	16.977	16.977
[Q12c=5.00]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[Q12d=1.00]	-1.929	1.421	1.842	1	.175	-4.714	.856
[Q12d=2.00]	-2.579	1.503	2.943	1	.086	-5.526	.368
[Q12d=3.00]	-.667	1.648	.164	1	.686	-3.897	2.563
[Q12d=4.00]	-2.127	1.684	1.595	1	.207	-5.428	1.174
[Q12d=5.00]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
Link function: Logit.							
a. This parameter is set to zero because it is redundant.							

However, we failed to obtain any result for one of the measures. Finally, for the variable lack of structure plan and execution of international activities, the result is not statistically significant as illustrated by p values of .175; .086; .686; .207. All these measures have p values that are above 0.05.

For the variable shortage of trained personnel in the international market, the reference variable is set at measure q12a=5 and has a zero-estimate value. The estimates are then compared to the reference level. The estimates obtained for this variable are 18.677; 18.002; 21.593; and 18.527. This indicates that a higher cumulative score is more likely because it is higher than the reference variable. Similarly, the parameter estimates for low or no managerial international exposure are -3.113; -2.370; -19.830 and -2.144. All these are negative. This indicates that a lower cumulative score is likely as they are all lower than the reference variable. On the contrary, the parameter estimates for inexperience managerial (owner) on development on international activities are 16.965; 17.162; 16.563 and 16.977. All these are positive and greater than the reference variable. This means that the measures are consistent in that cumulative scores more than the reference variable are likely. Finally, the parameter estimates lack of structure plan and execution of international activities variable are, -1.929; -2.579; -

.667; and -2.127. These indicated that a lower cumulative score is likely as they are lower than the reference variable.

Table 4. 64: Test of parallel lines

Test of Parallel Lines				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	Df	Sig.
Null Hypothesis	92.713			
General	126.806 ^b	. ^c	16	.

The null hypothesis states that the location parameters (slope coefficients) are the same across response categories.

a. Link function: Logit.

b. The log-likelihood value cannot be further increased after maximum number of step-halving.

c. The log-likelihood value of the general model is smaller than that of the null model. This is because convergence cannot be attained or ascertained in estimating the general model. Therefore, the test of parallel lines cannot be performed.

The table above illustrates the test of parallel lines. The intention was to test the assumption of proportional odds. Ordinarily, we would like this to be greater or equal to 0.05. In our case, the p value has not been generated because of violation of assumptions. Further data may have to be collected.

4.5.3 Financial barriers vs. growth process

The case processing summary is as indicated in above table. There were no missing values recorded. All the 112 respondents were accounted for (n= 112), as illustrated in table 4.75 (see appendix 3).

Table 4. 65: Model fitting information

Model Fitting Information				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	Df	Sig.
Intercept Only	83.530			
Final	71.082	12.448	12	.410
Link function: Logit.				

Model Fitting Information was tested to determine whether the model can help to improve our ability to predict the outcome. This is not statistically significant with a p value of 0.410. This is more than 0.05. This suggests that the model does not give us realistic predictions than if we just guessed based on the marginal probabilities for the outcome categories.

Table 4. 66: Goodness of fit

Goodness-of-Fit			
	Chi-Square	Df	Sig.
Pearson	60.292	44	.052
Deviance	49.529	44	.262

Link function: Logit.

Table illustrates the goodness-of-fit. Here, we would like to fail to reject the null hypothesis. In other words, we are looking for significant values greater than 0.05. In this regard, the Pearson p value is 0.052, and the deviance p value is 0.262. The result is consistent with the model.

Table 4. 67: Pseudo R-Square

Pseudo R-Square	
Cox and Snell	.105
Nagelkerke	.138
McFadden	.078

Link function: Logit.

The table above shows the r square. Here, the r-square of interest is the Nagelkerke, which is .138. This tells us that the model explains 13.8% of the variance in the dependent variable.

Table 4. 68: Parameter estimates

Parameter Estimates								
		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	Df	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
							Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Threshold	[Q10 = 1.00]	-2.359	1.852	1.622	1	.203	-5.989	1.271
	[Q10 = 2.00]	-1.142	1.834	.388	1	.533	-4.736	2.452
Location	[Q13a=1.00]	-17.923	4798.249	.000	1	.997	-9422.319	9386.472

[Q13a=2.00]	-18.138	4798.249	.000	1	.997	-9422.533	9386.258
[Q13a=3.00]	-17.270	4798.249	.000	1	.997	-9421.665	9387.126
[Q13a=4.00]	2.416	1.665	2.107	1	.147	-.847	5.679
[Q13a=5.00]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[Q13b=1.00]	-2.708	1.214	4.973	1	.026	-5.088	-.328
[Q13b=2.00]	-3.100	1.283	5.837	1	.016	-5.615	-.585
[Q13b=3.00]	-3.130	1.810	2.991	1	.084	-6.677	.417
[Q13b=4.00]	-2.657	1.369	3.766	1	.052	-5.340	.027
[Q13b=5.00]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[Q13c=1.00]	16.879	4798.249	.000	1	.997	-9387.517	9421.274
[Q13c=2.00]	17.564	4798.249	.000	1	.997	-9386.832	9421.959
[Q13c=3.00]	16.377	4798.249	.000	1	.997	-9388.019	9420.772
[Q13c=4.00]	-3.263	.000	.	1	.	-3.263	-3.263
[Q13c=5.00]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
Link function: Logit.							
a. This parameter is set to zero because it is redundant.							

For the parameter estimates, of financial barriers, these are illustrated and explained. For question on shortage of fund for firm to self-finance international operations, the results are not statistically significant as illustrated by p values of .997 and .147 for the measures. For the strict requirement for credit loan from bank variable, there are mixed results with p values of .026; .016; .084; and 0.052. Only one result in this category is not statistically significant, that is, with a p value of more than 0.05. In a similar vein, lack of government aid to finance international activities variable, the results are not statistically significant as indicated by p values of .997 in all measures apart from one that has failed to produce any result. All other measures have p values that are above 0.05.

For the variable shortage of fund for firm to self-finance international operations, the reference variable is set at measure q13a=5 and has a zero-estimate value. The estimates are then compared to the reference level. The estimates obtained for this variable are -17.923; -18.138; -17.270 and 2.416. This indicates that a lower cumulative score than the reference variable is

more likely for 3 of the measures, whilst a higher cumulative score is likely for only one of the measures. These are mixed results. Similarly, the parameter estimates for strict requirement for credit loan from bank are -2.708; -3.100; -3.130; and -2.657. All these are negative. This indicates that a lower cumulative score is likely as they are all lower than the reference variable. On the contrary, the parameter estimates for lack of government aid to finance international activities are 16.879; 17.564; 16.377, and -3.263. For 3 of the measures, the estimates are positive indicating that a higher cumulative score is likely than the reference variable. Only one measure has a negative estimate indicating that a lower cumulative score than the reference variable is likely. These are mixed results.

Table 4. 69: Test of parallel lines

Test of Parallel Lines				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	Df	Sig.
Null Hypothesis	71.082			
General	58.992 ^b	12.090 ^c	12	.438

The null hypothesis states that the location parameters (slope coefficients) are the same across response categories.

a. Link function: Logit.

b. The log-likelihood value cannot be further increased after maximum number of step-halving.

c. The Chi-Square statistic is computed based on the log-likelihood value of the last iteration of the general model. Validity of the test is uncertain.

Table 4.80 illustrates the test of parallel lines. The intention was to test the assumption of proportional odds. Ordinarily, we would like this to be greater or equal to 0.05. In our case, the p value is 0.438, and this is greater than 0.05. Therefore, the results are consistent with the assumption of parallel lines. This is a good result for the variables under consideration.

4.6 Qualitative Results

Table 4.81 presents the profiles of the firms interviewed in the qualitative part of the study. For example, Case firm 3, 6 and 7 show that they initiated their international business shortly after they were established. The owner of case 6 is into beauty and hair products, such as coconut oil and moisturizing cream. In fact, it emerged that the owner of case 6 stayed and studied in the UK and created networks with local vendors of shops. In this way, case 6 is well networked with the African community in the UK.

Thereafter, the owner moved back to Cameroon to establish an international business so maximise the opportunity. The relationship/connection in the exportation of the products in UK supports the international entrepreneur orientation (which shows case previous international exposure, through residency and work).

Here, knowledge of the UK market was acquired before embarking on producing for export whilst in Cameroon. Case 3 is a partly owned foreign firm and local firm, with established presence in China. The Cameroon partner demonstrated utilised the available human resource capital and the network relationships of the foreign partners in China (Chinese Counterpart). Unlike case 3, all the other cases had to work their way through the internationalisation process. Within these, informants highlighted a few opportunities that can benefit the internationalisation process.

Table 4. 70: Characteristics of firms for qualitative study

Case/Firm	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
Firm Type	M	S	M	M	S	S	M	M	S	S	M	M	S	M	S
Firm Size	300	55	38	31	25	70	101	69	18	40	15	60	30	46	10
Firm Age	25	21	18	24	22	26	13	23	16	23	27	21	25	20	26
Owner-Gender	M	M	F	M	M	M	M	M	F	M	M	M	M	M	M
International Experience	10	5	4	6	2	8	3	10	4	5	6	8	4	9	2

Domestic Before International Activities	7	5	6	3	5	15	4	5	6	10	4	6	8	9	10
First Year of Internationalization	NA	2002	2006	NA	NA	2007	2009	NA	2008	NA	2010	2003	2017	2007	NA
Year of Creation	2000	1997	2000	2012	2001	1999	2005	1998	2002	2005	2005	1997	2015	2006	2004

4.6.1 Partnerships

This is illustrated by the extract below:

My company entered Ivory-coast market as a result of a trade fair that took place in the economic capital of Cameroon, during the trade fair some buyers from the CEMAC market take advantage of the free trade zone and come to the fair, during the fair as we are indulge in the production of steel and clay pots, this company which I will withhold their name, was interested in our produced and as such made a demand which hence we then partner up with them since then to be their supplier through a joint venture. So, I always look forward to such events because the investment is huge and it's worth it.

(Case 14)

Here, there opportunity was identified at a “trade fair”. A partner was identified at this “trade fair”, and this helped the company to embark on the internationalisation journey. Following from this, a relationship was established and formalised for the firms to support each other.

The benefits gained from participating in a trade fair are also illustrated by case 3 in the extract below:

It is prominent to belong in an industrial association, because individually you cannot perform to the best, especially from a poor and corrupt nation like my country Cameroon, to internationalised and participate in trade shows it will take days or months if you venture on your own. Also let me just ask you my dear, do you think one or two firms can successfully organised a trade show here in this country. This is to tell you that the members facilitate the shows abroad and also do well to organise and host shows locally.

(Case, 3)

This illustrates that being a member of an industrial association is an important factor and an incident that triggers the initiation of internationalisation of SMEs behaviour. In this sense, international trade shows emerge as an opportunity to engage in international business

activities. In fact, “*it will take days or months if you venture on your own*”, and trade shows help to ease the process.

4.6.2 Lasting relationships

Though the foreign market orientation is good, note should be taken that firms need to established constant relationships and trust to their foreign partners and clients. This is illustrated by the extract below:

I will like to emphasize that, even though my orders are from morocco, I always visit Morocco every 6 months to make sure that the established relationships have built stay strong with increase trust with the shop owners that I supply to.

(Case, 6)

The above quote also indicates the efforts that firms go through to explore international business opportunities. Exposure to the international markets is important. Lasting relationships can also be created within the educational environment, and later translate into business partnerships as illustrated by the extract below:

While I was studying in UK, I sported potentials in the business I want to invest in, which in agriculture and food processes. During one our lectures, I made known my plans to few of my classmates from China, one of them was interested as His family were already into importing banana from Africa. So, he knew the international trait drill already. Upon graduation I partnered up with him, he became my investor and also, I am in this business today because of the network I created with him.

(Case, 9)

Thus, whilst students go to other countries for educational purposes, there are opportunities to meet other international students and others with an entrepreneurial mind-set. For instance, case states that “*during one our lectures, I made known my plans to few of my classmates from China, one of them were interested as His family were already into importing banana from Africa. So, he knew the international trait drill already*”. These are opportunities that are often taken for granted.

4.6.3 Family ties

It also emerged that contacts from friends, and family that live abroad is an important resource within the internationalisation process. From the respondent cases, the effect of networking with friends and members of the family is an international trigger. This is illustrated by the extract below:

During a visit to London, on my sister's wedding in 2017 i met the highlight of my business as I sold lots and have constantly been supplying since then, in my case I took the opportunity and told my sister that I will be doing some business, so she made an avenue where I met her friends in their monthly meetings and also church members, during which I shared flies and lift-let showcasing my design as I am in a fashion designer.

(Case, 14)

For case 14, the opportunity arose “*during a visit to London*”. In fact, it was a “*sister's wedding in 2017*”. This visit created opportunities to share business idea with “*friends*”, “*church members*”, and so forth. This opportunity was used to test the products in a foreign market.

4.6.4 Skilled workforce

Another important resource in the internationalisation process is the availability of a skilled workforce to help cope with the rising demand. This is illustrated by the extract below:

As you saw during our induction process, most of the employees you saw are the permanent full-time staffs, but during high demands I get temporary employments, this is because Paye (Cameroon in French) is low in machineries and technology as compared to other markets like China, India, and so on, most of the work here is done through rigours intensive labour, so it's important to get the numbers so to export the products

(Case, 3)

The above quote explains two significance points; the literature elaborates and confirms the constructive relationship between international propensity and size of the firm which is a fixed cost factor related to international business. For case 3, and many others, are “low in machineries and technology as compared to other markets like China, India, and so on”. This

indicates that there are challenges within this area, and a skilled workforce to engage in manual operations is needed. Hence, “*it’s important to get the numbers so to export the products*”. Here, “*the numbers*” refers to the labour force. This labour force must be skilled so that they can undertake the required tasks. Further, there is an opportunity to introduce machinery in the production process to help increase outputs.

Skilled workers are equally an important aspect of incident that is critical to stimulate internationalisation. This is illustrated by case 15 in the extract below:

When I initially started my business it was of a small scale, so I had a garage that I turned into my factory space, in the cause of years my production was just internal, as I am into production of retail consumer goods like, biscuits, snacks just to mention a few. But when my product gained popularity not only in Cameroon but in central Africa, I had to increase my workspace, and work force, so lease a factory. You saw for yourself when you came in right

(Case, 15)

As demand for the products increased, case 15 had to increase the “*workforce*”. This workforce had to be trained so that they can produce goods that are suitable for the international market. Not only was there an increase in the workforce, but the “*workspace*” had to be increased. These are important resources needed for international activities.

4.6.5 Risk behaviour

It emerged that internationalisation activities needs a propensity to undertake some risk. This is illustrated by the extract below:

To be involved in international transactions in (Cameroon) you have to be a high-risk taker. The demands from the buyers need funding as well as paying for labour so it’s not an easy thing my dear. See in this factory, we used to operate lots of us, as we rent the factory space to process our consumer retail goods. Opposite me, you can see the cup-webs, its shot down, because the owner there, produces health and beauty products she faces a challenge last month where she loans money and couldn’t pay. My sister let me tell you this industry and our country there is too much “Long-Throat” before your good cross and enter Nigeria, you have pay bribe upon bribe. Anyhow though, because

*I am committed to my clients and don't want to lose them, I do my best to satisfy them,
I take the risks and I know one day it will be better*

(Case, 12)

Risks involved can be financial risks. Access to cheap finance is a challenge, and times, if things do not go right, it becomes difficult to pay the “*loan money*”. There are also risks associated with bribery because “*you have to pay bribe upon bribe*”. This is common when business is sought in “*Nigeria*”. There is also the risk of raising the financial resources to pay “*for labour*”.

4.7 Summary of the Chapter

This chapter has presented the results of the study. It started with the reliability analysis, and results revealed varied reliability measurement for the research constructs, that is, when viewed as individual items. However, when all the research items are grouped together, a higher level of reliability was obtained. This suggests that the research constructs must not be viewed in isolation. The survey results unveil different interaction patterns between the research constructs. The next chapter discusses the results.

CHAPTER FIVE: DISCUSSION

5.0 Introduction

This chapter discusses the results of the study. It compares insights that emerge from the study to the existing literature. In doing this, the study also highlights the contributory elements of the study as the results are positioned within gaps in knowledge. Insights are drawn from both the quantitative and qualitative data sets and discussed within the context of the knowledge gaps identified in chapter 2.

5.1 The road to internationalisation

It emerged that firms in Cameroon manufacturing sectors have been involved in internationalisation activities for many years. Their main activities have been through exportation. One firm had been exporting since 1995. This is over 24 years' experience in exportation. The literature also reveals similar experiences regarding the internationalisation of SMEs in Vietnam and USA, where firms have vast experience of over 22years and 26years, respectively. Further, it was found that the overall size of the firms in respect to the workforce available was 300 with over 26 years of creation. This workforce is the combined total of SMEs in this study and indicates that Cameroon's manufacturing sector has many small and medium enterprises. It emerged that because of a small workforce, most firms are locally focused rather than internationally, further the size of the firm explains the low international propensity behaviour. This was interpreted as a missed opportunity to recruit a workforce that can help to increase production and produce for the export market.

The literature suggests that period for a firm to internationalise after creation is normally within 5 years of creation (Amato & Amato, 2007) Here, the assumption is that no firm can produce directly for export from the onset. Contrary to the literature, it was found that there is some SMEs start by exporting directly. It also emerged that most firms in developed economies internationalise much quicker than SMEs from Cameroon. This is a result of invisible trade barriers such as the need to meet certain international standards. This makes the playing field uneven for the Cameroonian SMEs, and acts as a barrier to the internationalisation activities.

For instance, case firms 3, 6 and 7 started their international business activities shortly after their formation. This could be because of the nature of the business activity. For example, the owner of case 6 is into beauty and hair products such as coconut oil, moisturizing cream, and the like. The owner studied in the UK and created networks with local shop owners. These networks were strong within the African community. After studying, the owner returned to Cameroon to establish an international business. In this sense, internationalisation started much earlier than reported in the literature. Within the literature, this is an international entrepreneur orientation that was enhanced by previous international exposure (Hall and Cook, 2009). In this sense, that international knowledge is a resource that was used for internationalisation. Hence, the acquired knowledge of international activity as emerged in this study is a resource that can be used to gain an early entry into international markets.

It also emerged that the road to internationalisation may also involve partnerships. For instance, Case 3 is a partly owned foreign firm and local firm, with established presence in China. The partnership was forged within the educational settings, as students. Further, among the 16 companies, only one firm was co-owned by a Chinese and Cameroonian. This demonstrates that the internationalization journey can be achieved through different avenues. Of importance are the connections established as students, conference delegates, weddings, and so forth.

These networks emerge as important resources for internationalisation. And yet, there is a silence in the literature about these important activities that take place as part of daily life.

5.2 Ties that Bind: trigger for internationalisation

The results reveal that there are some events that trigger the internationalisation process for SMEs. One of the crucial events that encourage SMEs to internationalise are trade fairs. The trade fair is interpreted as an external stimulus that creates opportunities for SMEs to engage in international business activities. This is a proactive incident. Respondents explained that they often engage in the Grand National trade fair that usually take place in Cameroon. It is here, that the international business opportunities were identified. Although the trade fair is not an instant credit and cash transaction, it serves as a forum for foreign contacts and subsequent arrangement for export orders and international partnerships through joint ventures.

The literature suggests that trade fairs are an important networking event for international businesses (Gao, 2004; Zahra, 2005; Aldrich, et al., 2006). Similarly, insights from the study are consistent with the contingency theory (Williams, 1979; Terjesen, et al., 2013). In this sense, the trade fair must be viewed as a networking opportunity, and as a resource that can help to trigger the mindset to engage with international business activities. Consistent with the network theory (Suresh & Ramraj, 2012), trade fairs provide the platform to establish international partnerships. Additionally, the series of events that took place at the trade fair, demonstrated that it is important to have networks. These networks stimulate the international behaviour of a firm.

The results also reveal that industrial associations provide an opportunity for SMEs to participate in various networking events. It emerged that Cameroon's trade associations include Alucam, group Teboh Enterprise, Cameroon Chamber of Commerce, international federation of Cameroonian exporters, food, and agriculture trade association, among others. These provide networking opportunities for SMEs. Participants to the qualitative study narrated their

engagement with a trade association. For instance, respondent case 2 pointed out that the courage and support provided by members from the association within the textiles industry encouraged her to engage in international business activities.

It also emerges that international orientation is because of firm's owner or manager. This is grounded in the owner or manager's previous exposure to the international environment. For example, others are exposed to the international environment through studies, whilst others attend family events such as weddings. These are opportunities for the SME owners or managers to develop an interest for international business activities. For example, one of the respondents was a student at a university in South Africa. She used foreign contacts created whilst at university to start her business in manufacturing of moisturising lotion.

The literature suggests that these relational ties help to trigger international business activities (Ruzzier & Antoncic, 2007) The RBV theory also considers SMEs owner/managerial behaviour in international orientation as a stimulating factor for internationalisation (Barney & Arikan, 2001; Ahmad & Kitchen, 2008). From these findings, we see the interaction of the network, RBV, and internationalisation theories.

5.3 Factors that Enabled SMEs International Demands

Comprehending to specifics on the proposed integrated frameworks and how it impacts firms' level to meet international demands is presented in the subsequent discussion.

5.3.1 Stage Theory

Despite the criticisms on the stage model (Oliveira, 2006; Williamson, 2008; Cook and Hall, 2009), the view that the size of the firm and the previous experience in the internal market that shape the business for international propensity is tested. The qualitative results revealed that the brewery and consumer retail manufacturing companies engage in mass production, producing different lines of products. This provides them with the opportunity to full time workers because of continuity in business. Respondents pointed out that to fulfil the

international orders by a stipulated period, there is need for simultaneous involvement of many factory workers. These workers must be trained. However, a lack of machinery and technical equipment means that production methods used in Cameroon are labour intensive.

For large firms, the need for a larger workforce size to meet the international export demands is a critical incident. The literature suggests that the constructive relationship between international propensity and size of the firm which is a fixed cost factor related to international business (Hall and Tu, 2004; Coad and Rao, 2010). For instance, Williamson (2008) pointed out that the size of a firm is important for internationalisation. The assumption is that a large firm has more workers with a different skill set. These skills are important for mass production industry. On the contrary, we find that with technological developments, firms can use machinery with a relatively smaller size of workforce, and yet, still produce for a niche international market.

Previous experienced in the domestic market is another essential factor that influences the internationalisation of SMEs in Cameroon. Some of the firms in the country have been long standing since their creation before they engaged in international activities. This enabled a better understanding on the Cameroonian business surroundings and how it operates. For instance, in the qualitative part of the study, respondent case, 1, 2, 7, 13, and 14 created business bonding with government agencies. These tied helped the companies to adapt and prepare themselves for the challenges within the international markets. As they internationalised, they were supported and guided by the government agencies. This domestic market experience is aligned with the stage theory (Hall and Tu, 2004). However, contrary to the stage theory, some firms were driven by demands from the external market and did not need to build any experience in the domestic market. The strength of their internationalisation was grounded in their networks. The ranking of the stage theory factors is as illustrated in table 5.1.

Table 5. 1: Rank order of the stage theory factors

Stage theory factor	Frequency Total= 16	Frequency Rate (%)	Rank
Size of the Firm	14	94%	1
Previous internal market experience	10	82%	2
International demands (via network contact)	4	24%	3

Source: synthesised from the interviewed cases

5.3.2 The Resource Based View Theory

International demands cannot be met without certain facilities (Barney, 2011). The resource-based view theory outlines some factors that influence international growth. The table below illustrates the important factors associated with the RBV model, and their differences will be subsequently analysed in relation to findings from the interview transcripts.

Table 5. 1: Rank order of the RBV variables

RBV factors	Frequency Total=16	Frequency Rate (%)	Rank
Number of workers	14	96%	2
International ownership	2	8%	5
Factory facilities and equipment's	16	100%	1
Financial resource	16	100%	1
Human resource and incentive	4	12%	4
Expert/skilled manufacturers	12	92%	3

Source: synthesized from interview cases

It emerges that finance is a crucial factor within the resource-based view perspective. In fact, machinery and equipment are vital resources to engage in manufacturing. Some interviewees revealed the difficulties they face with international orders. For instance, the buyers sometimes only support them with 25% of the entire production cost, the rest of the production is for the manufacturers. This support is required to capacitate the manufacture with the working capital to produce the required products. These financial resources are needed to help meet the demand. Also, the machinery must be available and in good condition for production to take

place. Equipment such as sewing machines, metal machines, and food processing equipment are a resource that can help to enhance production. In fact, equipment is essential to help produce goods that meet international standards.

Another factor that is highly ranked is the human capital. Skilled workers are equally classified under 4th as important aspects of incident that is critical to stimulate internationalisation. The human capital is required for the hands-on tasks. This is an important asset for the organisation, and yet, it is ranked 4th. It also emerges that some firms operated from the home environment, within small spaces, and yet, they produced for the international market. Yet, the literature depicts larger spaces with appropriate structures and facilities as resources that are needed for international expansion (Hall and Tu, 2004).

5.4.3 International Entrepreneurial Factor

Under the entrepreneurship theory, there are several factors facilitating the internationalisation process of firms. These include the following: 1) be internationally orientated, 2) have international business vision and international strategy, 3) have risk takers behaviour, and 4) have a positive perception on the international host market. The ranking of the above factors is as illustrated in table 5.3.

Table 5. 2: Rank order of influential entrepreneur factors

International Entrepreneurship Factors	Frequency Total=16	Frequency Rate (%)	Rank
Internationally oriented	4	12%	3
have international business vision and international initiation	10	88%	2
Have risk takers behaviour	16	100	1
Have a positive perception on the international host market.	10	88%	2

Source: Synthesised from interview cases

Amongst the factors, the vision to commence international business, having a positive perception about the host market, risk-taking behaviour, background about the international market, being internationally oriented are very crucial themes that emerged from the findings. Some of them went further to explain that at the start of their businesses, having the passion to enter the international market was an important goal for them. However, most of the firms had limited strategy. Their international strategies were not documented, but whatever they had in their minds about internationalisation, was effectively executed. This is contrary to the literature that draws our attention to well documented international market entry strategies (Oviatt & McDougall, 2005; Eisenhardt & Santos, 2002; Ruzzier & Antoncic, 2007). Some of these SMEs had no time and resources to produce written plans but had the audacity to enact their visions.

The literature suggests that antecedents of international entrepreneurial behaviour that includes risks (Dimitratos & Plakoyiannaki, 2003; Zhang, et al., 2009). Consistent with the literature, most of the respondents from the interview complained about the risks they face during their international transactions. It emerged that there is a perception in the international business arena that Africa is susceptible to corrupt business practices. This was a detriment to getting investment. Hence, raising start-up capital was a challenge, and a lot of firms had to rely on their own personal savings. It also emerged that risk-taking behaviour was perceived as essential by the respondents.

In terms of positive perception when it comes to international markets and its advantages, every firm in the interviewed had a positive perception on this. They all believed that international expansion even though it has barriers and challenges, has positive attractions that will encourage international business. Such perception is drawn from the enhancement of the company's growth and development, platform to expand and build partnership through

networking, increase the company’s revenue, market shares, and get the company to adopt internationally acceptable standards. The literature suggests the benefit of being internationally oriented and have an opened mind comes with lots of benefits but not limited to financial ones (Zheng *et al.*, 2009). Other important goals include creating relationships by meeting people through international activities.

5.4.4 Network Factor

There are three main factors that emerged from the study, which include 1) relationship through family and friends, 2) relationship creation through other business partners, and 3) network creation from industrial association. The ranking is as illustrated in table 6.4.

Table 5. 3: Rank order of network factors for internationalisation

Network connections	Frequency Total=16	Frequency Rate (%)	Rank
Relationship with industrial association	14	94%	1
Relationship connection through friends and family	8	50%	2
Relationship connections with business partners	4	25%	3

Source: synthesised from interviewed cases

The literature suggests that industrial association play a vital role as an internationalisation stimulus (Johanson & Vahlne, 2006). Others suggest that most networks are created from people joining trade unions and associations (Hutchinson, et al., 2009).

Through the business association from the industry union, some of the firms were able to get support to meet the cost for producing products that are required for the export market. For instance, some of the funds were gathered through their local “*jangi*”. These are meetings where they make monthly contributions. These collections are then used to support a member of the association when the need arises. This support is in the form of a loan accessible to members. These loans are less stringent than those provided through the traditional bank lending models. In fact, membership of the associations does not only provide a sense of

belonging, but also acts an opportunity of recognition. These associations were used by respondents as resources to obtain loans from the World Bank and Eco-bank, as illustrated by respondent cases, 2, 3.8, 9, 14 and 15.

Most of the companies interviewed agreed that they build capacity through programmes that were provided by the industry association. Programmes that were beneficial in boosting their abilities included: international skills such as market planning, international strategy organization, business knowledge, monetary planning. These training programmes were organised within a set period as a compliment for belonging in the industry union. As such the abilities enhanced their international process with knowledge on what to expect in the host market.

Another important relationship is built through connection with other business partners. During trade fair these manufacturers created business network. Others drew from their experiences of living and studying abroad. During this period, the entrepreneurs create bonds with partners that they see as potential business connections. The network creates an opening for market entry through franchising and joint ventures.

Rather than adopt a model of receiving aid, the respondents proved that they could engage in business as equal partners. Yet, the literature suggests that firms internationalise through their own efforts or receive aid from other partners (Johanson & Vahlne et al, 2009). From the findings, we learn that networking must be a proactive approach.

It was found that family and friends also influenced the process of international business, the connection that an entrepreneur has with a family or friend living abroad is another reason that triggers internationalisation. This connection is a resource that gives the entrepreneur a sense of trust in dealing with their business. It also reduces the cost of having to travel to find potential

buyers. For example, in the qualitative study, case 7 explained that his engagement in international business was through his brother. Case 7 manufacturer shoes. These include slippers that are handmade. His brother visited and he gave him a gift, so when his brother went back to France, he has been receiving positive response to his shoes, thereby triggering the idea to produce for the export market. It is stories like these that remain unreported in most accounts of internationalisation of SMEs. And yet, stories like these have seen the growth of many export-oriented SMEs.

5.5 Perception of internationalisation barriers

Part two of the empirical research demonstrated the events that triggered the international behaviour of SMEs to attained international demands. Therefore, this portion of the study seeks to explain the firms that choose to be entirely domestic in their business and the factors that prevented them from internationalising.

The findings reveal the barriers for internationalisation as: (1) lack of finance to support international business , (2) availability of potential growth in domestic market, (3) the small size of the firm, (4) lack of appropriate infrastructures and machinery, (5) high competitiveness in the international market, (6) lack of long term business ambition, (7) little or no governmental support, (8) inexperienced and unskilled workers, and, (10) lack of international presence or networks. Three most influential factors were identified as: (1) the size of the firm, (2) lack of finance to fund international demands, and (3) inadequate machinery and infrastructure.

The identified perceived barriers are consistent with the stage theory (Johanson & Vahlne, 2011), and the resource-based view model (Barney, 2002). These frameworks suggest that to embarked on international business, the firm must overcome market barriers that hinders internationalisation (O'Farrell, et al., 1994; Westhead & Wright, 2001). The lack of funding to

satisfy international orders, and lack of working capital emerged as barriers that prevent firms from engaging with the external market.

The work capital barriers perceived are consistent with previous studies in this area (Ibeh, 2003; Decker & Zhao, 2004). However, the difficulty in financing international business is not only limited to developing markets, it is a global issue. For instance, (Leonidou, 2004) conducted research of 32 SMEs internationalisation barriers in USA. Similarly, (Caves, 1971; Abor & Harvey, 2008) focused on SME internationalisation barriers in New Zealand. However, in Cameroon, SMEs financial barriers are significant because of the country's stage of economic development. This is much different from more developed economies such as Europe, China, and North America, where there are established institutions to support the internationalisation of SMEs.

Inadequate infrastructure and appropriate machinery posed as a threat to enter a new market. This barrier has a connection with the financial barrier in different areas such as spinning and weaving in the textile industry, in the food processing sector, and the like. However, this barrier was likely not concentrated as an evident of international barriers in the literature (Johanson & Vahlne, 2011; Westhead et al, 2001), this was because majority of the studies carried out were done in the developed markets. Here, they produce in large scale and bound to have the necessary equipment. This is unlike SMEs in Cameroon.

Another negating factor that restricted international expansion is the prospects of perceived barriers of the unknown problems they might encounter in the international market. Most non-international SMEs are hesitant to venture into international markets. The negative perceived barrier include: (1) limited knowledge to identify potential in the international market, (2) the excessive competitive threat in the international market, (3) the high rate of corruption in Cameroon, (4) the massive cost of investment involved in international business, and (5)

unfavourable governmental policy in Cameroon. However, the most impacting perceived barriers among the above were the cost to invest, the competitive nature, corruption, and bureaucracy in the business environment.

Another perceived barrier is the lack of governmental policy and incentives to engage firm's internationalisation process. Some of the case companies including the internationalized firms (1, 3, 5, 7, 15, and 16) revealed that there are no incentives provided to them by the government and no policy set in place to support them. They are limited in many areas (e.g. financially, inadequate infrastructures, machinery, and training) that can help boost their business and get them to level as their counterparts that internationalised.

Another important barrier that is perceived by domestic firms when it comes to international process is the in-experienced and low skilled full-time workers they have. One of the case companies said the lack of skilled employees limit their confidence to expand across borders. Also, another entrepreneur pointed out that without international exposure, they have limited knowledge of the international market.

Industrialisation in Cameroon could be on its low state due to the failed educational system. Consistent with the literature, a lack of skilled workers makes domestic firms hesitant to venture into the international arena (Lorenzen & Mudambi, 2013; Oliviera, 2006). Similarly, (Hutchison et al, 2009; Lenidou, (2004) who are of the view that firms lack international visions. This could be a result of a lack of skills. In a similar vein, within international entrepreneurship, (McDougall, 2007) suggests that owner-managers lack the qualities and experience to operate in international market.

5.5.1 General analysis from qualitative study

Regarding the research literature of the current study, there were five proposed integrated theoretical concepts that explore the critical events that influence the internationalisation process. The contingency theory is the most crucial of them all. The external environment was

the main influence for firms to initiate in international business. The study developed themes that classified as the critical incidents of firm's external business behaviour. Through business association (trade fairs, and industry association), another theme was connection through international orientation and relations also extended from friends and family members. The themes mentioned are directly linked to the network theory (Coviello & Munro, 2004; McAuley, 2010).

The research found out that amongst the 16 interviewees, 10 of them confirm that the international entrepreneurship theory prompted international movements of business abroad. This is linked to the micro-environment in a very technical way. The influence from critical incident through international orientation, network work through families and friends, international experience are all external factors connected to the social aspect in business.

5.5.2 General analysis from quantitative study

The lack of government incentives came up as a perceived barrier which is consistent with the resource-based view, and the stage theory as a determinant factor of international activities. Yet, the results revealed that in Cameroon, SMEs receive very little or no governmental incentives. In this case, the models must be revised to focus on other support mechanisms such as industry associations. This will better inform theoretical understandings of internationalisation processes within the Cameroonian environment.

Additionally, the contingency theory highlights issues surrounding meticulous planning, as a resource that can be used for international growth (Johanson & Vahlne, 2011; Westhead & Wright, 2001). And yet, the results reveal that some of the SMEs internationalised without even a written plan. The international entrepreneurship literature suggests that a firm's international behaviour is complex, and the business owners need to create certain networks. These

networks, supposedly, must be experienced in the international market to be able to catapult their business across nations. This view was consistent with the findings of the current study.

The survey results revealed that factors that hindered internationalisation of SMEs include, corruption (58%), tax and international tariff cost (50.5%), access to loans (38%), administrative bureaucracies (34%), competition in the international market (30%), inadequate infrastructures (20%). Other barrier to international business includes lack of ties between the public and private sectors, shortage of electricity, no or very low internet competency, transport, and communication shortages.

Further, the correlational analysis revealed a significant and positive relationship between knowledge and human resource barriers ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient =.354*); knowledge and product barriers ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient =.333*), knowledge and bureaucratic barriers ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient =.354), knowledge and exogenous barriers ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient = .334), as well as knowledge and general factors ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient=.700*). All the significant relationships were positive, and all were at the 0.01 level, 2 tailed. However, the relationship between knowledge, financial barriers, and the domestic market factors was not significant.

These findings suggest that the perceived barriers and the actual barriers that hinder international process of SMEs are multi-pronged and requires an integrated theoretical approach to fully comprehend. Then the external environmental barriers, that included the taxation or legal factors, the economic and political issues faced in the country, couple with other exogenous barriers to international process (Hutchison et al, 2007) must also be taken seriously.

5.6 Summary of the Chapter

In summary, the study can affirm that the findings of the constraint from both international firms and non-international firms can be compared and counteracted simultaneously. To comprehend the study, the factors that influenced the internationalisation of SMEs in Cameroon from the critical incidents structured and analysed in the part two of the empirical research influenced the capacity of these firms to be able to identify international opportunities. It emerged that the SMEs also rely on understandings that are not documented in the literature as resources for internationalisation. Following from this, a theoretical framework was developed that could help to capture the internationalisation resources that have not been accounted for in the literature. Such resources can help other SMEs in other developing economies other than Cameroon, to embark on the internationalisation journey. The next chapter draws conclusions, presents contributions, and recommendations.

CHAPTER SIX: CONCLUSIONS, CONTRIBUTIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Introduction

This chapter summarises the findings from of the study. This is achieved by revisiting the each of the research objectives and then outlining the evidence in support of achieving the stated objectives. The chapter then focuses on outlining the contributions of the study. These are divided into three areas, that is, theoretical, methodological, and managerial contributions. Practical and actionable recommendations that are informed by the findings are then made. Finally, research limitations are acknowledged, and suggestions for future researchers also outlined.

6.2 Summary and Main Conclusions

This section presents the summary of the research.

6.2.1 Summary of the Research

The study determined the challenges of the internationalization process of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) within the context of Cameroon and developed some guidelines that can help SMEs to internationalise their products and services. The conclusion reached is that all the international barriers probed in the study affects the international competitiveness of the firms. However, the strength of the perceived international barriers' impact is not the same. It was found that the main international barriers affecting the international competitiveness of SME's in Cameroon is internal (human resource, marketing knowledge and information, financial, product quality and product adaptation barriers) and external (government policy and exogenous international barriers, logistics, competition) forces.

The government accounts for just 14.07% of supplies made to industry segments. This affects the firms in the industry sectors with a majority being below 10 years to compete effectively and expand internationally. This is because government supplies will be less stringent and come as a form of aid than supplies from other market participants in the private sector. There is also limited government aid to finance international activities. Also, poor international promotion program with the government not setting up the adequate systems locally with which firms operating in the various industries can leverage to expand internationally. Bureaucratic barriers and a lack of finance are also of concern. Infrastructure such as the internet, telephone, power supply, and transport networks are of concern. This affects the performance of internationalising firms.

Human resource barriers affect the ability for firms to expand internationally. Developing countries like Cameroon have a comparative advantage in labour cost. However, the quality and availability of a skilled experienced and qualified labour force remains a problem. Another issue is that of the inflation rate. This has been rising since the year 2011 and has caused an increase in the cost of living. Also, the firms provide short term contracts of no more than six

months. This allows the labour force to effectively work as freelance, affecting the firm's ability to build a solid work force required to expand internationally. This finding is consistent with the literature in that limited skilled labour, difficulties in hiring specialised personnel, and a lack of adequate managerial capital (Hutchison *et al*, 2007; Moene, 2000; Oliviera, 2006; William, 2008), are obstacles to the internationalisation of SMEs.

As regards product quality and adaptation barriers, the main problem with poor product qualities are, lack of advanced machinery, lack of quality raw materials, and lack of skilled and specialized manpower. The goods imported are often from large corporations with international experience benefitting from economies of scale. As such local manufacturers find it difficult competing locally and fewer manage to expand internationally. In the international markets, there are established enterprises with more advanced machinery, and better product quality achieved through automation. This affects the ability of SMEs from Cameroon to compete in the international market. It emerged that there is a lack of knowledge to identify foreign market opportunities. There is also a lack of pricing information, and another related knowledge.

Financial barriers are of high importance because of inadequate government support and shortage of investment by the firms operating in the various segments. Respondents observed that there's difficulty with getting investment from banks to expand. Yet, financial investment is a key resource required for internationalisation. Further, there is limited government aid or support. High cost of capital is an obstacle to the internationalisation of SMEs. Though the government in Cameroon supports the growth of micro finance institutions, to support SME's, the funds are still not accessible to many small enterprises.

Exogenous barriers have been identified as significant in this research. Cameroon does not have a developed national airline carrier. As such, companies cannot benefit from the airline cargo transportation. International carriers charge premium prices, and this limits the ability of

SMEs to expand internationally. Another problem is lack of advanced technological machinery. Most of the machinery are imported from Europe or China. This is very expensive for the SMEs because they lack the required funding. Further, there are limited skills to operate these technologically advanced machineries.

6.2.2.1 Objective number one

The first objective was “*to critically review the literature on the internationalisation process of SMEs and identify gaps in knowledge*”. This was designed to identify gaps in knowledge, and to evaluate existing theoretical understandings within the internationalisation of SMEs literature. After evaluating the literature, a conceptual framework was developed, as illustrated in chapter 2. This helped to clearly identify gaps in the stage theory, resource-based view theory, and network theory. The critical analysis led to the development of new understandings of these theoretical frameworks. This objective was achieved through the critical literature review in chapter 2 of the thesis.

6.2.2.2 Objective number two

The second objective was, “*to ascertain the perceptions of managers on internationalisation, and how these perceptions impact on the internationalisation process of SMEs in Cameroon*”. Perceptions of managers on internationalisation process of SMEs in Cameroon varied amongst the survey respondents. For example, respondents were presented with a statement that “there is existing international opportunity” for their companies. Only 9.82% of the respondents strongly agreed, whilst 15.18% agreed. Those neutral to the statement were 11.61%. Many of the respondents (33.04%) disagreed that there is an existing international opportunity, whilst 30.36% strongly disagreed. Respondents were also asked to describe the internationalisation speed of their company. Most of the respondents (75.89%) indicated that the internationalisation speed was slow. This was followed by 14.29% of the respondents who indicated that it was medium. Finally, 9.82% of the respondents indicated that the internationalisation speed was high or rapid. Respondents also acknowledge barriers within the internationalisation process in Cameroon, and that these impact on the internationalisation process.

Respondents were also asked to identify a factor that described their company’s process of international expansion, or a process that they would use. The majority (44.64%) indicated

international entrepreneurship. This was followed by 22.32% who highlighted the network or relationship model. Further, 16.96% indicated the born global policy. Additionally, 8.93% suggested the transaction cost approach. Only 7.14% indicated the Uppsala model of internationalisation. Hence, this objective was achieved.

6.2.2.3 Objective number three

The third objective was, “*to determine the internal and external factors that affect the internationalisation of SMEs*”. The results on general factors of influence. In this category, respondents agreed with all the evaluative statements as illustrated by Political legal factors (84.8%); cultural factors (84.8%); competitive advantage (58%); firm’s level of technology (73.2%); distribution structure (13.4%); size of the firm (70.6%); age of the firm (14.3%); cultural similarities (81.2%); market similarities (82.2%); international relationship or network (83%); entrepreneurial or managerial expertise (74.1%); and environmental awareness (60.7%).

Barriers to internationalization were also identified, and their interaction ascertained. For example, a spearman correlation analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between the research constructs. A significant and positive relationship was found between knowledge and human resource barriers ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient =.354*); knowledge and product barriers ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient =.333*), knowledge and bureaucratic barriers ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient =.354), knowledge and exogeneous barriers ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient = .334), as well as knowledge and general factors ($p=.000$, correlation coefficient=.700*). All the significant relationships were positive, and all were at the 0.01 level, 2 tailed. However, the relationship between knowledge, financial barriers, and the domestic market factors was not significant. Considering the evidence summarised above, this research has achieved the third objective.

6.2.2.4 Objective number four

The fifth objective was designed “*to develop guidelines and recommendations that can help SMEs in Cameroon to overcome the challenges identified and internationalise their activities?*”. The intention was to provide practical recommendations that can help managers to overcome some of the challenges that they encounter in the internationalisation process of SMEs. This objective was met in part, by insights that emerged from the qualitative study.

Respondents revealed some suggestions that helped to inform managerial recommendations and guidelines. The guidelines were also enhanced by insights from the survey, as well as the literature. Further, an integrated theoretical framework was developed, and this could help managers enhance their chances of success when they engage with the internationalisation process. Considering the evidence summarised above, this research has achieved the fourth objective.

6.3 Contributions of the Research

This research makes specific contributions to theoretical debates, methodological debates, and managerial practice.

6.3.1 Theoretical Contributions

Although, literature from previous research has addressed the groundwork factors pattern to international theories and barring components. Few studies have been conducted in emergent markets. The focus has been on Asia, Europe, and North America. The study contributes to the development of an integrated theoretical framework that will help to address internationalisation issues within Cameroon, and other less developed countries. It emerges that the issue of context has often been relegated to a category of secondary theoretical interest (Crick & Jones, 2000; Coviello & Cox, 2006), and yet, it is these contextual understandings that have helped the internationalisation process amongst SMEs in Cameroon. In this sense, internationalization phenomenal cannot be evaluated using a single conceptual framework.

Apparently, to the best of my knowledge, this is the first study to examine the internationalisation barriers encountered by SMEs in Cameroon within the manufacturing industry. The study contributes to the literature surrounding the internationalisation of SMEs from Cameroon. This will provide insights for those firms seeking to enhance their competitiveness in the international arena.

6.3.1.1 Rethinking the resource-based view theory

Although, small firms in this study experienced a shortage of products and resources, they were able to internationalise. Despite the challenges faced in terms of a lack of knowledge, human

resources, financial, product, bureaucratic, and exogenous barriers, these firms were able to internationalise. And yet, if we follow the resource-based view theoretically and religiously, the SMEs in Cameroon would not have internationalised because of the identified barriers. One limitation is that the assumptions of the resource-based view are static, and yet the business environment evolves. Therefore, there are some contextual factors that helped these SMEs to internationalise. Yet, such factors are not accounted for within the resource-based view.

6.3.1.2 Rethinking the stage theory

The study contributes to a better understanding of the stage theory (Cavusgil, 2004; Koe, 2013; Kumar, 2012). The literature suggests that firms enter the international market with little or low commitment from the starting phase, and the strategies that influences this model of entry is the direct export mode of expansion (Acedo & Jones, 2007). Yet, the results reveal the propensity of SMEs to engage in international markets from their inception, thus ignoring the domestic market and pay attention to the global market. In this sense, the stage theory fails to predict the behaviour of some SMEs within this study. Therefore, there is a need to rethink the stage theory to accommodate internationalisation possibilities as emergent from this study.

6.3.1.3 Rethinking the theories of internationalisation

The study contributes to a contextual understanding of the internationalisation of SMEs. The literature depicts a well-documented international strategy of the firm (Baum, et al., 2011; Peng, et al., 2008). Yet, the results reveal that some SMEs did not have anything written to engage in international business. They seized the opportunity and progressed with their activities. It also emerged that these SMEs had limited skills and maintained a very small workforce. As such, documenting their international strategy was not of priority. Yet, they ventured into the international markets successfully. In this sense, there is a need to revisit the internationalisation theories, and include the contextual issues within the internationalising firm's countries. Here, the internationalisation experiences of American SMEs may be different from those of Cameroonian SMEs because of contextual factors. Yet, the literature on internationalisation is predominantly informed by scholars from more developed economies (Wright, et al., 2007). There is thus a dearth of studies on the internationalisation of SMEs from developing economies. Hence, this study contributes to understandings within this domain.

6.3.2 Methodological Contributions

Methodologically, the thesis uses mixed methods, a phenomenon that is gaining increasing importance in social research (Bell, et al., 2003). A lot of studies in this area have used mono methods, relying on a single data set. In fact, mono methods ignore the richness of gaining insights from multiple points of view. By conducting a survey of 112 firms and drawing insights from 16 firms in the qualitative study, the study unveils internationalisation understandings that have often been relegated to a category of secondary theoretical interest. This helps to view the same phenomena from different directions. Further, it contributes to our understanding of triangulation of data collection methods. In this sense, the study adds voice to the importance of triangulation. This helped to obtain critical insights about the internationalisation of SMEs in Cameroon. Therefore, future research in this area can draw insight from the methodological approach of this study and bring further understandings on how to overcome barriers in the internationalisation process by the SMEs.

6.3.3 Managerial Contributions

The findings of this study offer valuable insights into the challenges of the internationalization process of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) within the context of Cameroon. This section outlines some managerial contributions that can help SMEs to internationalise their products and services.

6.3.3.1 Cultivate an entrepreneurial mind-set

As a result of internationalization of manufacturers in Cameroon the sector is high labour intensive, and this affects the production levels. There is a need for domestic firms to use their profits to help train their staff. There is also a need for managers to adopt an entrepreneurial mind-set and take calculated risks to venture into the international markets. In other words, the managerial mind-set must be creative, innovative, and entrepreneurial in nature. The intention is to build a managerial mind-set that will be prepared for international competition.

6.3.3.2 Build knowledge assets

Insight from the study contributes to an understanding of the present-day manager. Here, the global environment requires a manager with an eagerness to acquire knowledge in different areas. This can be used as a resource to enhance business performance. Results reveal that

knowledge helps to boost information capacity, and preparedness for challenges within international markets. This knowledge can be acquired through formal training, informal training, industrial associations, friends, and family abroad.

6.3.3.3 Transform managerial thinking to focus on reality

Very often, managerial thinking is guided by textbook concepts. However, the results reveal SMEs that internationalised without documenting their strategies as outlined by the literature. Yet, these SMEs managed to internationalise their activities. There must be an understanding amongst managers that though business planning is important, there may be opportunities that arise outside their plans. These opportunities must not be ignored just because they are not documented in their business plans. In this sense, flexibility is required in managerial thinking. In other words, managers must be able to operate and make decisions outside their business plan. Although business plans are vital, they can be a limiting factor if followed religiously. In this sense, managerial thinking must be transformed from the textbook mentality, to being able to appreciate the evolving nature of business and make timely decisions, even without written plans.

6.3.3.4 Guidelines for SME managers and policy makers

Drawing from the literature, the findings, and discussion, some guidelines have been developed with the intention of helping SMEs in Cameroon to overcome the challenges identified and internationalise their activities (see figure 6.1). These guidelines can also be used by policy makers to help inform their policy making.

Figure 6. 1: Guidelines for SME managers and policy makers

Firstly, there is a need for both SME managers and policy makers to establish a localised understanding of the barriers affecting the internationalisation of SMEs. This will help to develop policies that are informed by local understandings, and local knowledge systems. This is proposed as the first step to overcoming the barriers. Secondly, the theoretical understandings of internationalisation must be viewed within the context of local knowledge systems. Here, there is a need to revise the theoretical models to make them relevant to the local situation. That will help to make the theories relevant to the local contexts, rather than assume that the business environment is the same the world over. Thirdly, specific managerial actions must be taken to account for the evolving business environment, account for SMEs that internationalise from inception, account for changing networks across borders, and the contextual understandings of internationalisation. This will help to make managerial decisions, and policies that are relevant, meaningful, and useful. This will also help to cultivate an entrepreneurial mindset amongst SME managers, and policy makers. This is a resource that is needed to achieve successful outcomes.

It is argued that, by embracing this procedural and practical approach, an entrepreneurial mindset amongst SMEs will be built. This will help the SMEs to use local knowledge systems as an asset that can help them to compete more effectively. Consequently, this will result in the growth of SMEs within international markets and promote local economic development.

Ultimately, the barriers to the internationalisation of SMEs will be transformed into opportunities of growth, job creation, competitiveness, and development.

It is also important to acknowledge the iterative nature of the proposed guidelines. This entails creating clear lines of communication to embrace feedback from various stages of the proposed model. It is argued that guidelines must be improved and modified on a continuous basis. This is because the business environment is not static, and as such, managers and policy makers must not ignore these changes. Further, local knowledge systems must be viewed as a resource for competitiveness. Hence, the need for transformed thinking, and modifying theoretical understandings so that meaningful and practical decisions are made.

6.4 Recommendations

Drawing from the findings, the following practical recommendations are made:

1. Managers must encourage the creation formal and informal networks, as these are resources that can be used within the internationalisation process of SMEs. Given the growth of social media, there are opportunities for networking at individual and organisational levels. SMEs owner/managers are encouraged to engage with different networks, both online and offline. The intention is to build relationships that can add value to the activities of the SMEs. Such changes in the technological environment must inform internationalisation strategies.
2. Whilst many challenges for internationalisation have been revealed, these can be overcome by engaging actively with individual, organisational, and industry networks. Such networks can be used as resources to overcome the challenges that are faced in the internationalisation process.
3. Managers must engage with policy makers to ensure that, bureaucratic barriers are reduced by developing policies and initiatives that are supportive of internationalisation activities. Initiatives could include knowledge sharing schemes, cultural exchange programmes, and international work placement opportunities. The intention is to encourage international knowledge exchange programs. This also helps to provide entrepreneurs with international exposure stimuli.

4. Managers must engage with policy makers to ensure that, within the educational system and policies, the curriculum must cultivate an entrepreneurial mind-set. For example, learning activities might bring real life examples from the international arena, and allow students to explore business opportunities. Such engagement might help to prepare the students for engagement with the international business environment.
5. Managers must invest in the development of platforms for business owners to connect with other foreign businesses. The intention is to help build ties and partnership that will promote international growth. This might help to encourage local firms to develop a mind-set that wants to venture into the international markets.
6. Managers must invest in gaining exposure to international stimuli. The results revealed that most of the firms that stayed internal were not exposed to international stimuli and opportunities. Therefore, owners/managers should actively seek to expand globally. This entails having a foreign business mind-set, and a global vision.

6.5 Limitations of the Research

There are some limitations that must be acknowledged:

1. This study was a doctoral study and had to be completed with a certain predefined time frame to help satisfy the immigration requirements of a student visa in the United Kingdom. This meant that all data sets had to be collected within this time frame. Further, any data sets that may have been available at times outside the predefined time frame were excluded from this study.
2. The sample size for the qualitative study was limited, that is, only six experts. The secondary data sets only focused on a single organisation. However, these data sets were complimented by survey data, and thereby attaining the benefits of triangulation.
3. Another limitation of the study were the resources required to collect data. The study was self-sponsored, and the researcher had to use personal savings to complete the study. This influenced the spread of the sample size for both primary and secondary data sets.

4. Another limitation of the study is the generalizability of the study results because the research focused explicitly on a single company. To achieve wider generalizability, there is still a need for insights to be obtained from other companies in the fast food industry. However, the results are still generalizable to this company.
5. The secondary statistical data sets used were collected for another purpose. It was not clear how variables were measured. Regardless, these data sets were obtained from company reports that are available in the public domain.

6.6 Suggestions for Future Studies

The study focused on the challenges of the internationalization process of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) within the context of Cameroon. Given the limitations of the study, and the gaps identified, there is still need for further studies as outlined below:

Study 1: Replication of current study in other manufacturing industries

Future studies are needed to ascertain the insights of other internationalising SMEs in other manufacturing sectors. This will help to test the emergent theoretical framework outlined in chapter 6, thereby helping to develop a more cohesive framework that might help SMEs from Cameroon, and other African countries to take calculated risks and internationalise their activities.

Study 2: Rethinking traditional internationalisation models

Further studies are needed to ascertain the effectiveness of the resource-based view, stage theory, and network theory when applied to the realm of internationalisation singularly. Here, studies can focus on the contextualised understandings of these theoretical models, and how they help to enhance the activities of SMEs that embark on internationalising their activities.

Study 3: Expanding the geographical coverage of the same study in Cameroon

Further research is recommended to cover a wider geographical area and include a larger survey. This can also focus on SMEs in a specific industry. Food manufacturers, Such a focus would help to bring deeper insights to those specific manufacturing areas

Study 4: Conducting similar studies in other African countries

Future studies can also be conducted in other African countries, using methodologies that were employed by this study. This would help to test the replicability of the study, and the generalizability within different African countries.

Study 5: SMEs in the process of internationalising

The study focused on SMEs with an international presence, thereby excluding those that are in the process of internationalising. Therefore, there is a need for studies that will focus on SMEs that are still internationalising.

6.7 Chapter Summary

The study determined the challenges of the internationalization process of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) within the context of Cameroon and developed some guidelines that can help SMEs to internationalise their products and services. In chapter 1, the researcher outlined the research problem, aim of the study, research objectives, research questions, and provided an overview of the thesis. In chapter 2, the focus was on critically reviewing the literature on internationalisation of the SMEs and identifying gaps in knowledge. In particular, the stage theory, network theory, and the resource-based view theory, were reviewed. This was followed by identifying gaps in knowledge, and then developing a conceptual framework that helped to position the study more strongly in the literature. Chapter 2 also provided the research context. This was informed by statistical indicators that helped to highlight the research problem more clearly. Chapter 3 focused on the methodology and used an abductive approach. Chapter 4 sequentially analysed the survey data, and the qualitative data. In chapter 5, the researcher discussed the findings within the context of the literature. This was followed by developing a theoretical framework, and some guidelines that could help to SMEs within the internationalisation process. These guidelines, and the theoretical framework, were informed by the findings of the study. Chapter 6 outlined the study contributions (theoretical, methodological, and managerial), recommendations and conclusions. Within this, research objectives were revisited, and the researcher explained how each of the research objectives was met.

Within this thesis, the international behaviour of the managers and firm owners has been tested through the development of an integrated theoretical framework. It emerged that there are some contextually based practices that are often ignored in most accounts of internationalisation

debates. The study contributes to the literature on internationalisation and suggests ways that the barriers to internationalisation can be overcome.

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Appendix 1.1 Ethical clearance approval

20/02/2018

Dear Becky Forbin,

Your application 1739: ethical approval form for research thesis, submission 2135, has been approved by the Business and Enterprise SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

School Ethics Committee

Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.

Appendix 1.2 Consent Form

PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: Barriers Affecting Effective internationalization process of Cameroon Manufacturing SMEs

Name of Researcher: Becky Forbin

Participant to complete this section: Please initial each box.

1. I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason.

3. I agree to take part in the above study.

4. I agree to the use of anonymous quotes in publications

Signature of Participant Date

Name of person taking consent Date

Signature of person taking consent

If you require any further information about this project then please contact:

Becky Forbin, University of the West of Scotland.

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Barriers Affecting the effective internationalization process of Cameroon Manufacturing SMEs

Project summary

The purpose of the research of is proceeding on the analytical points to the continuity of criticality of barriers affecting the process of internationalization, which includes limitation of resources, managerial incomprehension and deficiency of global market-related information on the impacts of SMEs external expansion. The barriers are principally internal as well as external coupled with the characteristics of the SMEs which are reflections of the constraints of firm's competency to internationalize. Therefore the study aims to explore and analyze the barriers that occur in an effective internationalization process by manufacturing SMEs in Cameroon while providing guidelines for SMEs to overcome international challenges.

Why have you been asked to participate?

You have been asked to participate because you fit the requirements of the group which is being studied. Your contribution is voluntary, and you may leave the session at any time you like.

Your contribution will be part of the evidence for this a study

Project risks

The research requires to filling out a questionnaire which will be kept for later analysis. We do not think that there are any significant risks associated with this study but if you feel there is any, please let us know and you are free to stop the process. Besides that, if you believe that any question is inappropriate, and you feel uncomfortable; please feel free to withdraw the process at any time. We will completely respect your decision.

How we protect your privacy

All the information you provide will be confidential. In the questionnaires won't be included any personal information that can identify you, maintaining the anonymity promised. Your personal details from the consent form and the questionnaire will be kept in secure places by the researcher. All the information and documentation will be destroyed at the end of this study.

YOU WILL BE OFFERED A COPY OF THIS INFORMATION SHEET TO KEEP

If you require any further information about this project, then please contact:

Becky Forbin, University of the West of Scotland.

Appendix 1.4 – Survey instrument

QUESTIONNAIRE

This Survey is part of DBA studies; it is intended for academic research purpose as data tool to collect information on the barriers affecting internationalisation process of Cameroon Manufacturing SMEs. Be aware the data and information provided by respondents will be confidential and represented comprehensively.

Key Terms: Internationalisation – foreign expansion

SMEs- Small Medium Enterprises

Domestic Market – Local/internal market

Instructions: SMEs that deals only in domestic and international market (please tick where appropriate) and kindly fill the part of the questionnaire that suits your company.

General Information

Name of the Firm (Confidential).....

Year of creation.....

Year of international operations

1. Gender

1. Male 2. Female

2. Age of the Firm

1. Less than 10years 2. 10-15years 3. 16-20years 4. 21-25years 5. 26-30 years 6. 31years and above

3. Owners/Entrepreneurs or the CEO of level of education

1. Primary education and below 2. Diploma/HND certificate 3. Bachelor Certificate 4. Master Degree and Above

4. What are the owners/CEO levels of experience in the industry?

1. 0-5 years 2. 6-10years 3. 11-15years 4. 16-20years 5. 20years and above

5. Number of employees working in your company, please specify the industry sector?

1. 0-10 2. 11-50 3. 51-100 4. 101-150 5. 151-250

6. What is your Firm's Industry Sector?

1. Wood 2. Textile 3. Agriculture 4. Metal Oil Others _____

7. In what regions and country does your firm operates it international activities?

1. Littoral Region 2. Northwest Region 3. Southwest Region 4. Central Region 5. Africa (CEMAC Zone) 6. Rest of Africa 7. Rest of the world

8. Who are there main suppliers and clients of your manufacture products?
 1. MNC (Large firms) 2. Government Firms 3. SMEs 4. Others VSME(Very small Business or single owners)
9. In your own opinion would say there is existing international opportunity for your company?
 1. Strongly Agree 2. Agred 3. Neutra 4. Disagred 5. Strongly Disagree
10. In terms of international growth process, how well would you describe the internationalisation speed of your company?
 1. Slow 2. Medium 3. High/Rapid

Note: The following part of the questionnaire contains five options (Strongly agree, agree, Neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree),

11. How do international knowledge, experience and information impact your firm's internationalisation process?

Knowledge and international experience barriers	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
--	-----------------------	--------------	----------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Shortage of knowledge on foreign market opportunities

Shortage of knowledge on perspective buyers, international agents and suppliers

Lack of research in international market

Shortage of information on international product pricing

Language and communication difficulties

12. How do you agree to the following human resource barriers affecting the internationalisation process of your firm?

Human resource Barriers	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
--------------------------------	-----------------------	--------------	----------------	-----------------	--------------------------

shortage of trained personnel in the international market

Low or no managerial international exposure

Inexperience managerial(owner) on development on international activities

Lack of structure plan and execution of international activities

13. Does your firm have enough capital resources to sustain its international activities and how will you agree on the following financial challenges encountered?

Financial Barriers	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
---------------------------	-----------------------	--------------	----------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Shortage of funds for firm to self-finance international operations

Strict requirements for credit loans from banks

Lack of government aid to finance international activities

14. Do you agree that your finished product meets international standards or is it a barrier to internationalisation?

Product Barriers	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
-------------------------	-----------------------	--------------	----------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Problem in product quality

Unable to meet international packaging standards

Unable to meet global product standards

Lack of ability to produce large quantities that meet market demand

Product branding problem

15. What is your opinion on the influence or role played by the government to promote the internationalisation of your firm?

Government Bureaucratic Barriers	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
---	-----------------------	--------------	----------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Lack of international promotion program

None or very little support to overcome international barriers

Protectionist barriers

Inadequate sponsorship by government to support private businesses

Poor diplomatic support

16. What is your opinion on the following factors influencing internationalisation of manufacturing SMEs?

Exogenous Barriers	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
---------------------------	-----------------------	--------------	----------------	-----------------	--------------------------

- International trade Policy
- Trade regulations
- High domestic Values
- Exchange rate fluctuation
- Inflation rate
- International trade taxes
- High interest rate
- Political Instability

17. What will you say is the reason for your company to remain in the domestic/local market?

1. Experienced over time 2. Low financial involvement Cultural awareness
 in the market 4. competitive advantage, other _____

18. What do you think are the factors and criteria that are valuable for domestic market?

- | | Strongly agree | Agree | Neutral | Disagree | Strongly disagree |
|--|-----------------------|--------------|----------------|-----------------|--------------------------|
| Change in political system of the Government | | | | | |
| Economic climate change | | | | | |
| Competitive Rivalries | | | | | |
| Change in government regulations | | | | | |

19. What is your opinion on the following factors when choosing and targeting a foreign potential market?

- | General factors of influence | Strongly agree | Agree | Neutral | Disagree | Strongly disagree |
|-------------------------------------|-----------------------|--------------|----------------|-----------------|--------------------------|
| Political/Legal factors | | | | | |
| Cultural Factors | | | | | |
| Economic Factors | | | | | |
| Competitive advantage | | | | | |
| Firm's level of technology | | | | | |
| Distribution structure | | | | | |
| Size of the Firm | | | | | |
| Age of the firm | | | | | |

- Cultural similarities
- Market similarities
- International relationship/network
- Entrepreneurial/Managerial expertise
- Environmental awareness
- Technological advancement

20. Which of the following appropriately describes your company's process of international expansion or if you haven't internationalised which would you used?
1. Uppsala Model of internationalisation 2. Born global policy 3. Network/relationship model 4. Transaction cost 6. International entrepreneurship
23. What kind of international activities does your company get involved in, in the external market?
1. Franchising 2. Import 3. Export 4. Licensing 5. Alliance 6. Joint venture
7. others please specify.....
21. What is your opinion about the phrase self-reference criterion (in decision making, unconsciously, referring to ones' personal cultural value and experience) is essential to internationalising?
1. Strongly agree 2. Agree 3. Neutral 4. Disagree 5. Strongly disagree
22. For the research purpose we will be glad if you can share more about your international experience.....

.....

End of Questionnaire

I appreciate your time and effort Thank you for your Answer

Appendix 1.5 Interview Questions Guide

A. General Information

Company's Name (Confidential)

Respondent Position:

Founding Date of the Company:

Number of Employees:

Company's internationalisation year:

Manufacturing product/sector of the industry:

B. Motivation of your company's internationalisation

1. Regards to the domestic market, how will describe your firm's position before the internationalization process took place? Would you say it was an essential decision for the company to internationalise?
2. When did you start internationalisation process?
3. How long did the firm work in its domestic market before foreign expansion and how long did the firm deliberate on the external expansion decision?
4. How did the firm implement its international plans? What were the first steps and how did the progression go on?
5. How important is the role of networks in internationalization process
6. What is the total number of countries that your company has international established presents and activities? Please list them and state the year

1	2
3	4
5.....	6

7. What were the main motivation of your firm internationalisation

1. Profit
2. International/global growth
3. Over saturation/high competition in the domestic market
4. Acquired information and knowledge about potential market
5. Other

C. Internationalisation Barriers/Challenges

1. What where the main challenges face by your company in entering a foreign market?

2. Does Cameroon Government make any attempt to facilitate those problems?
3. Was your company affected by cultural barriers? If yes what was the company's reaction?
4. Does the Cameroon government provide incentives for internationalisation and market research?
5. From the following statements below which do you think is most challenging factor for your company's?

Please choose one only

- a. Shortage of working financial capital
 - b. Unable to identify external opportunities
 - c. Inadequate data/analysis on foreign market
 - d. Inability to create international connections
6. What will you say was the most challenging factor for your company during the process of internationalisation?
1. political/legal
 2. Economic forces
 3. Exchange rate fluctuation
 4. Trade Tariffs and government regulation

D. International mode of Entry

1. What mode of entry is suitable for your company's internationalisation process?
1. Licensing Agreement
 2. Business Alliance
 3. Joint Venture
 4. Franchising
 5. Whole subsidiary
 6. Direct exportation
 7. Indirect exportation
2. Does your company intend to have established present internationally, hence through subsidiary?
3. Which of the following factors affects your companies entry mode (when your you intend to internationalized)
1. Insufficient Monetary capital
 2. Insufficient Knowledge
 3. Lack of external Market connections.
 4. Managerial emphasis on internal market growth
 5. Lack of exportation commitment
4. Are you experienced working in foreign companies?

[Appendix 2: Statistical tables](#)

DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS

Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	67	59.8	59.8	59.8
	Female	45	40.2	40.2	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Age of Firm

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	less than 10years	48	42.9	42.9	42.9
	10-15years	28	25.0	25.0	67.9
	16-20years	13	11.6	11.6	79.5
	21-25years	9	8.0	8.0	87.5
	26-30years	9	8.0	8.0	95.5
	30years and above	5	4.5	4.5	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Educational Level

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Primary education and below	20	17.9	17.9	17.9
	Diploma/HND Certificate	31	27.7	27.7	45.5
	Bachelor certificate	43	38.4	38.4	83.9
	Master degree and Above	18	16.1	16.1	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Owners Experience

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	0-5years	45	40.2	40.2	40.2
	6-10years	23	20.5	20.5	60.7
	11-15years	23	20.5	20.5	81.3
	16-20years	12	10.7	10.7	92.0
	20years and above	9	8.0	8.0	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Number of Employees

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	0-10	15	13.4	13.4	13.4
	11-50	41	36.6	36.6	50.0
	51-100	30	26.8	26.8	76.8
	101-150	13	11.6	11.6	88.4
	151-250	13	11.6	11.6	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Firm Industry sector

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Wood	33	29.5	29.5	29.5
	Textile	29	25.9	25.9	55.4
	Agriculture	30	26.8	26.8	82.1
	Metal	13	11.6	11.6	93.8
	Oil	7	6.3	6.3	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Region of operation

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Littoral region	30	26.8	26.8	26.8
	Northwest region	25	22.3	22.3	49.1
	Southwest Region	13	11.6	11.6	60.7
	Central Region	12	10.7	10.7	71.4
	CEMAC Zone	15	13.4	13.4	84.8
	Rest of Africa	10	8.9	8.9	93.8
	Rest of the world	7	6.3	6.3	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Client and Supplier base

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	MNC	16	14.3	14.3	14.3
	government Firms	18	16.1	16.1	30.4
	SMEs	55	49.1	49.1	79.5
	Others VSME (very small medium enterprise)	23	20.5	20.5	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Existing international opportunity

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	11	9.8	9.8	9.8
	Agree	17	15.2	15.2	25.0
	Neutral	13	11.6	11.6	36.6
	Disagree	37	33.0	33.0	69.6
	strongly disagree	34	30.4	30.4	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Growth process

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Slow	85	75.9	75.9	75.9
	Medium	16	14.3	14.3	90.2
	High/Rapid	11	9.8	9.8	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

foreign opportunities

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	67	59.8	59.8	59.8
	Agree	24	21.4	21.4	81.3
	Neutral	7	6.3	6.3	87.5
	Disagree	10	8.9	8.9	96.4
	strongly Disagree	4	3.6	3.6	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Agents, suppliers, and buyers

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	60	53.6	53.6	53.6
	Agree	32	28.6	28.6	82.1
	Neutral	6	5.4	5.4	87.5
	Disagree	14	12.5	12.5	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

international market research

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	strongly agree	65	58.0	58.0	58.0
	Agree	28	25.0	25.0	83.0
	Neutral	7	6.3	6.3	89.3
	Disagree	11	9.8	9.8	99.1
	Strongly Disagree	1	.9	.9	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Product pricing

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	55	49.1	49.1	49.1
	Agree	28	25.0	25.0	74.1
	Neutral	5	4.5	4.5	78.6
	Disagree	14	12.5	12.5	91.1
	strongly Disagree	10	8.9	8.9	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

communication difficulties

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	59	52.7	52.7	52.7
	Agree	32	28.6	28.6	81.3
	Neutral	8	7.1	7.1	88.4
	Disagree	11	9.8	9.8	98.2
	Strongly Disagree	2	1.8	1.8	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

shortage of trained personnel

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	strongly Agree	57	50.9	50.9	50.9
	Agree	39	34.8	34.8	85.7
	Neutral	6	5.4	5.4	91.1
	Disagree	7	6.3	6.3	97.3
	Strongly Disagree	3	2.7	2.7	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

low managerial exposure

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	61	54.5	54.5	54.5
	Agree	38	33.9	33.9	88.4
	Neutral	2	1.8	1.8	90.2
	Disagree	7	6.3	6.3	96.4
	strongly Disagree	4	3.6	3.6	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

inexperienced on international activities

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	strongly Agree	42	37.5	37.5	37.5
	Agree	50	44.6	44.6	82.1
	Neutral	6	5.4	5.4	87.5
	Disagree	12	10.7	10.7	98.2
	Strongly Disagree	2	1.8	1.8	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

lack of structure plan and execution

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	64	57.1	57.1	57.1
	Agree	32	28.6	28.6	85.7
	Neutral	4	3.6	3.6	89.3
	Disagree	10	8.9	8.9	98.2
	strongly Disagree	2	1.8	1.8	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Shortage of trained personnel

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	57	50.9	50.9	50.9
	Agree	39	34.8	34.8	85.7
	Neutral	6	5.4	5.4	91.1
	Disagree	7	6.3	6.3	97.3
	Strongly Disagree	3	2.7	2.7	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Low managerial exposure

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	61	54.5	54.5	54.5
	Agree	38	33.9	33.9	88.4
	Neutral	2	1.8	1.8	90.2
	Disagree	7	6.3	6.3	96.4
	strongly Disagree	4	3.6	3.6	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Inexperienced on international activities

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	42	37.5	37.5	37.5
	Agree	50	44.6	44.6	82.1
	Neutral	6	5.4	5.4	87.5
	Disagree	12	10.7	10.7	98.2
	Strongly Disagree	2	1.8	1.8	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Lack of structure plan and execution

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	64	57.1	57.1	57.1
	Agree	32	28.6	28.6	85.7
	Neutral	4	3.6	3.6	89.3
	Disagree	10	8.9	8.9	98.2
	Strongly Disagree	2	1.8	1.8	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Shortage of funds for international operations

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	52	46.4	46.4	46.4
	Agree	43	38.4	38.4	84.8
	Neutral	7	6.3	6.3	91.1
	Disagree	8	7.1	7.1	98.2
	Strongly Disagree	2	1.8	1.8	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Strict bank loan requirements

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	63	56.3	56.3	56.3
	Agree	29	25.9	25.9	82.1
	Neutral	5	4.5	4.5	86.6
	Disagree	12	10.7	10.7	97.3
	Strongly Disagree	3	2.7	2.7	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Strict bank loan requirements

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	63	56.3	56.3	56.3
	Agree	29	25.9	25.9	82.1
	Neutral	5	4.5	4.5	86.6
	Disagree	12	10.7	10.7	97.3
	Strongly Disagree	3	2.7	2.7	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Problem on product quality

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	63	56.3	56.3	56.3
	Agree	29	25.9	25.9	82.1
	Neutral	5	4.5	4.5	86.6
	Disagree	12	10.7	10.7	97.3
	Strongly Disagree	3	2.7	2.7	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Packaging standards

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	51	45.5	45.5	45.5
	Agree	44	39.3	39.3	84.8
	Neutral	7	6.3	6.3	91.1
	Disagree	7	6.3	6.3	97.3
	Strongly Disagree	3	2.7	2.7	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Global product standards

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	57	50.9	50.9	50.9
	Agree	39	34.8	34.8	85.7
	Neutral	6	5.4	5.4	91.1
	Disagree	7	6.3	6.3	97.3
	Strongly Disagree	3	2.7	2.7	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Low stock production

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	61	54.5	54.5	54.5
	Agree	38	33.9	33.9	88.4
	Neutral	2	1.8	1.8	90.2
	Disagree	7	6.3	6.3	96.4
	Strongly Disagree	4	3.6	3.6	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Product branding problem

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	42	37.5	37.5	37.5
	Agree	50	44.6	44.6	82.1
	Neutral	6	5.4	5.4	87.5
	Disagree	12	10.7	10.7	98.2
	Strongly Disagree	2	1.8	1.8	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

GOVERNMENT BUREAUCRATIC BARRIERS

International promotion program

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	64	57.1	57.1	57.1
	Agree	32	28.6	28.6	85.7
	Neutral	4	3.6	3.6	89.3
	Disagree	10	8.9	8.9	98.2
	Strongly Disagree	2	1.8	1.8	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Support to overcome international barriers

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	57	50.9	50.9	50.9
	Agree	39	34.8	34.8	85.7
	Neutral	6	5.4	5.4	91.1
	Disagree	7	6.3	6.3	97.3
	Strongly Disagree	3	2.7	2.7	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Inadequate governmental sponsorship

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	61	54.5	54.5	54.5
	Agree	38	33.9	33.9	88.4
	Neutral	2	1.8	1.8	90.2
	Disagree	7	6.3	6.3	96.4
	Strongly Disagree	4	3.6	3.6	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Poor diplomatic support

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	42	37.5	37.5	37.5
	Agree	50	44.6	44.6	82.1
	Neutral	6	5.4	5.4	87.5
	Disagree	12	10.7	10.7	98.2
	Strongly Disagree	2	1.8	1.8	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

EXOGENOUS BARRIERS

International trade policy

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	64	57.1	57.1	57.1
	Agree	32	28.6	28.6	85.7
	Neutral	4	3.6	3.6	89.3
	Disagree	10	8.9	8.9	98.2
	Strongly Disagree	2	1.8	1.8	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Trade regulations

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	52	46.4	46.4	46.4
	Agree	43	38.4	38.4	84.8
	Neutral	7	6.3	6.3	91.1
	Disagree	8	7.1	7.1	98.2
	Strongly Disagree	2	1.8	1.8	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

High domestic values

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	57	50.9	50.9	50.9
	Agree	39	34.8	34.8	85.7
	Neutral	6	5.4	5.4	91.1
	Disagree	7	6.3	6.3	97.3
	Strongly Disagree	3	2.7	2.7	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Exchange rate fluctuation

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	61	54.5	54.5	54.5
	Agree	38	33.9	33.9	88.4
	Neutral	2	1.8	1.8	90.2
	Disagree	7	6.3	6.3	96.4
	Strongly Disagree	4	3.6	3.6	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Inflation rate

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	42	37.5	37.5	37.5
	Agree	50	44.6	44.6	82.1
	Neutral	6	5.4	5.4	87.5
	Disagree	12	10.7	10.7	98.2
	Strongly Disagree	2	1.8	1.8	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

International trade taxes

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	64	57.1	57.1	57.1
	Agree	32	28.6	28.6	85.7
	Neutral	4	3.6	3.6	89.3
	Disagree	10	8.9	8.9	98.2
	Strongly Disagree	2	1.8	1.8	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

High interest rate

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	52	46.4	46.4	46.4
	Agree	43	38.4	38.4	84.8
	Neutral	7	6.3	6.3	91.1
	Disagree	8	7.1	7.1	98.2
	Strongly Disagree	2	1.8	1.8	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Political instability

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	56	50.0	50.0	50.0
	Agree	39	34.8	34.8	84.8
	Neutral	7	6.3	6.3	91.1
	Disagree	7	6.3	6.3	97.3
	Strongly Disagree	3	2.7	2.7	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Domestic market focused

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Experienced over time	41	36.6	36.6	36.6
	low financial involvement	24	21.4	21.4	58.0
	cultural awareness	18	16.1	16.1	74.1
	competitive advantage	19	17.0	17.0	91.1
	Others	10	8.9	8.9	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

FACTORS AND CRITERIA VALUABLE FOR DOMESTIC MARKET

Change in political system

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	50	44.6	44.6	44.6
	Agree	32	28.6	28.6	73.2
	Neutral	13	11.6	11.6	84.8
	Disagree	10	8.9	8.9	93.8
	Strongly Disagree	7	6.3	6.3	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Economic climate change

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	6	5.4	5.4	5.4
	Agree	9	8.0	8.0	13.4
	Neutral	15	13.4	13.4	26.8
	Disagree	72	64.3	64.3	91.1
	Strongly Disagree	10	8.9	8.9	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Competitive rivalries

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	47	42.0	42.0	42.0
	Agree	32	28.6	28.6	70.5
	Neutral	14	12.5	12.5	83.0
	Disagree	12	10.7	10.7	93.8
	Strongly Disagree	7	6.3	6.3	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Change in government regulations

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	7	6.3	6.3	6.3
	Agree	9	8.0	8.0	14.3
	Neutral	14	12.5	12.5	26.8
	Disagree	72	64.3	64.3	91.1
	Strongly Disagree	10	8.9	8.9	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Political legal factors

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	52	46.4	46.4	46.4
	Agree	43	38.4	38.4	84.8
	Neutral	7	6.3	6.3	91.1
	Disagree	8	7.1	7.1	98.2
	Strongly Disagree	2	1.8	1.8	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Cultural factors

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	56	50.0	50.0	50.0
	Agree	39	34.8	34.8	84.8
	Neutral	7	6.3	6.3	91.1
	Disagree	7	6.3	6.3	97.3
	Strongly Disagree	3	2.7	2.7	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Competitive advantage

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	41	36.6	36.6	36.6
	Agree	24	21.4	21.4	58.0
	Neutral	18	16.1	16.1	74.1
	Disagree	19	17.0	17.0	91.1
	Strongly Disagree	10	8.9	8.9	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Firm's level of technology

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	50	44.6	44.6	44.6
	Agree	32	28.6	28.6	73.2
	Neutral	13	11.6	11.6	84.8
	Disagree	10	8.9	8.9	93.8
	Strongly Disagree	7	6.3	6.3	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Distribution structure

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	6	5.4	5.4	5.4
	Agree	9	8.0	8.0	13.4
	Neutral	15	13.4	13.4	26.8
	Disagree	72	64.3	64.3	91.1
	Strongly Disagree	10	8.9	8.9	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Size of firm

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	47	42.0	42.0	42.0
	Agree	32	28.6	28.6	70.5
	Neutral	14	12.5	12.5	83.0
	Disagree	12	10.7	10.7	93.8
	Strongly Disagree	7	6.3	6.3	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Age of firm

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	7	6.3	6.3	6.3
	Agree	9	8.0	8.0	14.3
	Neutral	14	12.5	12.5	26.8
	Disagree	72	64.3	64.3	91.1
	Strongly Disagree	10	8.9	8.9	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Cultural similarities

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	67	59.8	59.8	59.8
	Agree	24	21.4	21.4	81.3
	Neutral	7	6.3	6.3	87.5
	Disagree	10	8.9	8.9	96.4
	Strongly Disagree	4	3.6	3.6	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Market similarities

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	60	53.6	53.6	53.6
	Agree	32	28.6	28.6	82.1
	Neutral	6	5.4	5.4	87.5
	Disagree	14	12.5	12.5	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

International relationship/network

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	65	58.0	58.0	58.0
	Agree	28	25.0	25.0	83.0
	Neutral	7	6.3	6.3	89.3
	Disagree	11	9.8	9.8	99.1
	Strongly Disagree	1	.9	.9	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Entrepreneurial/managerial expertise

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	55	49.1	49.1	49.1
	Agree	28	25.0	25.0	74.1
	Neutral	5	4.5	4.5	78.6
	Disagree	14	12.5	12.5	91.1
	Strongly Disagree	10	8.9	8.9	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Environmental awareness

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	44	39.3	39.3	39.3
	Agree	24	21.4	21.4	60.7
	Neutral	15	13.4	13.4	74.1
	Disagree	19	17.0	17.0	91.1
	Strongly Disagree	10	8.9	8.9	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Firm's international theories

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Uppsala Model of internationalisation	8	7.1	7.1	7.1
	Born Global policy	19	17.0	17.0	24.1
	Network/relationship model	25	22.3	22.3	46.4
	Transaction cost	10	8.9	8.9	55.4
	International entrepreneurship	50	44.6	44.6	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

International activities

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Franchising	5	4.5	4.5	4.5
	Import	29	25.9	25.9	30.4
	Export	64	57.1	57.1	87.5
	Licensing	13	11.6	11.6	99.1
	Alliances	1	.9	.9	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Appendix 3: Data Analysis Tables

Table 4.2: Overall item total statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item- Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Foreign opportunities	84.8393	373.704	.285	.888
Agents, suppliers and buyers	84.8214	369.319	.436	.886
International market research	84.8839	372.824	.346	.887
Product pricing	84.5179	362.937	.438	.886
Communication difficulties	84.7946	375.102	.275	.888
Shortage of trained personnel	84.8393	366.893	.511	.885
Low managerial exposure	84.8839	366.626	.503	.885
Inexperienced on international activities	84.6429	371.457	.385	.886
Lack of structure plan and execution	84.8929	370.457	.407	.886
Shortage of funds for international operations	84.7946	367.570	.511	.885
Strict bank loan requirements	84.8125	370.028	.379	.886
Lack of government aid	84.7768	367.238	.507	.885
Problem on product quality	84.8125	370.028	.379	.886
Packaging standards	84.7768	367.238	.507	.885
Global product standards	84.8393	366.893	.511	.885
Low stock production	84.8839	366.626	.503	.885
product branding problem	84.6429	371.457	.385	.886
International promotion program	84.8929	370.457	.407	.886
Support to overcome international barriers	84.8393	366.893	.511	.885
Inadequate governmental sponsorship	84.8839	366.626	.503	.885
Poor diplomatic support	84.6429	371.457	.385	.886
International trade policy	84.8929	370.457	.407	.886
Trade regulations	84.7946	367.570	.511	.885
High domestic values	84.8393	366.893	.511	.885
Exchange rate fluctuation	84.8839	366.626	.503	.885
Inflation rate	84.6429	371.457	.385	.886
International trade taxes	84.8929	370.457	.407	.886
High interest rate	84.7946	367.570	.511	.885
Political instability	84.8214	367.103	.503	.885
Change in political system	84.5536	375.727	.217	.889

Economic climate change	82.9554	378.908	.208	.889
Competitive rivalries	84.4821	379.207	.140	.891
Political legal factors	84.7946	367.570	.511	.885
Cultural factors	84.8214	367.103	.503	.885
Competitive advantage	84.1875	380.388	.098	.892
Firm's level of technology	84.5536	375.727	.217	.889
Distribution structure	82.9554	378.908	.208	.889
Size of firm	84.4821	379.207	.140	.891
Age of firm	82.9732	377.161	.246	.888
Cultural similarities	84.8393	373.704	.285	.888
Market similarities	84.8214	369.319	.436	.886
International relationship/network	84.8839	372.824	.346	.887
Entrepreneurial/managerial expertise	84.5179	362.937	.438	.886
Environmental awareness	84.2411	386.689	-.020	.894

Table 4.5: Research construct 1 - Item statistics

Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Foreign opportunities	1.7500	1.13503	112
Agents, suppliers and buyers	1.7679	1.02212	112
International market research	1.7054	1.01908	112
Product pricing	2.0714	1.36041	112
Communication difficulties	1.7946	1.05812	112

Table 4.6: Research construct 1- item total statistics

Item-Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Foreign opportunities	7.3393	8.316	.266	.239	.523
Agents, suppliers and buyers	7.3214	7.950	.408	.303	.445
International market research	7.3839	8.040	.392	.232	.454
Product pricing	7.0179	7.351	.290	.104	.519
Communication difficulties	7.2946	8.714	.242	.112	.534

Table 4. 4: Inter-item correlation matrix

Inter-Item Correlation Matrix				
	Shortage of trained personnel	Low managerial exposure	Inexperienced on international activities	Lack of structure plan and execution
Shortage of trained personnel	1.000	.287	.031	.066
Low managerial exposure	.287	1.000	.158	.189
Inexperienced on international activities	.031	.158	1.000	-.042
Lack of structure plan and execution	.066	.189	-.042	1.000

Table 4. 5:Item total statistics

Item-Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Shortage of trained personnel	5.3482	3.761	.203	.083	.254
Low managerial exposure	5.3929	3.178	.359	.136	.053
Inexperienced on international activities	5.1518	4.220	.073	.030	.399
Lack of structure plan and execution	5.4018	4.062	.108	.041	.362

Table 4. 71: Inter-item correlation matrix

Inter-Item Correlation Matrix								
	International trade policy	Trade regulations	High domestic values	Exchange rate fluctuation	Inflation rate	International trade taxes	High interest rate	Political instability
International trade policy	1.000	.064	.066	.189	-.042	1.000	.064	.071
Trade regulations	.064	1.000	.151	.065	.264	.064	1.000	.154
High domestic values	.066	.151	1.000	.287	.031	.066	.151	.982
Exchange rate fluctuation	.189	.065	.287	1.000	.158	.189	.065	.291
Inflation rate	-.042	.264	.031	.158	1.000	-.042	.264	.014
International trade taxes	1.000	.064	.066	.189	-.042	1.000	.064	.071
High interest rate	.064	1.000	.151	.065	.264	.064	1.000	.154
Political instability	.071	.154	.982	.291	.014	.071	.154	1.000

Table 4. 72: Item total statistics

Table 4.41: Item-Total Statistics						
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted	
Political legal factors	18.3482	18.013	.313	.114	.535	
Cultural factors	18.3750	18.255	.264	.080	.547	
Firm's level of technology	18.1071	18.024	.194	.090	.570	
Distribution structure	16.5089	19.766	.102	.084	.586	
Age of firm	16.5268	18.468	.250	.105	.551	
Cultural similarities	18.3929	17.880	.246	.260	.552	
Market similarities	18.3750	17.444	.356	.330	.522	
International relationship/network	18.4375	17.834	.309	.189	.535	
Entrepreneurial/managerial expertise	18.0714	15.544	.385	.184	.505	

Table 4. 73: Industry sector vs client supplier base

Firm Industry sector * Client and Supplier base Crosstabulation						
Count						
		Client and Supplier base				Total
		MNC	government Firms	SMEs	Others VSME (very small medium enterprise)	
Firm Industry sector	Wood	6	8	13	6	33
	Textile	3	1	19	6	29
	Agriculture	6	5	13	6	30
	Metal	0	4	6	3	13
	Oil	1	0	4	2	7
Total		16	18	55	23	112

Table 4. 74: Case processing summary

Case Processing Summary			
		N	Marginal Percentage
Growth process	Slow	85	75.9%
	Medium	16	14.3%
	High/Rapid	11	9.8%
Agents, suppliers and buyers	Strongly Agree	60	53.6%
	Agree	32	28.6%
	Neutral	6	5.4%
	Disagree	14	12.5%
International market research	Strongly Agree	65	58.0%
	Agree	28	25.0%
	Neutral	7	6.3%
	Disagree	11	9.8%
	Strongly Disagree	1	0.9%
Product pricing	Strongly Agree	55	49.1%
	Agree	28	25.0%
	Neutral	5	4.5%
	Disagree	14	12.5%
	strongly Disagree	10	8.9%
Communication difficulties	Strongly Agree	59	52.7%
	Agree	32	28.6%
	Neutral	8	7.1%
	Disagree	11	9.8%
	Strongly Disagree	2	1.8%
Foreign opportunities	Strongly agree	67	59.8%
	Agree	24	21.4%
	Neutral	7	6.3%
	Disagree	10	8.9%
	strongly Disagree	4	3.6%
Valid		112	100.0%
Missing		0	
Total		112	

Table 4. 75: Case processing summary

Case Processing Summary		N	Marginal Percentage
Growth process	Slow	85	75.9%
	Medium	16	14.3%
	High/Rapid	11	9.8%
Shortage of trained personnel	Strongly Agree	57	50.9%
	Agree	39	34.8%
	Neutral	6	5.4%
	Disagree	7	6.3%
	Strongly Disagree	3	2.7%
Low managerial exposure	Strongly Agree	61	54.5%
	Agree	38	33.9%
	Neutral	2	1.8%
	Disagree	7	6.3%
	Strongly Disagree	4	3.6%
Inexperienced on international activities	Strongly Agree	42	37.5%
	Agree	50	44.6%
	Neutral	6	5.4%
	Disagree	12	10.7%
	Strongly Disagree	2	1.8%
Lack of structure plan and execution	Strongly Agree	64	57.1%
	Agree	32	28.6%
	Neutral	4	3.6%
	Disagree	10	8.9%
	Strongly Disagree	2	1.8%
Valid		112	100.0%
Missing		0	
Total		112	

Table 4. 76: Case processing summary

Case Processing Summary

		N	Marginal Percentage
Growth process	Slow	85	75.9%
	Medium	16	14.3%
	High/Rapid	11	9.8%
Shortage of funds for international operations	Strongly Agree	52	46.4%
	Agree	43	38.4%
	Neutral	7	6.3%
	Disagree	8	7.1%
	Strongly Disagree	2	1.8%
Strict bank loan requirements	Strongly Agree	63	56.3%
	Agree	29	25.9%
	Neutral	5	4.5%
	Disagree	12	10.7%
	Strongly Disagree	3	2.7%
Lack of government aid	Strongly Agree	51	45.5%
	Agree	44	39.3%
	Neutral	7	6.3%
	Disagree	7	6.3%
	Strongly Disagree	3	2.7%
Valid		112	100.0%
Missing		0	
Total		112	

Appendix 4: List of Companies

Company	Description
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ALUCAM	The Cameroonian Aluminum Company, known as Alucam, is a company producing aluminum, based in Cameroon, in Édéa, founded by Péciney - Uguine. Its factory is located on the island of the town of Edea, chief town of the department of Sanaga-Maritime in the Littoral region, 67 km from Douala
Cameroon Development Corporation	The Cameroon Development Corporation is an Agro-Industrial Complex that grows, processes and markets tropical export crops. It operates in Cameroon in the Central African sub-region
Group Teboh Enterprises	
Samco Paper Company Ltd	SAMCO PAPER COMPANY LIMITED was founded in 1992 and has been an industry leader in the manufacturing and distribution of high-quality paper products to retail outlets nationally and regionally.
Societe Nantional de Raffinage (SONARA)	Created in 1973 and inaugurated in 1981, SONARA is a topping reforming refinery. SONARA places at the disposal of the market the following petroleum products: butane, gasoline, jet fuel, kerosene, fuel oil, distillate, fuel oil.
Herp Breeding Farm & Co. Ltd	We have been operating since 1982 and with abundant knowledge of breeding and exporting of fauna species, we work and export within the framework of the International Air Transport Association (IATA) and also with the International Civil Aviation Organisation (ICAO).
Cacoco BTP	The African Company of Design and Construction in Buildings and Public Works, CACOCO-BTP (ex Cameroon Construction Corporation) is a Company of Building and Public Works. It has been practicing in Central and West Africa since 1985. It was created with a purpose in one currency: Professionalism - Ethics - Ambition
KOOP Cameroon	KOOP Cameroun - Siège social is located in, Cameroon. Company is working in Civil engineering business activities
Razel SA	The civil works division of Fayat Group: FAYAT, an independent family group, is France's 4th largest construction and civil engineering company. It consists of seven core business areas: building and public works, steelworks, electricity, electronics and IT, road equipment, material handling, hoisting equipment & pressure vessels.
Scemar	
Bati Service	BATI SERVICE's activity covers the whole of Cameroon. For over 20 years, BATI SERVICE has successfully carried out in Cameroon and in all the provinces of the country, major reference works (new constructions and renovations)

Asquini-Encorad	
Geovic Cameroon	
Pecten	
Perenco	Perenco has operated in Cameroon since 1993 in close collaboration with the Société Nationale des Hydrocarbures (National Hydrocarbons Company). The producing operations of Perenco in Cameroon are based around concessions in Rio del Rey, Moudi and Ebome. Perenco also manages four shared production contracts: three are already in production (Bolongo, Dissoni, Moabi) while one remains at an exploratory stage in the Rio del Rey Basin. In 2018 Perenco and the SNH chose to develop the LNG (Liquified Natural Gas) market thanks to FLNG Hilli Episeyo (Floating LNG), the first floating liquefaction plant in the world, located off Kribi.
Addax Petroleum	Addax Petroleum was established in 1994 and since August 2009 has been a subsidiary of the Sinopec Group, one of the largest oil and gas producers in China, the biggest oil refiner in Asia and the third largest worldwide
SOCAPALM	1968 to 1980: Creation of Socapalm with 18 000 ha planted and 4 500 employees.
SOSUCAM	SOSUCAM (Société Sucrière du Cameroun) grows 46,207 acres of sugar cane plantations located on two sugar manufacturing sites, namely M'Bandjock and N'Koteng. SOSUCAM was created in 1965 and is now owned by the SOMDIAA Group, a French company, which holds 72.72% of its stock. Its remaining capital is distributed among the Cameroonian Government and Cameroonian private shareholders including SOSUCAM employees. Its corporate headquarters are located in Yaoundé.
Societe Camerounaise de Raffinage Maya and CIE (SCRMAYA)	The Cameroonian refining company Maya & Cie is an Argo industrial complex specialized in the transformation of palm oil. The Company produces and commercialize two brands of refined palm oil MAYOR and PRIMA PALM as well as two other brands of household soap like MAYOR SOAP and the MAY SOAP .
Chococam Tiger Brands	Founded in 1967, Chococam manufactures cocoa-based consumer products in its factory in Douala and sells these highly popular products in Cameroon, Nigeria and other countries of Central and West Africa.
Cimencam	Cimencam created in 1963 is a subsidiary of French of building materials Lafarge . It produces and sells Cameroon 's cement , the aggregates and concrete ready. It includes three factories: a grinding station located in Bonabéri on the banks of

	the Wouri river in Douala , an integrated cement plant in Figuil in the North region and a concrete plant located in Olembé in central Cameroon.
Azur Soap Factory	
LA Pasta Cameroun	Created in 2001, LA PASTA SA comprises two production units. The first unit, with a capacity of 15 T / day, dedicated to the production of quality pasta superior, is at BONABERI-Douala near the headquarters. The second unit, with a capacity of 320 T / day, is a flour mill dedicated to manufacturing wheat flour enriched with Iron, Folic Acid, Zinc and Vitamin B12. In a decade, LA PASTA SA has risen among the leaders both in pasta only in wheat flour. This performance was possible thanks to the emphasis placed on the quality and availability of products.
Green Nature Beauty	
OK Foods Cam	Created in February 1998, OK FOODS CAMEROON is an agrifood industry evolving in the confectionery, biscuit, dairy and chips segments. Based in Douala, the economic capital of the country, it is a subsidiary of the MICRODIS group. When it was launched, the company was exclusively involved in the importation of cookies and dairy products. In her growth project, she begins local production.
Panzani Cam	
SICALIA (Société Industrielle Camerounaise de Liquides Alimentaires)	Since 2002, SICALIA (Société Industrielle Camerounaise de Liquides Alimentaires), has settled in Cameroon , in Douala in the Bassa Industrial Zone SICALIA is located in the Bassa Industrial Zone, in Douala. We also have a depot in Yaoundé in order to be closer to our customers
Sodiacam	The SODIACAM is wholesale food distributor (intended for food professionals, such as restaurants, communities ...) and retail (for individuals) in Douala and Yaounde. The SODIACAM has in these two cities a store Leader Price, which are distributed in the products of this brand but also other imported brands and local products. The Leader Price store in Douala has 4 cases.
Palmol Plantation	Palmol plantation LTD is located in Douala, Cameroon. Company is working in Food manufacturing business activities.
Vision Bionaturals	Deals in the transformation of agricultural products into medicinal and consumable foods

Appendix 5: The Global Competitiveness Index

2.1: Country/Economy Profiles

Cameroon

Key indicators, 2013

Population (millions).....	22.0
GDP (US\$ billions).....	28.0
GDP per capita (US\$).....	1,271
GDP (PPP) as share (%) of world total.....	0.06

GDP (PPP) per capita (int'l \$), 1990–2013

Global Competitiveness Index

	Rank (out of 144)	Score (1–7)
GCI 2014–2015.....	116	3.7
GCI 2013–2014 (out of 148).....	115	3.7
GCI 2012–2013 (out of 144).....	112	3.7
GCI 2011–2012 (out of 142).....	116	3.6
Basic requirements (60.0%).....	116	3.8
Institutions.....	91	3.5
Infrastructure.....	126	2.5
Macroeconomic environment.....	90	4.4
Health and primary education.....	112	4.7
Efficiency enhancers (35.0%).....	113	3.5
Higher education and training.....	117	3.2
Goods market efficiency.....	113	4.0
Labor market efficiency.....	81	4.1
Financial market development.....	108	3.5
Technological readiness.....	120	2.8
Market size.....	91	3.3
Innovation and sophistication factors (5.0%).....	84	3.5
Business sophistication.....	98	3.7
Innovation.....	71	3.3

Stage of development

The most problematic factors for doing business

Note: From the list of factors above, respondents were asked to select the five most problematic for doing business in their country and to rank them between

Cameroon

The Global Competitiveness Index in detail

INDICATOR	VALUE RANK/144	INDICATOR	VALUE RANK/144
1st pillar: Institutions		6th pillar: Goods market efficiency (cont'd.)	
1.01 Property rights	3.6 99	6.06 No. procedures to start a business*	5 32
1.02 Intellectual property protection	3.4 87	6.07 No. days to start a business*	15.0 75
1.03 Diversion of public funds	2.4 121	6.08 Agricultural policy costs.....	3.3 112
1.04 Public trust in politicians.....	2.6 87	6.09 Prevalence of trade barriers	3.9 120
1.05 Irregular payments and bribes	3.1 115	6.10 Trade tariffs, % duty*	14.3 132
1.06 Judicial independence.....	2.8 113	6.11 Prevalence of foreign ownership.....	4.8 61
1.07 Favoritism in decisions of government officials	2.8 92	6.12 Business impact of rules on FDI	4.5 69
1.08 Wastefulness of government spending.....	2.8 86	6.13 Burden of customs procedures	3.6 90
1.09 Burden of government regulation.....	3.4 79	6.14 Imports as a percentage of GDP*	33.9 104
1.10 Efficiency of legal framework in settling disputes	3.5 78	6.15 Degree of customer orientation	4.2 96
1.11 Efficiency of legal framework in challenging regs.	3.3 74	6.16 Buyer sophistication.....	2.8 123
1.12 Transparency of government policymaking.....	4.0 62	7th pillar: Labor market efficiency	
1.13 Business costs of terrorism	5.0 87	7.01 Cooperation in labor-employer relations	3.6 128
1.14 Business costs of crime and violence.....	4.4 72	7.02 Flexibility of wage determination.....	4.7 98
1.15 Organized crime.....	4.6 79	7.03 Hiring and firing practices.....	4.2 38
1.16 Reliability of police services.....	4.3 62	7.04 Redundancy costs, weeks of salary*	15.3 72
1.17 Ethical behavior of firms	3.7 97	7.05 Effect of taxation on incentives to work.....	3.5 84
1.18 Strength of auditing and reporting standards	3.9 115	7.06 Pay and productivity.....	3.4 114
1.19 Efficacy of corporate boards	4.8 54	7.07 Reliance on professional management	3.6 109
1.20 Protection of minority shareholders' interests	3.9 86	7.08 Country capacity to retain talent.....	3.0 102
1.21 Strength of investor protection, 0–10 (best)*	4.3 105	7.09 Country capacity to attract talent	2.9 101
7.10 Women in labor force, ratio to men*.....	0.85 55	8th pillar: Financial market development	
2nd pillar: Infrastructure		8.01 Availability of financial services	3.8 106
2.01 Quality of overall infrastructure	3.2 116	8.02 Affordability of financial services	3.7 109
2.02 Quality of roads.....	2.9 116	8.03 Financing through local equity market.....	2.9 101
2.03 Quality of railroad infrastructure	2.8 63	8.04 Ease of access to loans	2.5 92
2.04 Quality of port infrastructure	3.6 95	8.05 Venture capital availability	2.3 102
2.05 Quality of air transport infrastructure.....	3.3 118	8.06 Soundness of banks.....	4.5 92
2.06 Available airline seat km/week, millions*	51.4 99	8.07 Regulation of securities exchanges.....	2.9 126
2.07 Quality of electricity supply	2.4 126	8.08 Legal rights index, 0–10 (best)*	6 63
2.08 Mobile telephone subscriptions/100 pop.*	70.4 123	9th pillar: Technological readiness	
2.09 Fixed telephone lines/100 pop.*	3.6 109	9.01 Availability of latest technologies	4.1 112
3rd pillar: Macroeconomic environment		9.02 Firm-level technology absorption.....	4.4 84
3.01 Government budget balance, % GDP*.....	-4.2 95	9.03 FDI and technology transfer	4.4 83
3.02 Gross national savings, % GDP*	16.2 96	9.04 Individuals using Internet, %*	6.4 127
3.03 Inflation, annual % change*	2.1 1	9.05 Fixed broadband Internet subscriptions/100 pop.*	0.1 130
3.04 General government debt, % GDP*	18.6 16	9.06 Int'l Internet bandwidth, kb/s per user*	3.2 130
3.05 Country credit rating, 0–100 (best)*.....	25.9 118	9.07 Mobile broadband subscriptions/100 pop.*.....	0.0 133
4th pillar: Health and primary education		10th pillar: Market size	
4.01 Malaria cases/100,000 pop.*	17,051.0 58	10.01 Domestic market size index, 1–7 (best)*.....	3.1 85
4.02 Business impact of malaria	3.8 59	10.02 Foreign market size index, 1–7 (best)*.....	3.8 99
4.03 Tuberculosis cases/100,000 pop.*.....	238.0 125	10.03 GDP (PPP\$ billions)*	53.3 88
4.04 Business impact of tuberculosis.....	4.1 127	10.04 Exports as a percentage of GDP*	23.0 124
4.05 HIV prevalence, % adult pop.*	4.5 131	11th pillar: Business sophistication	
4.06 Business impact of HIV/AIDS	4.0 124	11.01 Local supplier quantity.....	4.4 93
4.07 Infant mortality, deaths/1,000 live births*	61.1 131	11.02 Local supplier quality.....	3.9 103
4.08 Life expectancy, years*.....	54.6 134	11.03 State of cluster development.....	3.5 87
4.09 Quality of primary education.....	3.7 81	11.04 Nature of competitive advantage.....	3.2 97
4.10 Primary education enrollment, net %*	91.5 93	11.05 Value chain breadth.....	4.0 48
5th pillar: Higher education and training		11.06 Control of international distribution	3.4 125
5.01 Secondary education enrollment, gross %*	50.4 121	11.07 Production process sophistication	3.5 93
5.02 Tertiary education enrollment, gross %*.....	11.9 110	11.08 Extent of marketing	3.8 98
5.03 Quality of the education system	3.8 62	11.09 Willingness to delegate authority.....	3.4 108
5.04 Quality of math and science education	4.3 65	12th pillar: Innovation	
5.05 Quality of management schools.....	4.4 58	12.01 Capacity for innovation.....	3.8 64
5.06 Internet access in schools.....	2.7 127	12.02 Quality of scientific research institutions.....	3.5 83
5.07 Availability of research and training services.....	4.0 77	12.03 Company spending on R&D.....	3.3 53
5.08 Extent of staff training	4.0 69	12.04 University-industry collaboration in R&D	3.4 82
6th pillar: Goods market efficiency		12.05 Gov't procurement of advanced tech products.....	3.8 41
6.01 Intensity of local competition	4.6 109	12.06 Availability of scientists and engineers.....	4.1 64
6.02 Extent of market dominance	3.8 65	12.07 PCT patents, applications/million pop.*	0.1 107
6.03 Effectiveness of anti-monopoly policy.....	3.9 78		
6.04 Effect of taxation on incentives to invest.....	3.4 98		
6.05 Total tax rate, % profits*	48.8 108		

Cameroon

The Global Competitiveness Index in detail

INDICATOR	VALUE RANK/144	INDICATOR	VALUE RANK/144
1st pillar: Institutions		6th pillar: Goods market efficiency (cont'd.)	
1.01 Property rights	3.6 99	6.06 No. procedures to start a business*	5 32
1.02 Intellectual property protection	3.4 87	6.07 No. days to start a business*	15.0 75
1.03 Diversion of public funds	2.4 121	6.08 Agricultural policy costs.....	3.3 112
1.04 Public trust in politicians.....	2.6 87	6.09 Prevalence of trade barriers	3.9 120
1.05 Irregular payments and bribes	3.1 115	6.10 Trade tariffs, % duty*	14.3 132
1.06 Judicial independence.....	2.8 113	6.11 Prevalence of foreign ownership.....	4.8 61
1.07 Favoritism in decisions of government officials	2.8 92	6.12 Business impact of rules on FDI	4.5 69
1.08 Wastefulness of government spending.....	2.8 86	6.13 Burden of customs procedures	3.6 90
1.09 Burden of government regulation.....	3.4 79	6.14 Imports as a percentage of GDP*	33.9 104
1.10 Efficiency of legal framework in settling disputes	3.5 78	6.15 Degree of customer orientation	4.2 96
1.11 Efficiency of legal framework in challenging regs.	3.3 74	6.16 Buyer sophistication.....	2.8 123
1.12 Transparency of government policymaking.....	4.0 62	7th pillar: Labor market efficiency	
1.13 Business costs of terrorism	5.0 87	7.01 Cooperation in labor-employer relations	3.6 128
1.14 Business costs of crime and violence.....	4.4 72	7.02 Flexibility of wage determination.....	4.7 98
1.15 Organized crime.....	4.6 79	7.03 Hiring and firing practices.....	4.2 38
1.16 Reliability of police services.....	4.3 62	7.04 Redundancy costs, weeks of salary*	15.3 72
1.17 Ethical behavior of firms	3.7 97	7.05 Effect of taxation on incentives to work.....	3.5 84
1.18 Strength of auditing and reporting standards	3.9 115	7.06 Pay and productivity.....	3.4 114
1.19 Efficacy of corporate boards	4.8 54	7.07 Reliance on professional management	3.6 109
1.20 Protection of minority shareholders' interests	3.9 86	7.08 Country capacity to retain talent.....	3.0 102
1.21 Strength of investor protection, 0–10 (best)*	4.3 105	7.09 Country capacity to attract talent	2.9 101
7.10 Women in labor force, ratio to men*.....	0.85 55	8th pillar: Financial market development	
2nd pillar: Infrastructure		8.01 Availability of financial services	3.8 106
2.01 Quality of overall infrastructure	3.2 116	8.02 Affordability of financial services	3.7 109
2.02 Quality of roads.....	2.9 116	8.03 Financing through local equity market.....	2.9 101
2.03 Quality of railroad infrastructure	2.8 63	8.04 Ease of access to loans	2.5 92
2.04 Quality of port infrastructure	3.6 95	8.05 Venture capital availability	2.3 102
2.05 Quality of air transport infrastructure.....	3.3 118	8.06 Soundness of banks.....	4.5 92
2.06 Available airline seat km/week, millions*	51.4 99	8.07 Regulation of securities exchanges.....	2.9 126
2.07 Quality of electricity supply	2.4 126	8.08 Legal rights index, 0–10 (best)*	6 63
2.08 Mobile telephone subscriptions/100 pop.*	70.4 123	9th pillar: Technological readiness	
2.09 Fixed telephone lines/100 pop.*	3.6 109	9.01 Availability of latest technologies	4.1 112
3rd pillar: Macroeconomic environment		9.02 Firm-level technology absorption.....	4.4 84
3.01 Government budget balance, % GDP*.....	-4.2 95	9.03 FDI and technology transfer	4.4 83
3.02 Gross national savings, % GDP*	16.2 96	9.04 Individuals using Internet, %*	6.4 127
3.03 Inflation, annual % change*	2.1 1	9.05 Fixed broadband Internet subscriptions/100 pop.*	0.1 130
3.04 General government debt, % GDP*	18.6 16	9.06 Int'l Internet bandwidth, kb/s per user*	3.2 130
3.05 Country credit rating, 0–100 (best)*.....	25.9 118	9.07 Mobile broadband subscriptions/100 pop.*.....	0.0 133
4th pillar: Health and primary education		10th pillar: Market size	
4.01 Malaria cases/100,000 pop.*	17,051.0 58	10.01 Domestic market size index, 1–7 (best)*.....	3.1 85
4.02 Business impact of malaria	3.8 59	10.02 Foreign market size index, 1–7 (best)*.....	3.8 99
4.03 Tuberculosis cases/100,000 pop.*.....	238.0 125	10.03 GDP (PPP\$ billions)*	53.3 88
4.04 Business impact of tuberculosis.....	4.1 127	10.04 Exports as a percentage of GDP*	23.0 124
4.05 HIV prevalence, % adult pop.*	4.5 131	11th pillar: Business sophistication	
4.06 Business impact of HIV/AIDS	4.0 124	11.01 Local supplier quantity.....	4.4 93
4.07 Infant mortality, deaths/1,000 live births*	61.1 131	11.02 Local supplier quality.....	3.9 103
4.08 Life expectancy, years*.....	54.6 134	11.03 State of cluster development.....	3.5 87
4.09 Quality of primary education.....	3.7 81	11.04 Nature of competitive advantage.....	3.2 97
4.10 Primary education enrollment, net %*	91.5 93	11.05 Value chain breadth.....	4.0 48
5th pillar: Higher education and training		11.06 Control of international distribution	3.4 125
5.01 Secondary education enrollment, gross %*	50.4 121	11.07 Production process sophistication	3.5 93
5.02 Tertiary education enrollment, gross %*.....	11.9 110	11.08 Extent of marketing	3.8 98
5.03 Quality of the education system	3.8 62	11.09 Willingness to delegate authority.....	3.4 108
5.04 Quality of math and science education	4.3 65	12th pillar: Innovation	
5.05 Quality of management schools.....	4.4 58	12.01 Capacity for innovation.....	3.8 64
5.06 Internet access in schools.....	2.7 127	12.02 Quality of scientific research institutions.....	3.5 83
5.07 Availability of research and training services.....	4.0 77	12.03 Company spending on R&D.....	3.3 53
5.08 Extent of staff training	4.0 69	12.04 University-industry collaboration in R&D	3.4 82
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